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DREPT / LAW

Eastern Partnership: EU-Moldova

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Abstract: The article presents the relations between Moldova and the European Union in the framework of the Eastern Partnership. The established relations comprise individual and bilateral initiatives, being developed by the Action Plan, the instruments of the European Neighbourhood Policy and of the Association Agreement. There are analysed the legal foundations, political, economic, social and cultural relations between the European Union and Moldova. The research makes incursions on strengths and vulnerabilities, which are inherent and implacable for EU-Moldovan relations.

Keywords: Association Agreement, cooperation, the European Union, Eastern Partnership, Moldova, Neighbourhood Policy.

Introduction. The topic concerning how Europe is seen by human and social sciences represents a very complex and daring approach. Throughout its history Europe has been considered as the “Old Continent”, the cradle of civilization, the land of prosperity, and, for the last sixty year period, the land of peace. Europe, embodied by the European Union, is a large family of peoples committed to promote common values.

The preamble provisions of the *Treaty on European Union* are very emblematic, asserting “a new stage in the process of European integration (...), drawing inspiration from the cultural, religious and humanist inheritance of Europe, from which have developed the universal values of the inviolable and inalienable rights of the human person, freedom, democracy, equality and the rule of law, recalling the historic importance of the ending of the division of the European continent and the need to create firm bases for the construction of the future Europe, confirming their attachment to the principles of liberty, democracy and respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms and of the rule of law, confirming their attachment to fundamental social rights (...), desiring to deepen the solidarity between their peoples while respecting their history (...), determined to promote economic and social progress for their peoples (...),

resolved to establish a citizenship common to nationals of their countries, resolved to implement a common foreign and security policy including the progressive framing of a common defence policy, which might lead to a common defence (...), thereby reinforcing the European identity and its independence in order to promote peace, security and progress in Europe and in the world, resolved to facilitate the free movement of persons, while ensuring the safety and security of their peoples, by establishing an area of freedom, security and justice (...), resolved to continue the process of creating an ever closer union among the peoples of Europe, in which decisions are taken as closely as possible to the citizen in accordance with the principle of subsidiarity, in view of further steps to be taken in order to advance European integration”¹.

Article 1 (ex Article 1 TEU) establishes the European Union on the basis of the European Community and lays out the legal value of the treaties: “the high contracting parties establish among themselves a European Union (...) on which the Member States confer competences to attain objectives they have in common. This Treaty marks a new stage in the process of creating an ever closer union among the peoples of Europe, in which decisions are taken as openly as possible and as closely as possible to the citizen”².

Article 2 states that the European Union is “founded on the values of respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and respect for human rights, including the rights of persons belonging to minorities. These values are common to the Member States in a society in which pluralism, non-discrimination, tolerance, justice, solidarity and equality between women and men prevail”³.

Article 3 (ex Article 2 TEU) states the aims of the European Union: “(1) the Union's aim is to promote peace, its values and the well-being of its peoples. (2) The Union shall offer its citizens an area of freedom, security and justice without internal frontiers, in which the free movement of persons is ensured in conjunction with appropriate measures with respect to external border controls, asylum, immigration and the prevention and combating of crime. (3) The Union shall establish an internal market. It shall

¹ *Consolidated Version of the Treaty on European Union*, 15-16.

² *Ibidem*, 16.

³ *Ibidem*, 17.

work for the sustainable development of Europe based on balanced economic growth and price stability, a highly competitive social market economy, aiming at full employment and social progress, and a high level of protection and improvement of the quality of the environment. It shall promote scientific and technological advance. It shall combat social exclusion and discrimination, and shall promote social justice and protection, equality between women and men, solidarity between generations and protection of the rights of the child. It shall promote economic, social and territorial cohesion, and solidarity among Member States. It shall respect its rich cultural and linguistic diversity, and shall ensure that Europe's cultural heritage is safeguarded and enhanced. (4) The Union shall establish an economic and monetary union whose currency is the euro. (5) In its relations with the wider world, the Union shall uphold and promote its values and interests and contribute to the protection of its citizens. It shall contribute to peace, security, the sustainable development of the Earth, solidarity and mutual respect among peoples, free and fair trade, eradication of poverty and the protection of human rights, in particular the rights of the child, as well as to the strict observance and the development of international law, including respect for the principles of the United Nations Charter. (6) The Union shall pursue its objectives by appropriate means commensurate with the competences which are conferred upon it in the Treaties"⁴.

One of the European Union's interests is to promote peaceful cooperation and partnership relations with other countries as well. These relations differ in content according to degree of proximity, interest (in a wider sense) and strategic policy. Moldova, one of the European Union's neighbours, seems to be privileged by its geographical position and European cultural heritage. In the same time Moldova seems to be in the centre of geopolitical games in the region, even if it is one of the smallest countries in Europe and one of the most peaceful countries in the world. Moreover, Moldova has a short experience of independence, which makes it very vulnerable in face of neighbouring countries.

EU-Moldova relations are very complex in nature, *de jure* and *de facto*. The framework of EU-Moldova relations face certain potential

⁴ Ibidem, 17.

challenges, which have to be taken into consideration in the development of the strategic partnership between the European Union and Moldova.

Association Agreement can be a salvation for Moldova in the Eastern turmoil or a definite disappearance from the map of Europe; it depends entirely on the European Union, the United States of America and NATO, and, of course, the will of Moldova's people.

Rationale. EU-Moldova relations are of great importance now when Europe's security seems to be threatened by external factors.

Geographically and historically, Moldova is a part of Europe; geographically, because Moldova is situated on the European continent and, historically, because the Romanian nation lives both in Romania and in Moldova. A larger part of the Romanians lives inside the European Union, the other part, due to the vicissitudes of modern history, lives outside the European Union, i.e. in Moldova. These geographical, historical and spiritual nuances of culturally belonging to Europe, but, in the same time, outside the EU community shapes *volens-nolens* the EU-Moldova relations with all related issues referring to bilateral cooperation or relations with other actors in the region or worldwide.

Consequently, the research will embrace an interdisciplinary approach in dealing with EU-Moldova relations to fit the objectives and comprehensiveness of the investigation. It is a perspective, which is seen with Eastern Europe eyes.

The interest on EU-Moldova relations focuses on legal, political, economic, and cultural, perspectives in building a lasting partnership, on the one hand. On the other hand, strengths and vulnerabilities are considered as well.

Cooperation Relations. Multiple approaches characterise EU-Moldova relations in a wider sense. Nevertheless the most important levels of cooperation between the EU and Moldova refer to legal framework, political aspirations, economic and trading affairs, cultural appropriateness.

Legal Relations. The relations between the European Union and Moldova are shaped by the European Neighbourhood Policy that is a foreign policy instrument of the European Union for external border countries to bring closer European neighbours.

Legal foundations of EU-Moldova relations were formally launched by signing the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement (PCA) on November 28, 1994, which entered into force on July 01, 1998, for a 10 year period.

The European Neighbourhood Policy was developed in 2004 to strengthen stability, security and prosperity of all partners. The European Neighbourhood Policy is based on the values of democracy, rule of law and respect of human rights. The European Neighbourhood Policy is proposed for 16 countries in the South (Algeria, Egypt, Israel, Jordan, Lebanon, Libya, Morocco, Palestine, Syria and Tunisia) and in the East (Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Georgia, Moldova and Ukraine). The aim of the European Neighbourhood Policy is to promote good governance and social development in the neighbouring countries through: closer political links, partial economic integration, support to meet EU standards and assistance with economic and social reforms. The European Neighbourhood Policy covers four action areas to: (1) strengthen the rule of law, (2) democracy and respect for human rights, (3) promote market-oriented economic reforms, (4) promote employment and social cohesion and cooperate on key foreign policy objectives such as countering-terrorism and the non-proliferation of weapons of mass destruction.

The financial instrument is the European Neighbourhood and Partnership Instrument (2007-2013) to promote the established objectives of the European neighbourhood policy⁵.

The European Neighbourhood Policy is an adequate response to a changing neighbourhood. In 2010, Štefan Füle, Commissioner for Enlargement and European Neighbourhood Policy, said: "The ENP is a win-win game: the higher our partners' reform ambitions, the stronger our response. Economic reforms have progressed remarkably across our neighbourhood, both East and South. What is essential for the future is to go up a gear on democratic and political reforms, where progress has been real but generally slower"⁶. In 2011, Catherine Ashton, EU High Representative for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy, said: "What we are launching today is a new approach. A partnership between peoples aimed at

⁵ Regulation (EC) No 1638/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 October 2006 laying down general provisions establishing a European Neighbourhood and Partnership Instrument

⁶ http://www.enpi-info.eu/main.php?id=344&id_type=2

promoting and supporting the development of deep democracy and economic prosperity in our neighbourhood. This is in all our interests. We will make funding available for countries in our neighbourhood to support and match the speed of political and economic reform they wish to make. Our support is based on partnership, not on imposition. It is a relationship based on mutual accountability which cuts both ways where each side will hold the other to account against agreed goals and objectives”⁷.

A new and more ambitious European Neighbourhood Policy develops the partnership for democracy and shared prosperity with more funds for more reform. The new European Neighbourhood Policy has a strong focus on democracy and inclusive economic development. The new financial tool of the European Neighbourhood Policy is the European Neighbourhood Instrument (ENI)⁸, which replaces the European Neighbourhood and Partnership Instrument (2007-2013). The European Neighbourhood Instrument (ENI) is designed for the period 2014-2020 in the European Union’s financial framework.

The provisions of article 2 refers to the article 8 of the Treaty on European Union (TEU) which provides that the Union is to develop a special relationship with neighbouring countries, aiming to establish an area of prosperity and good neighbourliness, founded on the values of the Union and characterised by close and peaceful relations based on cooperation⁹.

The provisions of article 3 provide that under the European Neighbourhood Policy (ENP), the Union offers European Neighbourhood countries a privileged relationship, building upon a mutual commitment to, and promotion of, the values of democracy and human rights, the rule of law, good governance and the principles of a market economy and sustainable and inclusive development. It further provides, where appropriate, a framework for enhanced mobility and people-to-people contacts, particularly through visa facilitation and readmission agreements, and, on a case-by-case basis, through visa liberalisation¹⁰.

⁷ Ibidem

⁸ *Regulation (EU) No 232/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 March 2014 establishing a European Neighbourhood Instrument*

⁹ Ibidem, p. 27

¹⁰ Ibidem

The European Neighbourhood Instrument (ENI) articulates express provisions on the special relationship and the privileged relationship of the European Union with neighbouring countries, reiterating commitment to and promotion of values of democracy, respect of human rights, the rule of law, good governance, market economy, sustainable development, to establish an area of prosperity and peace.

The European Neighbourhood Policy works on bilateral Action Plans or Association Agendas between the European Union and neighbouring partners among which is Moldova.

A joint EU-Moldova ENP Action Plan contains specific objectives based on commitments to shared values and development of reforms¹¹. The EU-Moldova ENP Action Plan is based on the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement (PCA), which establishes the legal framework for EU-Moldova relationship. The Partnership and Cooperation Agreement was signed on November 28, 1994, and entered into force on July 01, 1998, for the next 10 years. The agreement, a political document on the strategic objectives between the European Union and Moldova, provides the basis of cooperation in the political, commercial, economic, legal, cultural and scientific spheres. EU-Moldova ENP Action Plan was jointly adopted at the Cooperation Council on February 22, 2005.

EU-Moldova ENP Action Plan set a range of priorities to: sustained efforts towards a viable solution to the Transnistrian conflict; further strengthening the stability and effectiveness of institutions guaranteeing democracy and the rule of law; ensuring the democratic conduct of parliamentary elections in Moldova in accordance with European standards; ensuring respect for the freedom of the media and the freedom of expression; further reinforcing administrative and judicial capacity; resuming cooperation with IFIs; implementing actions aimed at poverty reduction, to strengthen private sector led growth and for fiscal sustainability; improving the investment climate through appropriate structural reforms aimed at ensuring non-discriminatory, transparent and predictable business conditions and by the fight against corruption; progress towards a system of efficient, comprehensive state border management on all sectors of the Moldovan border including the Transnistrian sector;

¹¹ *EU-Moldova Action Plan*, 32 p.

working towards the EU granting Autonomous Trade Preferences, by ensuring effective control of the origin of goods from Moldova; stepping up the fight against organised crime, including trafficking in human beings; ensuring the efficient management of migratory flows, including initiating the process towards conclusion of a readmission agreement between the European Community and Moldova¹².

The Eastern Partnership is a joint initiative of the European Union and six countries of Eastern Europe (Belarus, Moldova and Ukraine) and Southern Caucasus (Armenia, Azerbaijan, and Georgia), which was launched in 2009. The Eastern Partnership works in the framework of the European Neighbourhood Policy aiming at deepening political cooperation and economic integration. The Eastern Partnership is based on common values of democracy, rule of law, respect of human rights and commitment to market economy. The Eastern Partnership covers two dimensions: bilateral – developing closer cooperation between the European Union and partner country; multilateral – bringing partners closer within framework for exchange and cooperation.

Bilateral dimension consists of six aspects: new contractual relations, integration into the European Union's economy, easier travel to the European Union, energy and transport cooperation, economic and social development, and financial support.

Among all Eastern Partnership countries Moldova benefits from all six mentioned aspects in developing closer cooperation with the European Union.

In 2010 Moldova began negotiating the Association Agreement (AA) with the European Union, including a Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Area. In 2013 Moldova initialled the Association Agreement with the European Union¹³, on the occasion of the Eastern Partnership Summit in Vilnius.

A recent achievement is that the European Union included Moldova to the list of third countries whose nationals are exempt from visa

¹² Ibidem, p. 3

¹³ *Association Agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Moldova, of the other part*, 984 p.

requirement. The amendment¹⁴ of *Council Regulation (EC) No 539/2001 of 15 March 2001 listing the third countries whose nationals must be in possession of visas when crossing the external borders and those whose nationals are exempt from that requirement* entered into force on April 28, 2014, thereby abolishing visa requirements for Moldovan citizens who want to travel to the Schengen zone for a short-stay and hold a biometric passport: “This Regulation shall be binding in its entirety and directly applicable in the Member States in accordance with the Treaties”¹⁵.

On this occasion, Cecilia Malmstrom, Commissioner for Home Affairs, said: “By the end of the month Moldovan citizens with a biometric passport will not need a visa anymore to travel to the Schengen zone for short-stays. This is a great achievement and the beginning of a new chapter in our relations. We launched our Visa Dialogue with Moldova on June 2010, and less than four years later travelling to the Schengen zone without a visa will become a reality for Moldovan citizens. This shows that the efforts by the Moldovan authorities have paid off and that the EU is committed to deliver on engagements with third countries wishing to work with us. The possibility to visa-free travel to the Schengen area for short stays will further facilitate people-to-people contacts and strengthen business, social and cultural ties between the European Union and Moldova. This is also an excellent example for other countries of the region, demonstrating that a strong political commitment and the effective implementation of reforms bring tangible results”¹⁶.

In the result Moldova signed the Association Agreement with the European Union in 2014.

Political Relations. Moldovan political and diplomatic relations with the European Union and Member States began to develop immediately when Moldova became a subject of international law. Political and legal

¹⁴ *Regulation (EU) No 259/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 3 April 2014 amending Council Regulation (EC) No 539/2001 listing the third countries whose nationals must be in possession of visas when crossing the external borders and those whose nationals are exempt from that requirement*, pp. 9-11

¹⁵ *Ibidem*, p. 11

¹⁶ <http://eumoldovadiologue.eu/commissioner-malmstrom-on-visa-free-travel-for-moldova-this-is-a-great-achievement/>

foundations of EU-Moldova relations were formally launched by signing the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement (PCA) on November 28, 1994.

Thus, the legal foundations of the political dialogue were established. The agreement contains common objectives in the following spheres: trade and economic cooperation – liberalization of trade based on Most Favoured Nation treatment and the elimination of quantitative restrictions; legislative harmonisation (provisions governing goods, services, labour, and capital, as well as competition and intellectual property protection, aiming at bringing Moldova in line with the legal framework of the single European market); cooperation in the fields of science and technology, energy, environment, transport, postal services and telecommunications and a range of other areas such as education and training, social and cultural cooperation; political dialogue on domestic, regional and international issues of mutual concern such as observance of principles of democracy and human rights and political stability in the region (particularly related to the Transnistrian region); cooperation in justice and home affairs – money laundering, measures to counter illicit production, and the fight against drugs.

EU-Moldova ENP Action Plan of 2005 contributed greatly to deepening the EU-Moldova political dialogue.

The institutional framework of political relations is determined by the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement (PCA) including: the Co-operation Council (annual) at Ministerial / Commissioner level (EU-Presidency, European Commission, High Representative, Government of Moldova) has the overall responsibility for the running of the PCA; Cooperation Committee meets at senior civil servants level and is chaired alternately by the European Commission and the Moldovan side; Sub-Committees meet at specialised experts' level and support the work of the Co-operation Committee. Four subcommittees are operational: Sub-Committee on Trade and Investment; Sub-Committee on Financial, Economic and Statistical issues; Sub-Committee on Customs and Cross-border Cooperation, and Justice, Freedom and Security; Sub-Committee on Energy, environment, networks, science and technology, training, education.

The Parliamentary Co-operation Committee between the European Parliament and the Moldovan Parliament has as a rule two meetings a year, one in Brussels and one in Chisinau.

Within the Council of the European Union, the Council Working Group on Eastern Europe and Central Asia develops institutional relations with Moldova.

In 2011 Moldova officially received an “action plan” toward the establishment of a visa-free regime for short-stay travel in the European Union and in 2014 the *Regulation (EU) No 259/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 3 April 2014 amending Council Regulation (EC) No 539/2001 listing the third countries whose nationals must be in possession of visas when crossing the external borders and those whose nationals are exempt from that requirement* made possible abolishing visa requirements for Moldovan citizens, holders of biometric passports.

The Delegation of the European Union to Moldova was opened in 2005 to promote political and economic relations. The Delegation of the European Union to Moldova has a status of a diplomatic mission, representing officially the European Union in Moldova.

Moldovan political and society aspirations converge to integration of the country in the European Union, defined as a political and economic union.

EU-Moldova political relations are crucially determined by legal foundations between the European Union and Moldova.

Economic and Trade Relations. Moldova developed progressively its economic and trade relations over the past 20 years. Legal foundations for economic and trade affairs has been the Partnership Cooperation Agreement of 1994. Later on EU-Moldova Action Plan used to play an important role. Negotiations for a Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Agreement (DCFTA) include market access and regulatory spheres of mutual EU-Moldova interests.

The European Union is the first trading partner with over 54% of Moldova’s total trade. The European Union’s exports to Moldova constitute € 2 billion (2012), while its imports from Moldova represent € 940 million (2012). Trading with Moldova is 0.1% of the European Union’s overall trade¹⁷.

It turns out that economic and trade relations between the European Union and Moldova have grown constantly and irreversibly towards a

¹⁷ <http://ec.europa.eu/trade/policy/countries-and-regions/countries/moldova/>

positive development for both parts. From the economic point of view, the European Union is the strategic partner of Moldova.

Cultural Relations. The cultural heritage of Europe is rich and diverse. Even nowadays Moldova is outside the European Union; its culture is European *per se*. The European nature of Moldova's culture originates in geographical, linguistic, historical and civilisational characteristics. Geographically, Moldova is situated on the European continent. Linguistically, the mother tongue of the people of Moldova is Romanian, a language belonging to Italic (Romance, Latin, Romanic, Neo-Latin) languages.

Moreover, Romanian is one of the twenty-four official languages of the European Union that promotes language learning and linguistic diversity.

Historically, the people of Moldova inhabited the land of their ancestors; in the past the territory of Moldova was a part of the historical Moldova, which had tight linguistic and spiritual connections with Wallachia and Transylvania, forming in the modern history the unitary Romanian nation-state.

Civilisationally, Moldova belongs to the European civilisation. Synthetically, it is worth mentioning that by its art, science, philosophy, religion, cuisine, clothing, sport, Moldova's culture is a European culture *par excellence*. José Manuel Durão Barroso, the President of the European Commission, in his speech *European Union and Moldova: a journey to share* underlined that culturally Moldova belongs to Europe: "There is no doubt that Moldova belongs to Europe and that it already now shares a common culture, language and history with the European Union. I have said it and I can repeat it: we see Moldovans as Europeans, you belong to our family of nations"¹⁸.

Strengths. Legal, political, economic and cultural foundations shape the quintessential strengths of EU-Moldova relations, which are complex and supportive. It is worth mentioning the multi-level support by the European Union to Moldova.

Cooperation examples are relevant:

¹⁸ José Manuel Durão Barroso, *European Union and Moldova: a journey to share*, European Commission - SPEECH/12/888, 11/30/2012

- helping to build capacity in the Moldovan public administration and supporting the strengthening of public financial management systems in line with EU best practice;
- helping the poor segments of the Moldovan population to cope with the increases in gas prices, through the provision of budgetary support helping the government to strengthen social compensation schemes;
- helping to restructure and upgrade the water sector that more people get access to clean drinking water;
- through joint programmes with the Council of Europe to improve the rule of law, the independence of the judiciary and respect for human rights in Moldova;
- trade access to the European market through the generous Autonomous Trade Preferences (ATP) scheme, which means that the EU lifts trade tariffs for all Moldovan products except those clearly specified in the ATP regulation, for which only a quota is tariff-free;
- providing technical support for improvements to health and phyto-sanitary systems which would allow Moldovan food products access to the EU market;
- agreements on visa facilitation and readmission that facilitate visa procedures, whilst at the same time fight illegal migration are in force since 1 January 2008. Member States agreed to strive to set up in 2010 a dialogue examining the conditions for visa-free travel of Moldovan citizens to the EU as a long-term goal, taking into account the EU Global Approach to Migration and keeping in mind that gradual steps towards full visa liberalisation would be taken provided that conditions for well-managed and secure mobility were in place;
- Moldova benefits from a Mobility Partnership as one of the two pilot countries in the world. The mobility partnership offers a political framework for cooperation between the Union and third countries in the field of migration, and includes items of relevance for both the EU and interested third countries. Three major dimensions of the Global Approach – legal migration, migration and development, and fighting against illegal migration – are joined in one, coherent policy framework. The pilot Mobility Partnership with the Republic of Moldova is the best example of such well-

balanced framework. Around 40 initiatives are currently being implemented within the Mobility Partnership between EU and Moldova¹⁹.

Perhaps, the best accomplishment of EU-Moldova relations is the hope to return Moldova to Europe.

Vulnerabilities. Even EU-Moldova relations have known a consistent development over the years; however, there are certain issues to consider avoiding misinterpretation of facts. These “vulnerabilities” may come either from the European Union and Moldova or outside EU-Moldova relations from different reasons.

Member States. Member States could probably have certain reserves towards Moldova. These reserves are defined by indicators to comply with during a definite period of time on reforms, market economy, rule of law, respect of human rights, just to count several of them.

On the other side, the relationships with the European Union’s institutions are good. This is a driving force in changing positively the existing perceptions about Moldova in the European Union and, what is more important.

Moldova. EU-Moldova relations are more affected from the Moldovan side than from the European Union’s one. Misconceptions characterise attitudes towards the European Union in general and EU-Moldova relations especially.

There are certain orchestrated myths, circulating about the relations of Moldova with the European Union. They are concentrated especially on EU-Moldova Association Agreement (AA) and Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Area (DCFTA). The official website of the Delegation of the European Union to Moldova counts 32 of such myths: signing the Association Agreement poses a threat to Moldovan culture and traditional values; the Association Agreement will force Moldova to legalise gay marriage; if the Association Agreement is signed, the authorities will have to cut jobs and decrease wages, and people will lose their pensions; the Association Agreement will further enflame Russia-Moldova relations and could lead to the loss of the Transnistrian region; the Association Agreement brings little benefit to Moldova and just imposes extra demands; the EU is engaged in a

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geopolitical competition with the Russian Federation; the Association Agreement will lead to Moldova's loss of sovereignty; the signature of the Agreement will lead Moldova to immediate economic difficulties; the economic benefits of DCFTA for Moldova are negligible, while the costs of reform will be significant; Moldovan farmers will not be able to cope with the introduction of EU SPS standards and will lose out; there will be no opportunities for Moldovan exporters in the EU market; if the Association Agreement is signed, Moldova's traditional exports to Russia will be disrupted because of the adoption of European standards; by signing the Association Agreement, Moldova will lose the CIS market; Moldova-Russia trade relations are likely to worsen as a result of DCFTA; consumer prices will increase as a result of the DCFTA; Moldova will be flooded by EU goods as a result of the DCFTA; if the Agreement is not applied in Transnistria, its companies will not be able to export to the EU anymore; the Transnistrian economy will suffer after Moldova signs the Association Agreement; not applying the Association Agreement in the Transnistrian region would further divide the country; Moldova has several free trade agreements in force which the EU considers incompatible with DCFTA; the EU will benefit from DCFTA immediately, while Moldova needs to implement reforms; the DCFTA ties Moldova's hands and limits its sovereignty; Russia is afraid of an influx of goods from the EU as a result of DCFTA with Moldova, this will harm Russia-Moldova relations; only businesses will benefit from the DCFTA, not the Moldovan people; Moldova has to engage in ambitious reforms like the EU's new Member States but it does not have membership perspective; Moldova has to implement all the reforms in less time than EU Member States; the cost of reform will amount to [any figure], which is beyond our means; EU assistance is not enough to cover the reform needs; the EU will be the only true beneficiary of the Agreement as it does not need costly reforms to access the Moldovan market; Moldova will face sanctions and its products will be banned from the EU market if it does not respect the reform deadlines; the EU must do something to help SMEs, as small businesses will be hit the hardest by the reform process; the DCFTA with the EU is not better for Moldova than participation in the Customs Union.

Such myths are fabricated by third parties, which follow to undermine successful EU-Moldova relations. It is an instrument to give the

wrong impression about the European Union. Just to draw a parallel, similar myths circulated about the United States of America in the ex-Soviet Union.

Additionally, sociological instruments convey interesting data on EU-Moldova relations. Answers are extremely relevant to describe EU-Moldova relations and people's perceptions on them.

According to the sociological survey *Widening the European Dialogue in Moldova*, 98.2% of respondents answered that they have heard about the European Union. 30.2% answered that they are very much interested in what is happening in the EU. 17.5% of respondents describe EU-Moldova relations very good. 23% said that the perception of Moldova in the European Union is a positive one. On the other hand, 40.1% asserted that the perception of the European Union in Moldova is positive. 31.4% considered EU-Moldova relations equal and mutual beneficial. 39% underlined that EU-Moldova relations are improving. 50.4% stated that the European Union is interested in developing closer links with Moldova. Only 50% have heard about the Association Agreement and its initialing. 62% believe that trade with the European Union would increase by the Association Agreement. 43% responded that economic cooperation is currently developing between the European Union and Moldova and it is a successful one. The least successful (14.8%) is fighting against corruption. 35% have heard about DCTFA. DCTFA involves liberalisation of trade of goods and services (35.7%). The European Union believes that Moldova is a friendly country (80.6%). The European Union sees Moldova as a friendly country (90.1%). 41.7% describe relations between the European Union and Moldova more talking than concrete actions. Moldova could learn a lot from the European Union in relation to market economy (46.7%). The Transnistrian conflict an obstacle for Moldova's closer integration in the European Union (70.2%). The European Union and Russia cannot work together to resolve the Transnistrian conflict, they are rivals in this region (37%). Moldova's foreign policy more orientated towards the West / the European Union (46.1%). If a referendum about Moldova's future were held today, 35.9% would vote for more cooperation with Russia and Eurasian Union and only 31.8% for more cooperation with the European Union. 44.3% would choose admission to the European Union and 40.4% to the Eurasian Customs Union. When thinking about the European Union 46.8% they have in mind hope. Germany is the most liked Member State by

Moldova's people (38.2%). 70% of respondents have never visited the European Union. 79.1% have never applied for Schengen visa. 48.4% of respondents visited Russia. 46.8% believe that Moldova will become a member of the European Union and it is likely to happen between 2014 (0.4%) and 2100 (0.4%), while the highest rate is 17.7% for 2015.

The first conclusion is that the population of Moldova is informed improperly or has limited access to information of public interest.

Differentiated answers could be explained by the fact that 70.0% have never visited the European Union, 79.1% have never applied for Schengen visa and a majority of Moldova's people have visited other countries than the European Union. These facts explain to a certain extent grouping and re-grouping of answers.

One more fact could be the media influence as about 90% of TV channels in Moldova are in Russian, i.e. of Russia, a constant situation developed for over two decades.

Third Countries. EU-Moldova relations are jeopardized by a third party. The "terrible child" of contemporary international relations, is the only country, which is dissatisfied by EU-Moldova relations. There could be a lot of pretended motives, but it is not the case for them. In fact, "the terrible child" faces certain inside doubts, which should be clarified for its sake. Is the jungle law on the table? Certain issues should be taken into consideration to elucidate such a behavior. Does the international law count? Events that happen now in the Eastern Europe insinuate a state of international disorder, i.e. the international legal order has to be re-established, but when and by whom. These are just a couple of academic interrogations concerning such regional relations in Europe.

Conclusions. The background of EU-Moldova relations is explainable by geographical, historical and cultural reasons. That is the normal (natural) way of understanding the cooperation development between the European Union and Moldova.

Now EU-Moldova relations have moved to the stage when Moldova's admission to the European Union seems to be irreversible in a long run. In fact it is a historical "homecoming" of Moldova in the larger European family of free peoples. The European Union has to admit as soon as possible Moldova in the Union. Jean-Claude Juncker warned not to let Moldova become Russia's "next victim" after Ukraine, i.e. the European Union will

protect Moldova from Russia. "After the events in Ukraine it is now a matter of great urgency that the Europeans sign an association agreement with Moldova very quickly, that is, in the coming weeks". Jean-Claude Juncker backed that call, saying: "he needs to know that he cannot do in Moldova what he did in Crimea"²⁰.

In terms of security, the European Union and the United States of America have to replace the Russian military bases in Transnistria with their own military forces to re-establish peace in the region.

Chuck Hagel, US Defense Secretary, warned that it is a must to increase military spending in the face of this challenge, "over the long term, we should expect Russia to test our alliance's purpose, stamina, and commitment"²¹. Russia's annexation of Crimea and its backing of separatists in Eastern Ukraine "has reminded NATO of its founding purpose (...); NATO must stand ready to revisit the basic principles underlying its relationship with Russia"²². Chuck Hagel, US Defense Secretary, underlined that "future generations will note whether (...) at this moment of challenge, we summoned the will to invest in our alliance"²³. Chuck Hagel, US Defense Secretary, added that "we must not squander this opportunity or shrink from this challenge. We will be judged harshly by history (...) if we do"²⁴. Otherwise, there are serious concerns about Moldova's place on the map of Europe.

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²⁴ *Ibidem*

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Terorismul și dreptul internațional

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Abstract: Terrorism is not a newly founded concept, it was conceived over a long period of time in the past, and manifested itself in differed ways, from the classic notion of terrorism to cyberterrorism. That being said terrorism is not evil incarnate, it is the evil in ourselves, it is our fanatic side that is obsessed with power, with vengeance, with destruction. Therefore, this phenomenon which is specific to our race (only a human being, takes pleasure in sadistic acts and acts of terror) needs to be analyzed the way it is from an objective point of view, to comprehend its ways and mechanisms, to annihilate its causes, to destroy its structures and to limit its effects. Preventive measures against terrorism, need to include and maintain strategic situations, dominated by a coherent system always under civil and military surveillance of states, organizations and people that are believed to be involved in terrorist networks. Cyberterrorism, alongside antiterrorism war, needs to be defined by the international law, by the law of peace and law of war.

Keywords: terrorism, international law, UNO, Council of Europe, European Union, CIS, BSEC, Europol, human rights.

Motto:

„Cheia terorismului nu o reprezintă actul în sine, ci frica de acel act.”

Keith Olbermann

Terorismul din secolul al XXI-lea tinde să îndrepte omenirea către o nouă eră a agresivității, el fiind unul din cele mai sângeroase și mai barbare tipuri de violență care există.

Spectrul amenințărilor asimetrice și atipice a devenit extrem de variat și se află în continuă diversificare și internaționalizare, ele fiind de importantă majoră: crima organizată, proliferarea armelor de distrugere în masă, traficul de droguri, corupția, acțiunile teroriste și activitățile ilegale de finanțare a terorismului. În marea lor majoritate, acestea se întrepătrund sau se relaționează deoarece urmăresc impunerea prin violență a unor

revendicări de natură diversă aparținând unor grupuri cu interese minoritare.

Dinamica fenomenului terorist internațional evidențiază schimbările majore intervenite în natura amenințărilor la adresa securității statelor în perioada post-Război Rece, motivațiile violenței sau agresiunii de orice natură devenind foarte diverse: de la cele politice și religioase la cele economice, informatice, cibernetice, sau de orice altă natură și în strânsă legătură cu crizele majore, interesele crimei organizate, interesele etnice și religioase, războaiele informaționale etc.

Terorismul transfrontalier este un fenomen în dezvoltare continuă, devenind un pericol social din ce în ce mai letal la adresa securității naționale, regionale și mondiale în condițiile modificării continue a motivațiilor, tacticilor, modalităților de acțiune și a țintelor vizate și a creșterii sprijinului logistic, nivelului de susținere unei părți a opiniei publice și specializării pregătirii teroriștilor.

Dimensiunile actuale ale violenței terorismului contemporan sunt de natură să zdruncine stabilitatea relațiilor normale de conviețuire pașnică, să afecteze legăturile politice, culturale, economice și de altă natură dintre țări și popoare în conformitate cu normele morale și principiile dreptului internațional.

Terorismul internațional reprezintă o amenințare strategică nu doar pentru SUA și țările UE, dar și pentru Rusia, China, India și pentru multe alte țări, inclusiv Republica Moldova.

Efectele atacurilor teroriste din ultimii ani ai secolului XXI (11 septembrie 2001; insula Bali 2002; 25 decembrie 2003 Pakistan; atacurile teroriste de la Istanbul 2003; 11 martie 2004 Spania; 07 iulie 2005, Londra etc.) se resimt și în zilele noastre, iar recrudescența fenomenului, sub diversele sale fațete și valențe, continuă să erodeze arhitectura mediului actual de securitate, în care nu doar confruntarea fizică periclitează stabilitatea omenirii, ci și cea purtată în spațiul virtual, tehnologic sau informațional, cu consecința afectării siguranței statelor, în însași substanța sa.

Actele teroriste din ianuarie 2015, din Franța, și extinderea amenințărilor de același gen în țări considerate în trecut drept „oaze” ale securității (Belgia, Danemarca, Germania etc.) ne arată cât de vulnerabili suntem în fața acestui pericol, a cărui uriașă dimensiune ne creează o stare

permanentă de angoasă, dar și un sentiment de revoltă, dublat de simțirea firească de a ne solidariza și coopera,

Între termenii *terorism* și *drept internațional* există o legătură strânsă.

Așadar,

- Terorismul a devenit/este un fenomen universal, care se practică atât în timp de pace, cât și în timp de conflict armat.

- Dreptul internațional acționează, atât în caz de pace, cât și timp de război internațional, or ne internațional.

Desigur, actele de terorism comise în caz de război au o conotație juridică diferită față de cele comise în situație de pace (pe care nu le vom examina).

Mai jos ne vom referi la combaterea terorismului în situații de pace, care ridică trei probleme importante, după cum sunt:

1. Pericolul terorismului în plan global;

2. *Modus operandi* al teroristului;

3. Metode și mijloace de prevenire și reprimare a fenomenului terorist.

Așadar, prima (pericolul terorismului),

în zilele noastre terorismul a devenit una dintre amenințările cele mai grave la adresa securității naționale, regionale și internaționale, fiind definit de Secretarul general al Națiunilor Unite: *“Teroriștii care au atacat Statele Unite la 11 septembrie - preciza Kofi Annan - vizau o națiune, dar ei au rănit o planetă întreagă. Atacul a fost lansat practic împotriva întregii umanități și este în interesul umanității să nu lase să triumfe forțe care i s-ar împotrivi”* [1].

În ce privește *modus operandi*, actele teroriștilor sunt îndreptate, de regulă, împotriva civililor care nu au nicio legătură directă cu obiectivul urmărit de teroriști. Scopul lor este să provoace teamă, spaimă. Intimidarea prin violență sau amenințare cu violență a civililor, a vieții sau a bunurilor lor. Violența practică de teroriști este ilegală, exercitată de anonimi, îndreptată împotriva ordinii de drept. Actele teroriste au caracter umilitor pentru ființele umane și sunt percepute în genere drept crime.

Iar în activitatea de prevenire și reprimare a terorismului menționăm, războiul împotriva terorismului reprezintă ansamblul acțiunilor întreprinse de întreaga comunitate internațională.

Succint ne vom opri la cadrul juridic care legitimează lupta pentru eradicarea terorismului a fost definit nu numai de Națiunile Unite, dar și de organizațiile regionale – NATO, CE, OSCE etc.

Spre exemplu, la 8 septembrie 2006, Adunarea Generală a ONU a adoptat Strategia mondială împotriva terorismului, al celor 192 de state membre, prin care se abordează global fenomenul, în contextul unei cooperării internaționale degrevată de componenta politică, având forma unei Rezoluții și a unui Plan de acțiune, completate în 2008 [2].

Adoptarea acestui document și marchează primul moment din istoria Națiunilor Unite în care statele membre au căzut de acord asupra unui cadru strategic și operațional de luptă împotriva terorismului [3].

Consiliul Europei este unul dintre pilonii de bază ai luptei antiteroriste. Parlamentul European a adresat, la 9.02.2007, Consiliului o recomandare privind factorii care încurajează terorismul și favorizează recrutarea de teroriști [4]. Printre recomandări se numără: elaborarea unei strategii globale care să includă atât lupta împotriva indivizilor care comit atentate, cât și fenomenul terorismului în ansamblu, de la recrutarea de teroriști, la rolul rețelei sociale care încurajează și generează terorismul, terminând cu situația victimelor.

Consiliul Europei a adoptat la 16.05.2005 Convenția privind prevenirea terorismului.

Comunitatea Statelor Independente (CSI) a adoptat Strategia de luptă contra terorismului [5], inclusiv și Asociația Statelor din Asia de Sud-Est [6].

Atât în plan universal, cât și regional avem un șir de instrumentele, după cum urmează, în plan internațional:

- Convenția cu privire la infracțiuni și anumite acte săvârșite la bordul aeronavelor (Tokyo, 1963);
- Convenții referitoare la reprimarea capturării ilicite de aeronave (Haga);
- Convenția pentru reprimarea actelor ilicite îndreptate împotriva securității aviației civile (Montreal, 1973);
- Convenția pentru reprimarea actelor ilicite îndreptate împotriva siguranței navigației maritime (Roma, 1988);
- Protocolul asupra platformelor fixe situate pe platoul continental (Roma, 1988);

- Protocolul privind incriminarea actelor de violență săvârșite pe aeroporturi ce servesc traficului internațional, complementar Convenției privind incriminarea actelor săvârșite împotriva siguranței aeronavelor (Montreal, 24 februarie 1988);

- Convenția privind prevenirea și sancționarea infracțiunilor contra persoanelor care se bucură de protecție internațională, inclusiv agenții diplomatici (New York, 1973);

- Convenția internațională contra luării de ostatici (New York, 1973);

- Convenția privind marcarea explozibililor plastici în scopul detectării (Montreal, 1 martie 1991);

- Convenția O.N.U. privind incriminarea atentatelor teroriste cu bombă (New York, 15 decembrie 1997);

- Convenția O.N.U. privind incriminarea finanțării terorismului (New York, 9 decembrie 1999) ;

- Amendamentul O.N.U. la Convenția privind protecția fizică a materialelor nucleare (2005);

- Protocolul O.N.U. pentru reprimarea actelor ilicite împotriva siguranței navigației maritime (2005);

- Protocolul O.N.U. pentru reprimarea actelor ilicite împotriva siguranței platformelor fixe pe platoul continental (2005);

- Convenția internațională privind reprimarea actelor de terorism nuclear – New York, 14 septembrie 2005 etc.

Din instrumente regionale antiterorism menționăm:

- Convenția europeană pentru reprimarea terorismului (1979)

- Convenția Organizației Statelor Americane privind prevenirea și pedepsirea actelor de terorism care au forma crimelor împotriva persoanelor care au relevanță internațională (Washington, 1971);

- Convenția Asociației Asiei de Sud-Est pentru cooperare regională privind reprimarea terorismului (Kathmandu, 1997);

- Convenția arabă privind reprimarea terorismului (1998);

- Convenția Organizației Islamice pentru reprimarea terorismului internaționale (1999)

- Convenția Organizației Statelor Africane privind prevenirea și combaterea terorismului (Algiers, 1999);

- Convenția privind cooperarea statelor CSI (Minsk, 1999);

- Rezoluția Uniunii Europene privind interzicerea actelor de terorism în spațiul comunității (1997);

- Convenția Consiliului Europei privind prevenirea terorismului – Varșovia, 16 mai 2005;

- Convenția Consiliului Europei privind descoperirea, sechestrarea și confiscarea produselor care stau la baza metodologiei privind finanțarea terorismului – Varșovia, 16 mai 2005 etc.

După 1994, Adunarea Generală a ONU a adoptat mai multe rezoluții speciale, intitulate generic *“Măsuri pentru eliminarea terorismului internațional”*:

- Rezoluția 49/60, 9 decembrie 1994;
- Rezoluția 50/53, 11 decembrie 1995;
- Rezoluția 51/210, 17 decembrie 1996;
- Rezoluția 52/165, 15 decembrie 1997;
- Rezoluția 53/108, 26 ianuarie 1999;
- Rezoluția 54/110, 2 februarie 2000;
- Rezoluția 55/158, 30 ianuarie 2001 etc.

Consiliul de Securitate al ONU a adoptat următoarele rezoluții:

- Rezoluția nr. 579 a Consiliului de Securitate – adoptată la 18 decembrie 1985, din inițiativa S.U.A., condamnă categoric luările de ostateci și răpirile de orice fel;

- Rezoluția privind combaterea terorismului – adoptată la reuniunea de la Tokyo, din 4 – 6 mai 1986, precizează măsurile ce trebuie aplicate, atât în cadrul legislației internaționale, cât și în planul normelor interne, *„împotriva oricărui stat implicat în mod evident în sprijinirea terorismului internațional”*;

- Rezoluția 748 privind reprimarea terorismului (9 martie 1992);

- Rezoluția 1269, care condamnă orice act terorist (1992);

- Rezoluția 1368, care condamnă atacurile teroriste din New York și stabilește principiile cooperării statelor împotriva terorismului (12 septembrie 2001);

- Rezoluția 1373, privind combaterea terorismului, adoptată sub auspiciile capitolului VII din Carta ONU (28 septembrie 2001);

- Rezoluția nr. 1540/ 2004 a Consiliului de Securitate O.N.U. privind neproliferarea armelor de distrugere în masă;

- Rezoluția nr. 1904/ 2009 a Consiliului de Securitate O.N.U. privind aplicarea de sancțiuni împotriva Al-Qaeda, asupra lui Osama ben Laden și a grupării talibanilor.

În aceeași măsură, la nivelul țărilor Organizației Cooperării Economice a Mării Negre (OCEMN), s-au intensificat preocupările în sfera creării unui cadru legislativ coerent și adaptat, prin intrarea în vigoare a următoarelor documente:

- Carta OCEMN (Yalta, 1998);
- Acordul încheiat la nivelul guvernelor țărilor membre OCEMN referitor la cooperarea în domeniul combaterii criminalității, în special a celei organizate (Corfu, 1998);
- Protocolul adițional la sus-menționatul Acord, referitor la combaterea terorismului (Atena, 2004) etc.

Dintre documentele recente adoptate în cadrul ONU, menționăm Rezoluția 2178(2014) privind luptătorii teroriști străini (LTS), adoptată la 24 septembrie 2014, de către Consiliul de Securitate al ONU, în temeiul capitolului VII din Carta ONU [RCSONU 2178(2014)].

Iar printre acțiunile întreprinse pe plan european ne referim la Comisia Europeană care a prezentat 28 aprilie 2015 Agenda europeană privind securitatea pentru perioada 2015 - 2020, prin care se dorește să sprijine cooperarea dintre statele membre în ceea ce privește combaterea amenințărilor la adresa securității și să intensifice eforturile comune depuse în lupta împotriva terorismului, a criminalității organizate și a criminalității informatice.

Pe agendă figurează instrumentele și măsurile concrete la care se recurge în aceste activități comune în vederea garantării securității și în vederea combaterii, într-un mod mai eficace, a celor mai urgente trei amenințări.

S-a demonstrat că, recente atacuri teroriste îndreptate împotriva populației și a valorilor Europei au fost coordonate la nivel transfrontalier, ceea ce arată că trebuie să conlucrăm pentru a face față acestor amenințări, cu respectarea deplină a drepturilor fundamentale.

Desigur, responsabilitatea pentru asigurarea securității interne le revine în primul rând statelor membre, dar provocările transfrontaliere pun la încercare capacitatea diverselor țări de a acționa în mod individual și

necesită sprijinul UE pentru crearea unui climat de încredere și pentru facilitarea cooperării, a schimbului de informații și a acțiunilor comune.

Printre acțiunile centrale se numără și combaterea radicalizării,

Comisia UE a înființat un Centru de excelență pentru colectarea și difuzarea de cunoștințe de specialitate în domeniul combaterii radicalizării, pe baza Rețelei UE pentru sensibilizarea publicului cu privire la radicalizare (RAN) — o rețea la nivelul întregii UE, lansată în 2011. Și astfel, se consolidează schimbul de experiență în rândul profesioniștilor direct implicați în prevenirea radicalizării și a extremismului violent la nivel local.

Actualizarea Deciziei-cadru privind combaterea terorismului, de asemenea asigură un cadru juridic mai coerent pentru combaterea fenomenului luptătorilor străini. Astfel, se creează posibilitatea unei cooperări intensificate, inclusiv, cu țările terțe în această chestiune.

Tăierea finanțării infractorilor de asemenea v-a consolida cooperarea dintre autoritățile competente din Europa (în special unitățile naționale de informații financiare, care vor fi conectate la Europol).

Comisia a analizat și necesitatea unor noi acte normative pentru combaterea finanțării terorismului, cât și pentru amplificarea măsurilor de confiscare a bunurilor obținute din activități infracționale.

Un alt aspect este îmbunătățirea dialogului cu sectorul IT.

În 2015, Comisia lansează un forum al UE cu marile companii informatice, în vederea combaterii propagandei teroriste pe internet și în rețelele de socializare și în vederea analizării unor modalități de a lua în considerare îngrijorările exprimate de autoritățile de aplicare a legii cu privire la noile tehnologii de criptare.

Inclusiv, consolidarea cadrului juridic în domeniul armelor de foc: consolidarea acestuia este necesară pentru a se ține cont de traficul ilegal de arme și de reactivarea ilegală a armelor, pentru a se stabili standarde comune, a se intensifica schimbul de informații și a se stimula cooperarea cu țările terțe.

Se propune consolidarea instrumentelor de combatere a criminalității informatice: prioritatea este să se găsească modalități de depășire a obstacolele de care se izbesc anchetele penale în mediul online, în special în ceea ce privește competența judiciară și regulile privind accesul la elementele de probă și informațiile online.

Se solicită îmbunătățirea capacităților de care dispune Europol. Printre măsurile avute în vedere se numără și cea de crearea unui Centru european de combatere a terorismului, care va ajuta Agenția UE să intensifice sprijinul acordat autorităților naționale de aplicare a legii pentru desfășurarea unor acțiuni de combatere a luptătorilor teroriști străini, a finanțării terorismului, a conținuturilor extremiste violente din mediul online și a traficului ilicit de arme de foc.

Noul mod de lucru diferit, de colaborare din cadrul Comisiei permite o abordare cuprinzătoare a securității, în agendă fiind introduse măsuri din toate sectoarele de politică, de la justiție și afaceri interne până la afaceri financiare, transporturi și mediu.

Terorismul nu este un fenomen nou în Europa. Acesta reprezintă o amenințare la adresa securității noastre, la adresa valorilor societăților noastre democratice și la adresa drepturilor și libertăților cetățenilor europeni. Între anii 2009 și 2013, în statele membre ale UE au avut loc 1010 atacuri eșuate, contracarate sau finalizate, soldate cu 38 de decese. În plus, mai mulți cetățeni europeni au fost răpiți sau uciși de grupări teroriste în întreaga lume.

Statele membre ale Uniunii Europene sunt angajate pe deplin să lupte împreună împotriva terorismului și să asigure cetățenilor săi un nivel cât mai ridicat de protecție. În acest sens, Consiliul a adoptat în 2005 strategia UE de combatere a terorismului. Strategia se axează pe patru piloni principali: prevenirea, protecția, urmărirea și răspunderea. Prin intermediul celor patru piloni, strategia recunoaște importanța cooperării cu țările terțe și cu instituțiile internaționale.

Una dintre prioritățile UE în domeniul combaterii terorismului este identificarea și abordarea factorilor care contribuie la radicalizare și a proceselor de recrutare a persoanelor care comit acte de terorism. În acest sens, Consiliul a adoptat o strategie UE pentru combaterea radicalizării și a recrutării în scopuri teroriste. Având în vedere evoluțiile recente, precum fenomenul persoanelor care acționează singure și al luptătorilor străini sau potențialul tot mai mare de mobilizare și de comunicare al mijloacelor de comunicare sociale, Consiliul a adoptat o versiune revizuită a acestei strategii în iunie 2014. În decembrie 2014, miniștrii justiției și afacerilor interne au adoptat o serie de orientări pentru Strategia revizuită a UE pentru

combaterea radicalizării și a recrutării. Aceste orientări stabilesc o serie de măsuri care să fie puse în aplicare de către UE și statele membre.

A doua prioritate a strategiei UE de combatere a terorismului este protecția cetățenilor și a infrastructurii și reducerea vulnerabilității la atacuri. Aceasta cuprinde protejarea frontierelor externe, îmbunătățirea securității transporturilor, protejarea țintelor strategice și reducerea vulnerabilității infrastructurilor critice. În acest domeniu, UE lucrează în prezent la elaborarea unor acte legislative prin care se reglementează utilizarea datelor din registrul cu numele pasagerilor (PNR) în scopul asigurării respectării legii.

UE depune eforturi în vederea combaterii capacității de planificare și de organizare a organizațiilor teroriste și a aducerii acestora în fața justiției. Pentru a realiza aceste obiective, UE și-a îndreptat atenția asupra mai multor aspecte: consolidarea capacităților naționale, îmbunătățirea cooperării practice și a schimbului de informații între autoritățile polițienești și judiciare (în special prin intermediul Europol și Eurojust), abordarea chestiunii finanțării terorismului și dejucarea mijloacelor de organizare a atacurilor și de comunicare ale organizațiilor teroriste. În mai 2015, Consiliul și Parlamentul European au adoptat noi norme de prevenire a spălării banilor și a finanțării terorismului.

Cel de al patrulea obiectiv al strategiei UE de combatere a terorismului este pregătirea, în spiritul solidarității, în vederea gestionării și a reducerii la minim a consecințelor unui atac terorist. Acest lucru se realizează prin îmbunătățirea capacității de a gestiona urmările, coordonarea răspunsului și nevoile victimelor. Printre prioritățile din acest domeniu se numără elaborarea unor modalități ale UE de coordonare a situațiilor de criză, revizuirea mecanismului de protecție civilă, dezvoltarea procedurilor de evaluare a riscului sau schimbul de bune practici privind asistența acordată victimelor terorismului.

Uniunea Europeană și statele membre se confruntă cu importante probleme de securitate. Terorismul, criminalitatea organizată și infrafracțiunile informatice constituie amenințări în continuă extindere pentru societate, peste tot în Europa, a căror natură și amploare s-au schimbat în mod evident. Europa trebuie să facă față efectelor instabilității politice care afectează vecinătatea imediată și care compromit interesele UE în materie de securitate. Odată cu prezentarea noii agende europene privind

securitatea, Comisia Europeană realizează unul din punctele înscrise în programul de lucru pentru anul 2015, fiind în același timp un subiect care figura printre orientările politice ale *Comisiei Juncker*, prezentate în luna decembrie 2014.

În iunie 2014, Consiliul European a cerut Comisiei Europene reexaminarea strategiei de securitate internă a Uniunii Europene, adoptată în 2010, iar Consiliul JAI din decembrie 2014 și-a expus prioritățile în ceea ce privește reînnoirea strategiei. Astfel, obiectivele fixate în strategia de securitate 2010-2014, rămân valabile și ar trebui să fie menținute în noul program.

Agenda europeană privind securitatea definește maniera în care Uniunea poate aduce o valoare adăugată statelor membre, pentru a le ajuta în asigurarea securității. Deși securitatea este o responsabilitate mai întâi de toate în sarcina statelor membre, acestea nu pot să-și asume totul singure. Respectând responsabilitățile naționale de aplicare a legii și de asigurare a securității interne, toți actorii naționali și europeni trebuie să colaboreze mai bine pentru a face față amenințărilor transfrontaliere.

Deci, agenda europeană privind securitatea trebuie să fie un program partajat între Uniune și statele membre, având ca rezultat crearea unui spațiu european de securitate internă în care persoanele fizice sunt protejate, în deplină conformitate cu drepturile fundamentale.

UE sprijină statele membre să prevină și să combată terorismul prin intermediul mai multor instrumente. UE oferă un cadru juridic pentru a contribui la coordonarea acțiunilor transfrontaliere de aplicare a legii. Printre instrumentele principale se numără *mandatul european de arestare*, *Sistemul european de informații cu privire la cazierele judiciare și mecanismele de asistență judiciară reciprocă cu țările terțe*.

În al doilea rând, UE sprijină eforturile depuse de statele membre pentru combaterea radicalizării pe teren prin intermediul Rețelei UE pentru sensibilizarea publicului cu privire la radicalizare (RAN), care permite experților și practicienilor să facă schimb de bune practici.

În al treilea rând, UE contribuie la prevenirea finanțării terorismului prin intermediul legislației împotriva spălării banilor, al rețelei unităților de informații financiare din UE și al Acordului dintre UE și SUA privind Programul de urmărire a finanțărilor în scopuri teroriste (mai multe

informații referitoare la acțiuni specifice de combatere a terorismului se pot găsi în MEMO/15/3140).

Multe provocări în materie de securitate provin din afara UE, iar colaborarea cu țările terțe este un element esențial al Agendei europene privind securitatea. UE a elaborat o inițiativă de combatere a terorismului în Balcanii de Vest pentru a îmbunătăți cooperarea regională și schimbul de informații cu privire la lupta împotriva terorismului și a jihadismului din vecinătatea Europei. În plus, ca urmare a Consiliului Afaceri Externe din 9 februarie 2015, UE a lansat un nou program intitulat „*Combaterea radicalizării și a luptătorilor teroriști străini*”. În prezent, UE contribuie cu 10 milioane EUR la combaterea radicalizării în regiunea Sahel-Maghreb și la oprirea fluxului de luptători străini din Africa de Nord, Orientul Mijlociu și Balcanii de Vest (pentru detalii a se vedea IP/15/4865).

La 24 septembrie 2014, Consiliul de Securitate al ONU a adoptat Rezoluția 2178(2014) privind luptătorii teroriști străini (LTS) în temeiul capitolului VII din Carta ONU [RCSONU 2178(2014)].

În octombrie 2014, Consiliul a invitat Comisia UE să exploreze modalități de remediere a eventualelor deficiențe din Decizia-cadru privind combaterea terorismului (Decizia-cadru 2002/475/JAI *privind combaterea terorismului*, care a fost modificată prin Decizia-cadru 2008/919/JAI, denumită în continuare „*Decizia-cadru privind terorismul*”), având în vedere, în special, RCSONU 2178(2014)].

În Declarația comună de după Consiliul JAI de la Riga, miniștrii au convenit asupra importanței de a lua în considerare posibile măsuri legislative pentru a se ajunge la o înțelegere comună privind infracțiunile de terorism în lumina RCSONU 2178(2014). În rezoluția din 11 februarie 2015, Parlamentul European a subliniat necesitatea, printre altele, de a armoniza incriminarea infracțiunilor în care sunt implicați luptătorii teroriști străini și de a evita eventualele lacune în urmărirea penală prin actualizarea Deciziei-cadru privind terorismul. La 21 ianuarie 2015, Comitetul de Miniștri al Consiliului Europei (CoE) a instituit Comitetul privind luptătorii teroriști străini și aspecte conexe (COD-CTE). Plasat sub autoritatea Comitetului de experți privind terorismul (CODEXTER), COD-CTE a fost însărcinat să redacteze un protocol adițional la Convenția Consiliului Europei privind prevenirea terorismului (CETS nr. 196). După trei runde de discuții în cadrul COD-CTE (23-26 februarie 2015, 9-12 martie 2015 și 23-26 martie 2015),

CODEXTER a supus discuției și ulterior a aprobat protocolul adițional la 10 aprilie 2015, în cadrul celei de a 28-a reuniuni plenare. Adunarea Parlamentară a Consiliului Europei și-a dat avizul cu privire la protocolul adițional în sesiunea din 20-24 aprilie. Protocolul adițional a fost aprobat în prealabil de Comitetul de Miniștri la 12 mai 2015, în vederea adoptării sale finale la 19 mai 2015.

Protocolul adițional are ca scop facilitarea punerii în aplicare rapide, coordonate și eficiente a anumitor aspecte ale RCSONU 2178 (în principal a celor legate de prevenirea și urmărirea plecării luptătorilor teroriști străini), promovarea unei înțelegeri comune și a unui răspuns comun la infracțiunile legate de luptătorii teroriști străini, facilitarea în sens mai larg a cercetărilor și urmărilor penale având ca obiect fapte de natură pregătitoare care riscă sau amenință să conducă la săvârșirea de infracțiuni de terorism și facilitarea cooperării internaționale prin intensificarea schimbului de informații.

Astfel, protocolul adițional prevede incriminarea următoarelor fapte: participarea într-o asociație sau grupare în scopuri teroriste (articolul 2), primirea de instruire în scopuri teroriste (articolul 3), deplasarea în străinătate în scopuri teroriste sau tentativa de deplasare în străinătate în scopuri teroriste (articolul 4), furnizarea sau colectarea de fonduri pentru astfel de deplasări (articolul 5) și organizarea sau facilitarea unor astfel de deplasări (articolul 6). În fine, articolul 7 vizează îmbunătățirea schimbului de informații prin obligarea părților să desemneze un punct de contact care să furnizeze informații sau să trateze cererile de informații disponibile în timp util

Cadrul juridic al UE care reglementează infracțiunile ce au legătură cu terorismul este prevăzut în Decizia-cadru privind combaterea terorismului. Protocolul adițional extinde domeniul de aplicare al infracțiunilor care trebuie să fie incriminate sau introduce infracțiuni similare cu cele deja prevăzute în decizia-cadru.

La 02 decembrie 2015, Comisia Europeană a adoptat un pachet de măsuri pentru a consolida lupta împotriva terorismului și a traficului de arme și explozibil, care prevede, în special, "*incriminarea*" călătoriilor în străinătate. Acest pachet include o "*directiva privind terorismul*", care trebuie "*sa consolideze arsenalul UE de prevenire a atacurilor teroriste*".

Migrația și terorismul sunt tratate ca subiecte distincte deoarece, așa cum a subliniat și președintele Comisiei Europene, Jean-Claude Juncker, mulți solicitanți de azil fug ei înșiși din calea terorismului promovată de gruparea Stat Islamic, talibani sau alte organizații extremiste.

Dilema cu care se confruntă UE este că Schengen înlesnește circulația persoanelor și bunurilor în UE, dar necesită de asemenea o mai bună împărtășire a informațiilor, pentru a preveni criminalitatea transfrontalieră.

Aproximativ 1,7 milioane de cetățeni UE traversează zilnic frontierele în spațiul Schengen pentru a merge la serviciu, potrivit institutului Bruegel. Sondajele de opinie indică de asemenea că mulți europeni prețuiesc Schengen mai mult decât orice schimbare adusă de UE. Dar unele state, ca Franța, Germania, Austria și Ungaria, au introdus, deja, controale temporare la frontiere. "*Scopul nostru este clar: trebuie să redobândim controlul asupra frontierelor noastre externe pentru a limita aflulul de imigranți și a conserva Schengen*", a precizat Donald Tusk, președintele Consiliului European, în invitația la summit-ul de la Bruxelles, din 17-18 decembrie 2015. Jean-Claude Juncker a afirmat că europenii au acum o singură graniță și "*o responsabilitate comună de a o proteja*". Salvarea Schengen înseamnă sporirea supravegherii tuturor persoanelor care intră sau ies din spațiul de circulație fără pașaport.

Pe viitor, cetățenii UE, la fel ca cei din afara blocului comunitar, vor trebui să prezinte pașapoartele la control, pentru a fi comparate cu bazele de date ale poliției. Aceste baze de date trebuie însă îmbunătățite. Peste un milion de imigranți au intrat în UE anul acesta (2015), majoritatea dornici să ajungă în Germania sau alte state nordice mai prospere, unde își pot găsi locuri de muncă sau au rude. Războiul sirian a dus imigrația către UE la un nivel-record și există temeri că actuala campanie internațională împotriva grupării Stat Islamic și raidurile ruse în sprijinul lui Bashar al-Assad vor determina și mai mulți sirieni să fugă din țară. În aceste condiții, cei 28 de lideri UE vor examina din nou modalități de a ajuta Grecia și Turcia să gestioneze situația migrației. Turcia, care se confruntă cu peste două milioane de refugiați sirieni, este într-o poziție bună de negociere acum, criticii apreciind că UE riscă să facă compromisuri privind situația drepturilor omului, din dorința de a limita fluxul de imigranți. Comisia Europeană a propus oficial în această perioadă (14-18.12.2015) crearea unei poliții europene anti imigrație, care ar urma să aibă 1.500 de membri și va putea fi

detașată rapid la frontierele externe ale Uniunii Europene, printr-o decizie luată la Bruxelles care va putea fi blocată doar cu o majoritate a statelor membre. Proiectul, care va avea nevoie de aprobarea statelor membre, prevede înființarea unei noi structuri cu efective terestre și maritime pentru protejarea frontierelor externe, prin înlocuirea actualei Agenții pentru frontiere - Frontex. Această forță ar putea să intervină chiar și atunci când țările-gazdă nu sunt de acord, din acest considerent, la prezent, unele state membre UE sunt ostile acestui plan.

În concluzie menționăm, în prezent trăim cu toții într-o lume în care siguranța și stilul nostru de viață sunt amenințate de acte de violență extremă. Considerăm că, fenomenului global al terorismului trebuie întâmpinat cu răspunsuri ferme, cu unitate și solidaritate din partea tuturor popoarelor vizate de acest fenomen. Trebuie ca împreună să luăm toate măsurile posibile care să blocheze orice posibilitate ca o conflagrație mondială să apară în perioada următoare. Un al treilea război mondial ar avea o cu totul altă înfățișare decât orice altă conflagrație convențională, cu care istoria ne-a provocat în trecut.

Prin continuitatea proiectelor și principiilor, care derivă din UE și NATO, vor fi formulate răspunsuri pe măsură la amenințările teroriste. UE garantează că viața cetățenilor europeni este protejată, numai într-un sistem în care unitatea, egalitatea și fraternitatea sunt principii de bază pentru fiecare dintre noi și pentru toate statele.

Valul de atentate comise anul acesta de organizații teroriste în Franța, Turcia sau Kenya au determinat o mobilizare fără precedent în Consiliul de Securitate al ONU.

La 18 decembrie 2015, a fost adoptată cu unanimitate, o Rezoluție ce vizează tăierea surselor de finanțare ale jihadiștilor. Pentru prima dată, în vederea adoptării acestei rezoluții la reuniunea de la New York au asistat miniștrii de Finanțe ai celor 15 state membre în Consiliul de Securitate. Rezoluția este de fapt un text tehnic de 28 de pagini elaborat în comun de SUA și Rusia, ce vizează direct gruparea Statul Islamic. Documentul cere țărilor să stopeze contrabanda cu produse petroliere și cu artefacte pentru a sancționa sprijinul financiar acordat grupării teroriste sunnite. Statele sunt invitate ca legislațiile lor naționale să considere finanțarea terorismului drept o crimă gravă, chiar și în absența oricărei legături cu un act terorist precis.

Așadar, terorismul provoacă pierderi și din acest considerent această activitate criminală trebuie combătută prin toate mijloacele: politic și militar, iar fiind cercetată, ea necesită a fi judecată penal.

Pe de o parte, o societate democratică trebuie să adopte anumite măsuri de natură preventivă sau represivă pentru a se proteja împotriva amenințărilor teroriste la adresa celor mai importante valori și principii pe care ea se bazează.

Pe de altă parte, autoritățile publice, legislativul, guvernul, instanțele judecătorești și administrația dețin obligația legală de a adopta măsurile necesare în acest sens cu condiția respectării stricte a drepturilor și libertăților fundamentale consfințite de Convenția europeană a drepturilor omului (CEDO), cât și a altor documente importante în materia drepturilor omului.

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The Competence of the EU to Negotiate and Conclude International Agreements: the Opportunity of a Negotiation between the European Union and the Eurasian Economic Union

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Abstract: The contribution investigates the competence of the European Union to conclude international agreements with specific regards to the procedure and its critical aspects. The main attention is, then, dedicated to the possibility and the opportunity of a negotiation between European Union and Eurasian Economic Union in order to strengthen cooperation in Europe. The final proposal, according with “Jean Monnet” functionalist approach, is to include in the negotiations those countries which are geographically in-between but are not members of EU neither of EEU.

Keywords: European Union, Eurasian Economic Union, International agreements, Procedures, Critical issues.

1. Introduction¹.

As it is well known, after the Second World War, western European countries decided, under the same strategy, to start two different integration processes under two different legal umbrellas².

The aspiration was clear and was the maintaining of peace.

The first pillar of the strategy was the integration through the Council of Europe. In the legal system of the Council of Europe, the Convention of Human Rights (formally the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms) deserves a specific attention. It pursued, at

¹ This contribution reproduces with few modifications the speech made at the International Conference, on “European Union and Eurasian Economic Union towards a greater Europe from Lisbon to Vladivostok” organized by Prof. Yulia Sushkova, under her Jean Monnet Program, at the Ogarev Mordovia State University, Russian Federation, 1-2 December 2015.

² The third pillar of the same strategy could be considered the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) but it is important to underline its different nature and its own geopolitical background.

regional level, the same objective of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, at global level.

The main scope is to guarantee a minimum common level of protection of human rights, not negotiable by the Contracting States. The particular novelty was the creation of a Court charged to guarantee the enforcement of the Convention and the protocols.

The *revolutionary* idea was that any individuals may refer to the Court, after domestic remedies have been exhausted, claiming to be the victim of a violation of the rights set forth in the Convention or the protocols thereto, as well as any Contracting State may refer to the Court any alleged breach of the provisions of the Convention and the protocols thereto by another Contracting State³. In other words, it makes “justiciable” by the European Court of Human Rights any national legislation or decision affecting human rights.

The second pillar of this strategy was the economic integration through the three historical Communities (European Economic Community, European Coal and Steel Community and EURATOM) which many reforms and enlargements, during sixty years, led to the European Union as it is today.

The integration of strategic national markets, the free movement of goods, services and individuals were the instrument to avoid controversies. In the Jean Monnet approach, economic integration was definitely the best instrument to maintain peace but it never was an objective itself. Unfortunately, today some adversaries of the European integration and many technocrats misunderstand, in different ways, the relationship between peace and economic integration.

Today, twenty-eight European countries are members of the European Union and forty-seven countries are members of the Council of Europe and signed the European Convention of Human Rights. It means that almost all the States that represent the geographical Europe (and more than it) agreed on common values and on a common understanding about human rights.

³ Since the Court was established, almost all applications have been lodged by individuals ex art. 33 of the Convention. Art. 34 of the Convention regulates the so called inter-State application.

2. The idea of “Greater Europe”.

The visionary perspective of a united Europe is, in some way, tied to the very idea of Europe and to the original vision of the European integration as a tool for peace. Since the fall of the Berlin Wall, the integration of the post-Communist countries became a political objective of the European Union. During the Nineties, also the idea of the integration of Russia in the European Union was at stake. Doubtless, this option has probably been more discussed at academic level than at political level. Although this option was never close to be realized, the idea of a united Europe received a strong impulse when, in February 1996, Russia became a member of the Council of Europe and signed the Convention of Human Rights.

The idea of “Greater Europe” did not emerge from a void. Over the last fifteen years it has been present in major policy statements of Russian leaders. It was employed to advocate closer co-operation between Russia and the West.

The concept takes shape after the editorial contribution of Russian Prime Minister Vladimir Putin published on 25 November 2010 by German daily *Süddeutsche Zeitung*, where he described his vision of “a unified continental market with a capacity worth trillions of euros.” The core of his proposal was the creation of a harmonious economic community stretching from Lisbon to Vladivostok. At the same time, he did not exclude the possibility to challenge and discuss about more advanced forms of political integration.

The vision of Greater Europe lacked a clear reference to the integration processes in the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) area, or the place that the countries of Russia and the EU’s “shared neighbourhood” would occupy in the new European architecture. On 4 October 2011, Putin, just partially, closed this gap in an article published in the *Izvestia daily* making references to the concept of Greater Europe as a space comprising two blocs: the European Union and the Eurasian Community⁴.

⁴ See for a comprehensive analysis of the development of Greater Europe concept, M. Menkiszak, “Greater Europe Putin’s vision of European (dis)integration”, *OSW Studies*, 46, 2013

In order to understand the proposal, it is necessary to remember that in 2000, five Member States of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) decided to create the Eurasian Economic Community⁵. During the first decade of the New Millennium, this international organization implemented a number of economic policies based on the same fundamental freedoms (goods, capital, services, and people) on which were based the European Communities at their dawn.

On 10 October 2014, the Members of the Eurasian Economic Community signed an agreement with which they terminate the Eurasian Economic Community and launched the Eurasian Economic Union. From this moment, the Eurasian Economic Union has the possibility to become the natural interlocutor of the European Union for a broader programme of cooperation and economic integration.

This development shows the importance to detail which is the competence of the European Union to conclude international agreements and which are the rules that govern the negotiation, the approval and the implementation of international agreements according with the EU Treaties.

3. The EU competence to conclude international agreements under Lisbon Treaty.

With the Lisbon Treaty, the European Union enlarged its competences in many matters. It is always worth to underline that the Treaty of Lisbon was approved after the failure of the Constitutional Treaty project and it amends the EU's two core treaties, the Treaty on European Union and the Treaty establishing the European Community. The latter is renamed the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union.

For the object of my contribution, it is worth to assess that the Lisbon Treaty seeks to strengthen the role of the European Union (EU) at international level. The possibility to realize this enhancement remains controversial because the foreign policy is a fundamental element of the national States' sovereignty and Member States are protective of their role in international relations.

At institutional level, the Treaty of Lisbon introduces two major innovations: the creation of the High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy (it replaced the High Representative for

⁵ Founding members were Russia, Belarus, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan.

Common Foreign and Security Policy provided by the Treaty of Amsterdam) which heads the European External Action Service; and the development of the Common Security and Defence Policy.

At operational level, the Treaty of Lisbon enlarges the competence of the European Union to negotiate and conclude international agreements.

First, European Union unequivocally acquired legal personality. It means that it could be formally a subject of international law, capable of negotiating and concluding international agreements on its own behalf. These agreements have legal effects both in the internal legal order of the EU and in the internal legal order of the Member States.

Second, it is important to remember that the division of competences between the EU and Member States also applies at international level. The EU may negotiate and conclude an international agreement, if it has either exclusive competence or competence which is shared with Member States.

Article 3 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU specifies the matters and the areas in which the EU has exclusive competence⁶. The areas in which competences are shared are, indeed, defined in Article 4 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU⁷. Where agreement covers also areas

⁶ Art. 3 of the TFEU: 1. The Union shall have exclusive competence in the following areas: (a) customs union; (b) the establishing of the competition rules necessary for the functioning of the internal market; (c) monetary policy for the Member States whose currency is the euro; (d) the conservation of marine biological resources under the common fisheries policy; (e) common commercial policy. 2. The Union shall also have exclusive competence for the conclusion of an international agreement when its conclusion is provided for in a legislative act of the Union or is necessary to enable the Union to exercise its internal competence, or in so far as its conclusion may affect common rules or alter their scope.

⁷ Art. 4 of the TFEU: 1. The Union shall share competence with the Member States where the Treaties confer on it a competence which does not relate to the areas referred to in Articles 3 and 6. 2. Shared competence between the Union and the Member States applies in the following principal areas: (a) internal market; (b) social policy, for the aspects defined in this Treaty; (c) economic, social and territorial cohesion; (d) agriculture and fisheries, excluding the conservation of marine biological resources; (e) environment; (f) consumer protection; (g) transport; (h) trans-European networks; (i) energy; (j) area of freedom, security and justice; (k) common safety concerns in public health matters, for the aspects defined in this Treaty. 3. In the areas of research, technological development and space, the Union shall have competence to carry out activities, in particular to define and implement programmes; however, the exercise of that competence shall not result in Member States

which remain under the competence of the Member States than it is concluded both by the EU and by the Member States. It is therefore a mixed agreement to which Member States must give their consent.

Third, new Treaties define which kind of agreement EU may conclude. According to Article 216 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU, “the Union may conclude an agreement with one or more third countries or international organisations”.

Subsequent Article 217 adds that EU may also conclude “with one or more third countries or international organisations, agreements establishing an association involving reciprocal rights and obligations, common action and special procedure”.

These provisions correspond to two types of agreement: first one is for international agreements strictly speaking; second one is for those agreements which establish an association between EU and other subjects.

Both kind of agreements may be concluded in cases provided for by the founding Treaties; or in a legally binding act; or where the conclusion of an agreement is necessary in order to achieve, within the framework of the Union’s policies, one of the objectives referred to in the Treaties; or where the conclusion is likely to affect common rules or alter their scope.

Fourth, a new procedure has been defined by the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union. The ordinary procedure is ruled by Article 217, but it is necessary to consider for specific subjects also Article 207.

In order to describe the procedure we can distinguish three phases: the initiative, the negotiation and the conclusion.

The initiative lies with the Commission, or the High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy where the agreement envisaged relates exclusively or principally to the common foreign and security policy.

Commission or High Representative submits recommendations to the Council, which is entitled to authorise or deny the opening of

being prevented from exercising theirs. 4. In the areas of development cooperation and humanitarian aid, the Union shall have competence to carry out activities and conduct a common policy; however, the exercise of that competence shall not result in Member States being prevented from exercising theirs.

negotiations adopting a decision. The decision is adopted, depending on the subject, by qualified majority or unanimously.

It is worth to underline that, in the EU governance, while the Commission represents the European Union and must act independently by the Member States, the Council is formed by the Member States Ministries (depending on the fields under discussion) and represents Member States' Governments.

This is very important to keep in mind because it means that the opening of negotiations depends both on the willingness of the Commission and on the willingness of national governments.

The development of the negotiation, once it has been authorized, requires the appointment of the Union negotiator or the head of the Union's negotiating team. This decision is again a matter for the Council as well as the adoption of the negotiating directives. The requested majorities are still the same: qualified majorities or unanimity.

An exception to these ordinary rules applies if agreements are relating, ex art. 207 TFEU, to trade in goods and services, to the commercial aspects of intellectual property, to foreign direct investments, to the achievement of uniformity in measures of liberalisation, to export policies and to measures to protect trade.

In these cases, the negotiator is, by default, the European Commission, which shall conduct these negotiations in consultation with a special committee appointed by the Council to assist the Commission in this task and within the framework of such negotiating directives as the Council may issue to it.

The Commission as negotiator shall report regularly to the special committee and to the European Parliament on the progress of negotiations.

The conclusion of the agreement requires always the adoption of a decision by the Council authorising it, and, if necessary, its provisional application before entry into force.

In this phase, the European Parliament plays a key role because Article 217 requires its prior consent in a number of cases.

More in detail, the parliamentary consent is always necessary for: i) every association agreements; ii) the agreement on Union accession to the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms; iii) agreements establishing a specific institutional framework by

organising cooperation procedures; iv) agreements with important budgetary implications for the Union; v) agreements covering fields to which the legislative procedure requires the consent of the European Parliament.

As it is quite clear, the list is quite broad and cases *sub iv)* and *sub v)* may allow the enlargement of the competence of the European Parliament⁸.

In all other not listed cases, the European Parliament has not a veto power but still shall deliver its opinion within a time-limit set by the Council. In the absence of the opinion, the Council may act.

4. *Critical aspects of the described procedure.*

As it is clear “at the first sight” the procedure is quite burdensome.

In particular, it is worth underlining three main critical aspects.

The first relates to the fact that Council, as we already said, shall act by a qualified majority throughout the procedure and, in some case, it shall act unanimously.

The unanimity is obviously necessary when the agreement covers a field for which unanimity is required for the adoption of a Union act or in the fields of trade in services and the commercial aspects of intellectual property, of foreign direct investment, of trade in cultural and audiovisual services⁹, of trade in social, education and health services¹⁰.

Then, the unanimity is also *always* necessary (and it is particular important for the case under consideration) for any association agreements, as well as for the agreements with the States which are candidates for accession to the EU and for the specific agreement (already ongoing) on accession of the Union to the European Convention of Human Rights.

It is worth underlining, where the unanimity is required, the opposition of just one Member State in the Council may impede the conclusion of the agreement.

⁸ The real novelty, capable to enlarge the role of Parliament, is represented by the request of its consent for agreements covering fields to which the legislative procedure requires the consent of the European Parliament while the case of “agreements with important budgetary implications for the Union” has always been interpreted in a restrictive manner.

⁹ Where these agreements risk prejudicing the Union’s cultural and linguistic diversity in the field

¹⁰ Where these agreements risk disturbing the national organisation of such services and prejudicing the responsibility of Member States to deliver them.

Also where the Treaties require the qualified majority, it is necessary to assess that, in controversial cases, it could not be so easy to achieve. The discipline of the qualified majority for the adoption of the Council's decisions has a long history and suffered several changes with the evolution of the European integration.

Today, according to Article 16 of the Treaty on European Union (after Lisbon Treaty) a qualified majority shall be defined as at least 55 % of the members of the Council, comprising at least fifteen of them and representing Member States comprising at least 65 % of the population of the Union.

It means that a minority of countries (at least four Countries), which represent more than 35 % of the population of the Union, may always impede the beginning of the negotiation as well as the conclusion of the Agreement.

The second critical aspect concerns the role of the European Court of Justice. In fact, according to Article 218, par. 11, of the TFEU, a Member State, the European Parliament, the Council or the Commission may require the opinion of the Court of Justice as to whether an agreement envisaged is compatible with the Treaties.

If the opinion of the Court of Justice is adverse, the agreement envisaged may not enter into force, unless it is amended or the Treaties are revised.

The third critical aspect relates the cases where the EU negotiates agreements regarding matters which are in part under EU competence and in part under Member States competence. The Treaties do not rule a specific procedure for these "mixed agreements" neither an exact definition.

According with the jurisprudence of the European Court, we can affirm that the conclusion (and the entry into force) of these agreements requires also the approval of the Member States, according with their internal constitutional rules.

5. The examples of Anti-Counterfeiting Trade Agreement (ACTA) and Transatlantic Trade and Investment Partnership (TTIP).

Despite the undoubted complexity of the procedure, the European Union has negotiated and concluded quite many international agreements in the last few years. In many cases, through the consensus of the Member

States and the European Institutions, the conclusion raised no major problems.

Two cases that raised several critical issues may be really interesting, in the context of this contribution, because they concern important political and economic matters as well as sensitive topics for the public opinion

The first example is the Anti-Counterfeiting Trade Agreement (so called ACTA Agreement). It was a multinational treaty for the purpose of establishing international standards for intellectual property rights enforcement (ACTA). The contracting members were the EU, all its Member States, Australia, Canada, Japan, South Korea, Morocco, New Zealand, Singapore and the United States.

It is possible to consider it as a mixed agreement.

On one hand, EU had, in this case, exclusive and shared competence with Member States according to Article 4 of the EU Treaty; on the other hand some matters were a Member States competence. For this reason, the conclusion of ACTA Treaty required both the adoption of a Council decision and the signing and the approval of the Member States. In July 2012, the European Parliament voted overwhelmingly against the agreement reached by negotiators, "killing" ACTA inside of EU.

The second example is still ongoing.

It is the Transatlantic Trade and Investment Partnership (TTIP) which the EU (and its Member States) and USA are negotiating. The European Commission had the mandate by the Council to negotiate and represent both the European Union and its Member States. The process of negotiation has been reserved. Apart the publication of the directives of the Council almost all information on negotiations are coming from leaked documents.

In both cases, public opinions in the Member States reacted against even without knowing exactly the effective content of agreements. The decision to keep negotiation reserved was probably the main reason of the strong opposition. This experience should be taken due account in case of a negotiation between the European Union and the Eurasian Economic Union

6. Concluding remarks.

As I am a lawyer I have concentrated my attention on the rules which regulate the possibility for the European Union to negotiate and conclude international agreements with third countries or with other international organizations.

In order to understand, which are the real possibilities to begin a process of cooperation between the EU and the Eurasian Economic Union; it is then necessary to make two really general and final remarks about the current political situation and its impact on the prospect of a negotiation between the European Union and the Eurasian Economic Union.

The first important remark is related to the EU situation. As we all know, its very nature is today very different from its origin. Almost sixty years have passed from the birth of the first three Communities and today the European Union is much more than a custom union and really less than a political union or a Federation. Furthermore, seven rounds of enlargement modified not just the boundaries of the EU. New political issues appear with the Eastern Enlargement. In particular, as we all know, new concerns arise, at international level, regarding the relationship between EU and Russia. Moreover, the recent economic crises led to the adoption of strict rules about the formation of the national budgets (in particular for Member States that adopted the EURO currency) which are able to orient the internal political choices even in matters, like welfare state, which formally remained under the national authority power. All this produced different rifts: among Member States in favour and in contrast of a deeper integration, among western EU countries and eastern EU countries about international policies, among continental countries and southern countries about economic issues. These rifts make it difficult, today, to imagine that the EU can make choices that have to be unanimous or widely shared by all Member State Governments. Overall if the choice regards economic and politically oriented international agreements or association agreements.

The second important remark is about the international situation. We all know about crises inside of Europe and at its borders and about the effects they produced in the relationship between European Union and Russia as well as, from a legal point of view, the tension they created inside the legal system of the Council of Europe.

Leaving apart any different political understandings about these crises, I just would like to address two glosses.

First, as the German philosopher Immanuel Kant wrote more than two centuries ago – and history dramatically showed that he was right - just a strong cooperation and integration at international level and between all the European Countries may secure the perpetual peace and guarantee

prosperity to our entire Continent. For this reason it is necessary that every States, every Institutions and every International Organization shall, within its competence, make all possible effort to preserve the existing cooperation in order to work, in the next future, for a deeper cooperation between European Union and Eurasian Economic Union. Moreover, I think that the Jean Monnet approach to the European integration through the integration of markets and economies in order to preserve the peace and the stability may be applicable also to the perspective of an economic agreement between European Union and Eurasian Economic Union.

Second, it is not possible to obtain peace and stability without the involvement of those countries which represent “shared neighbourhood” of the EU and the EEU. For this reason any economic agreement between EU and EAEU should be enlarged to European countries which are not part of the European Union neither of Eurasian Economic Union. Just in this way, the cooperation could help to stabilize the current situation and to postpone the decision (which today appears critical for many geopolitical reasons) of their political participation to one or another European integration process.

Finally, in these days, difficult and sad for terroristic attacks which murdered innocents in every part of Europe, it is worth to remember and repeat, without fear to appear rhetoric, that “Greater Europe” already exists in terms of culture, values, principles and not questionable human rights and that the first objective – common to everybody in Europe – should be to protect and strengthen it.

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ECONOMIE / ECONOMICS

Cultural Economy and the New Bases of Debrecen's Development

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Abstract: Debrecen is not only the second most populous city in Hungary, but it is also a very important cultural, religious, educational and economic centre, whose effect is perceptible beyond the borders as well. In terms of city development, the city centre's renewal has great importance in Debrecen economy. It promotes, beside the built environment's renewal, the development of the cultural life (cultural economy) and the tourism. Debrecen's cross-border connections and the economic possibilities can be consolidated through this process as well.

Keywords: urban renewal, city centre, cultural economy, tourism.

Debrecen – The cultural-educational centre

Debrecen is an important spiritual, cultural and tourist centre of Northeast Hungary. The church, state and local institutions, which were established during the last centuries, contributed not only to the development of the city, but they also formed the city's morphology and a part of them (Reformed Great Church, Reformed College, St. Anna Cathedral etc.) are considered as important cultural and historical monuments and tourist sights.

In the last centuries Debrecen could owe its spiritual and cultural progress to the denominational schools. The Reformed College has to be mentioned in the first place, which raised the city from its surroundings and made a reputation during the centuries. Within the walls of the Reformed College not only the inhabitants of Debrecen have learnt but it has great attractive force for the city's wider surroundings included those areas where Hungarians live beyond the frontier. Lots of famous Hungarian poets,

writers, scientists and politicians have learnt in this school. Many of them were not born in Debrecen and they did not have any relationships with the city previously. The Reformed Theological University has possessed the building of the Reformed College from the autumn 2014. The Reformed Gedeon Dóczy Grammar School can be found in the city centre, too. Svetits Institute and the former Piarist School's successor, St Joseph Grammar School are the most important Roman Catholic schools in the city. Both of them are situated near the Roman Catholic St Anna Cathedral. Beside the mentioned Churches there are some smaller one in the city (Greek Catholic, Lutheran, Unitarian, Jewish), which have also built their own schools, communal houses next to or near their churches and chapels during the centuries. Next to the churches, parsonages, episcopal offices were built, too. The major part of the church buildings are now listed monument. One part of these buildings have (beside their religious and cultural importance) great tourist appeal as well. A real religious-cultural district has been developed in the neighbourhood of the Reformed Great Church and the St Anna Cathedral.

The economic development played great part in the urbanisation of Debrecen in the second half of the 19th and in the beginning of the 20th century. The centre of Debrecen renewed and because of the growing number of the craftsmen and tradesmen the functional areas of the city changed greatly.¹ The concept of city centre and the suburb were developed officially by that time.² Demand for both education and culture increased as well. Beside the first theatre lots of secondary schools were established at that time. Tourism was also developed and the city's one of the most famous hotel's building, Hotel Aranybika (Hotel Golden Bull), was finished at the end of this period (1915).

¹ István Süli-Zakar, "Debrecen Gazdaságának és településszerkezetének történeti-földrajza" [Debrecen's economy and settlement structure's historical geography], in *Tanulmányok Debrecen városföldrajzából II.* [Studies from Debrecen's urban geography II], ed István Süli-Zakar (Debrecen, Kossuth Lajos Tudományegyetem Társadalomföldrajzi Tanszék, 1996), 201-202.

² Lajos Sápi, "Debrecen városépítése és belterületének fejlődése, 1850-1918" [Debrecen's city building and the development of the inner city, 1850-1918], in *Debrecen története 1849-1919., 3. kötet* [Debrecen's history 1849-1919, Vol. 3], ed Péter Gunst (Debrecen, Csokonai Kiadó, 1997) 66-68.

The establishment of the university had great importance in many respects. It helped the city's spiritual and cultural development and preserved its regional leading part. The circumstance that Debrecen was a school city and the education had great tradition in the city played a great part in the foundation of the university. The university's cradle was the city's Reformed College, which assured (from the 16th century) the uninterrupted higher education in Debrecen and the faculties of the university were formed from its academic level branch.³ Through the university (est. 1912) Debrecen became the leading spiritual and educational centre of the northeast part of the country. The faculties of the university (theological, law, medical, arts and natural science) helped the inveteracy of many new branches of the science in the city. One part of the lessons was held in the rooms of the Reformed College until the buildings of the university have not been finished yet. The place for the buildings of the university was marked out in the Great Forest. The Great Forest, which borders Debrecen from the north, is the old wooded property of the city. When the university moved to the Great Forest the area was enriched with new functions. At first the clinics' buildings were built. The first administrative buildings were finished by 1918. The buildings continued in the next decades. The opening ceremony of the university's main building was held in 1932.⁴ Beyond the university buildings altered greatly the morphology of the environment, it formed a new intellectual field of force within the border of the city. We can look back to these changes from historical distance and those buildings, which were built at that time, represent significant cultural-historical worth in our days. It is especially true in the case of the university's main building, that is (with the park which lies in front of it) very important both from tourist and recreation aspect.

³ Károly Fekete, "A Debreceni Egyetem bölcsője a város Református Kollégiuma" [The city's Reformed College is the cradle of the University of Debrecen], in *A Debreceni Egyetem története 1912-2012* [History of the University of Debrecen 1912-2012], eds István Orosz and János Barta (Debrecen, Debreceni Egyetemi Kiadó, 2012) 15-16.

⁴ József Mudrák and Sándor Király, "Felépítés, működés, oktatás, tudományos munka. Az egyetem a két világháború között" [Building, operating, education, scientific work. The university between the two World War], in *A Debreceni Egyetem története 1912-2012* [History of the University of Debrecen], eds István Orosz and János Barta (Debrecen, Debreceni Egyetemi Kiadó, 2012) 57-59, 62-65.

The Great Forest (the City Park) is one of the most favourite recreation places for the inhabitants of Debrecen. In the time of the university construction (in the 1920s and 1930s) there were some other important investments in the area of the Great Forest. The area of the thermal and open-air baths was gradually developed, the old football stadium was built and the public cemetery was established in the eastern part of the forest. Beside the inhabitants of the city more and more tourists visited the Great Forest. Because of the great number of the visitors the services had to be improved as well.

After the World War II the tourist industry was hard to recover in the city. Since the stress was on the mass home-building (the city's huge housing estates were created at that time – in the 1970s and 1980s) and on the industrialization so the developments in the tourist industry were pushed into the background. The majority of the tourists came from Hungary and the most foreigners came from the former socialist countries. One of the most important tourist pageants is the Flower Carnival, which is organised every year on the 20th of August. Beside the failure of the tourist developments and because of the building prohibition in the city centre the situation became graver so by the time of the change of regime a considerable part of the buildings (mainly in the centre) became dilapidated.

Urban renewal as the basis of cultural economy

At the time of the change of regime the city centre of Debrecen (similarly to other Hungarian cities) showed neglected appearance. The local authority had to cope with the mass of the out-of-date old houses, the problem of the public places' restoration, the reformation of the traffic system, the raising of the services' level and it had to do something against the bad demographic statistics (aging population, moving from the inner city etc.) as well. Because of the bad economic conditions (the loss of the eastern markets, the closing of factories, the growth of unemployment rate, inflation etc.) the local authority had to work under bad conditions in the first part of the 1990s. Although there were some smaller house restorations in the city centre but bigger, overall reconstruction programs (because of the mentioned problems) could not be realised. Indeed, in the course of time, because of the developments which were behind and the motorization the situation became worse in the city centre. Some years after the change of regime the centre of the city was neglected, ruined and

it suffered from the huge traffic as well.⁵ The old plan of the city leaders for the renewal of Piac Street (the main street of Debrecen) and the forming of the (new) main square could not have realized yet. Public buildings with crumbling walls spoiled the view of the city in that time. The restoration of the remained small streets in the historical core of the city, the development of the infrastructure and the restoration of the old houses meant financial burden for both the local authority and the inhabitants. Arbitrary squatters moved into some empty houses, which had low conveniences in the centre. The removal of these undesired people was urgent for public order reasons, too.⁶ The development of these quarters just could be realized within the scope of a comprehensive renewal plan. The experts who had researched the city before called the attention to the necessity of demolition in the respect of the useless buildings and the importance of new streets' opening, which can make the exploration of inner ground plots possible and the starting of the necessary developments. According to them the mentioned problems would be solved by the help of the improving economy.⁷

The city' local authority realized the necessity of changes and decided on the block rehabilitation in 1993. In the next years the local authority strove to form the required establishments, the financial funds and it started to make the first plans for the reconstruction of the centre.⁸ The success of reconstruction was mainly financial question.⁹ Because of the

⁵ István Süli-Zakar (ed), "Debrecen fejlesztési elképzelései" [Debrecen's development conceptions], ed István Süli-Zakar (Debrecen, Debreceni Regionális Gazdaságfejlesztési Alapítvány, 1994) 207.

⁶ Tibor Kecskés, "Debrecen városfejlődése a rendszerváltás után" [Debrecen's city development after the change of regime], in *Falvaink sorsa" és "A városnövekedés szakaszai". Tisztelgés a 80 éves Enyedi György akadémikus előtt* [„Our villages' fortune" and „The city growth's stages" Salutation of the 80 year-old academic György Enyedi], ed István Süli-Zakar (Debrecen, Debreceni Egyetem Kossuth Egyetemi Kiadó, 2011) 133.

⁷ Süli-Zakar, "Debrecen fejlesztési elképzelései ...," 207-208.

⁸ Gábor Kozma, "A városmarketing elemeinek alkalmazása Debrecenben a rendszerváltozás után" [City marketing in Debrecen since the change of regime], in *Studia Geographica 7.*, ed in chief István Süli-Zakar (Debrecen, A Kossuth Lajos Tudományegyetem Földrajzi Tanszékeinek Kiadványa, 1999) 73-77.

⁹ Attila Csaba Kondor, "A városrehabilitáció fő színterei – egy megvalósult projekt bemutatása" [The main scenes of urban renewal – a realized project's introduction], in *Városfejlődés és városrehabilitáció. Budapesti és lipcsei tapasztalatok* [City development

difficult financial circumstances the local authority had to wait with the launching of the projects. In this period there was little money for cultural developments and the city's tourists' growth was not so intense, as it was expected before. The lack of developments and projects could be also felt. Because of the poor milieu, the few and unsuitable hotel rooms, the enticement of the tourists became harder. The Hotel Aranybika, which was the pride of Debrecen some decades before, lost its gloss by the 1990s. Though some smaller hotels and pensions were built in the city but their capacity and the offered services were not appropriate for everybody.

The economic situation became better from the end of the 1990s and it made possible the realization of bigger projects and developments. Within the urban renewal there were lots of cultural projects and important tourist developments during the last two decades. These projects led to many changes, which transformed the morphology of the city. Naturally, the conservation of the quarters' original structure is an important question during the city (centre) renewal.¹⁰

The renewal began with the main street, which grows wider in front of the Great Church. A particular street structure developed in the city centre some centuries ago. Instead of the main square a main street was born, which grew wider in front of the Great Church (the former St Andrew Church). The problem came from the fact that there was not real main square in the heart of the city, where the inhabitants and the tourists could stop and rest a bit or where they could sit down and talk to each other etc. The problem was on the other hand that those inhabitants who lived in the main street had to suffer a lot from the huge traffic which flowed through the city centre. Beside the small green area there were some benches as well, but the first task of this area was the conducting of the motor and pedestrian traffic. After a long planning procedure, the end of the 1990s gave the chance for the local authority to renew or restore this area. According to the plans such kind of main square had to be created in the heart of the city where people could have a rest, by the help of colourful programmes they could have a good time or just relax. Naturally all this led

and urban renewal. Budapest and Leipzig experiences], eds Attila Csaba Kondor and Tamás Egedy (Budapes, Magyar Földrajzi Társaság, 2007) 74.

¹⁰ Tamás Egedy, "Városrehabilitáció és életminőség" [Urban renewal and the quality of life], (Budapest, MTA Földrajztudományi Kutatóintézet, 2009) 76-79.

(with the exception of tram) to the expelling of the motor traffic. The building started in 2000 and the inhabitants could take the (new) main square over in the next year.

So the opening of the main square (officially: Kossuth Square) was the first very important stage of the urban renewal in Debrecen. The forming of the main square created a new tourist target area within the city centre. Beside the Great Church (which is the symbol of Debrecen and a scenic spot itself) the square became rich with new things. We have to mention among the new scenic spots the coat of arms of Debrecen, which can be found in front of the statue of Kossuth, the glass pyramid, which was built by the Great Church and represents an old destroyed tower and the two fountains that can be mentioned, too. The green areas ensure the care-free complete rest for both the inhabitants and the tourists. The aim of the leaders of the city and the architects was the creation of a new square, which refers (by the help of the new elements of the square) to the past of Debrecen and can be the scene those cultural mass programmes that are organized by the city.¹¹ The main square became suitable for not only cultural programmes, but for the organisation of different events (different festivals, book week, and the accompanying programmes of the Flower Carnival) as well. Beside the mentioned, political programmes can be also held in the main square. The market, which is held before Christmas, reminds us of the old function of the square. The cafés and restaurants which were opened in the past years, indicates the growing importance of tourism in the centre.

The new Kölcsey Cultural Centre (opened in 2006) is the biggest conference centre in East Hungary and is suitable for the organization of different cultural events and conferences. The Modern and Contemporary Art Centre (MODEM) can be found here, too. The biggest art gallery of the Northern Great Plain Region can be found in this three-storeyed building. The area of the building is 4.650 square meters and it has 3.000 square

¹¹ Gábor Biczó, "Séta a debreceni Kossuth téren, avagy a „vizuális narratológia” gyakorlatban” [Walk on Debrecen Kossuth Square, or the „visual narratology” in practice], in *Terek és szövetek. Újabb perspektívák a városkutatásban* [Spaces and textures. Newer perspectives in the city research], eds Tímea N. Kovács, Gábor Böhm and Tamás Mester (Budapest, Kijárat Kiadó, 2005) 88.

meters for exhibitions.¹² The third part of this building complex is the Hotel Lycium. One of the reasons of its building was those conferences, which are arranged in the Kölcsey Centre. So the hotel plays important part in the business and conference tourism. The building complex was finished and opened in 2006. Baltazár Dezső Square, which is one of the newest squares of Debrecen, was formed in modern style between the Kölcsey Centre and Déri Museum. This square connects the building complex with the museum and the Déri Square. The reconstruction of Déri Square finished (after the opening of the main square) in 2002. In the case of this square the main task was the preservation of the recreation character. Beside the renewal of the vegetation and the restoration of fountain, new benches were set out. Both squares are linked with important cultural institutions and they make possible the arrangement of outdoor programmes for them. Déri Square (first of all) for the museum's visitors and the Baltazár Dezső Square for the Kölcsey's visitors offer possibilities for recreation or relax. The inner reconstruction of Déri Museum also finished some years ago. Nowadays the museum is a multifunction institution, whose one of the main tasks is the entertainment of the visitors.¹³ The characteristic feature of the function change of the museums is that they try to organize more spectacular temporary exhibition, which can be attractive for uninitiated people, too. The changes have another feature: 'the museums' shops have become cultural supermarkets' moreover 'the museums have become not only cultural spaces but consumer spaces as well'.¹⁴

The building of the Reformed College, where an important exhibition of ecclesiastical art and a library can be found, is situated behind the Great Church, near the Museum. Kálvin Square, which also got over a reconstruction in the near past, is situated between the College and the Great Church. The project, which was a part of the city rehabilitation started

¹² Euro-Régió Ház Kht., "Debrecen Megyei Jogú Város Integrált Városfejlesztési Stratégiája" [Debrecen's integrated city development strategy], (Debrecen, 2008) 77.
http://portal.debrecen.hu/upload/File/Gazdasag/varosrehabilitacio/IVS_Debrecen_20080407.pdf (accessed: 10/06/2015)

¹³ György Enyedi, "A városok kulturális gazdasága" [The cities' cultural economy], in *A magyar városok kulturális gazdasága* [The Hungarian cities' cultural economy] eds György Enyedi and Krisztina Keresztély (Budapest, MTA Társadalomkutató Központ, 2005) 24-25.

¹⁴ *Ibidem*, 24.

in 2009 and it was finished two years later. Beside the renewal of vegetation, the footpaths, the benches and the lighting were also mended and renewed. Over the restoration this area gained new functions: a café with a gallery was formed just behind the Great Church.

Through the urban renewal projects the area that is between the Great Church and Kölcsey Centre has prominent importance in the city's tourism and cultural economy. There was significant progress in the infrastructure of this area in the near past. The cultural district of Debrecen is forming in front of our eyes. The formation of the city's cultural districts can connect the reconstruction of the ruined districts with those projects, which want to execute different cultural plans.¹⁵ Owing to the urban renewal a more or less homogeneous cultural district was formed during the last years and decades.

We have to mention (among others) the alteration of Csapó Street, where a Mediterranean style pedestrian area was formed. In this section of Csapó Street the old houses and some shops changed function and were renewed. The old flower market disappeared from the street and one part of the flower-sellers moved into the new market's building. The huge building of Debrecen Forum was built on the corner of Csapó and Rákóczi Street. The planned Latinovits Theatre (which will work in Forum) has not been finished yet.

One of the city centre's newest pedestrian streets is the Simonffy Street and the neighbouring Hal Alley. The tourist attraction became important in both areas during the last years. The restoration of the upper section of Simonffy Street finished in 2004, while the renewed Hal Alley was opened in 2010. It is important to mention that during the reconstruction of Hal Alley there was a block exploration in this area as well. Through the exploration a direct connection was created with the neighbouring Bajcsy-Zsilinszky Street. Not only the values of the properties have become higher but this area can enjoy the benefits of tourism by the help of reconstruction. One of the most striking features of this area is those cafés, which were opened in the last years. In the neighbourhood of these cafés we can find confectioneries, galleries, travel agencies and shops, which sell special

¹⁵ Anna Wessely, "Városi kultúrák és kulturális negyedek" [City cultures and cultural quarters], in *A kulturális negyed mint városfejlesztési stratégia* [The cultural quarter as an urban development strategy], ed Balázs Berkecz (Pécs, Európa Centrum Kht., 2007) 21.

things. This part of the city centre has gained big popularity within a short time. We can fixed that those questions which are connection with the society, the environment and the quality of life become more and more important during the urban renewal.¹⁶ So it is not surprising that this area is more popular among those people who want to buy a flat in the city centre. The old, ruined buildings' places are occupied by more and more new, modern and chic houses. The city renewal makes positive changes in the inhabitants' housing conditions and encourages the mobilization of the flats.¹⁷

People (thanks for the cultural institutions, art galleries, exhibitions, different associations etc.) can choose from among many high-standard, colourful programs in the city centre. In the new pedestrian streets we can also find cafés, bars and confectioneries. Because of the mentioned changes the centre of Debrecen has important part in the cultural life of the city. It is also important that the renewal of the city centre helps not only the renewal of Debrecen but give back the former spirit of the city.¹⁸

The cultural economy of Debrecen

Nowadays the cultural economy, which is based on the humanity's spiritual and cultural heritage, plays important part in the development of the settlements. We know many international and Hungarian examples in connection with those cities, which had traditional but out-of-date industries and sought the way out through the education and cultural developments. By the help of these developments their economic structure has been changed and the importance of cultural economy has become larger.

If we want to draw on a map the most important cultural institutions, which operate in Debrecen, we can observe three areas (Figure 1). The cultural economy has strong concentration in the city centre. We can mention here the Reformed College with the Reformed Theological University and the building of the former Teacher's Training College. Déri Museum, Kölcsey Centre with MODEM and the city's theatres also belong to this area.

¹⁶ Kondor, "A városrehabilitáció fő színterei...", 73-74.

¹⁷ Egedy, "Városrehabilitáció és életminőség...", 76-79.

¹⁸ Süli-Zakar, "Debrecen fejlesztési elképzelései...", 207-208., 225.

If we examine both the international and the Hungarian plans for the renewal of the city centre we can see that the renewal of the cultural districts have great importance. If there is not cultural district in the city, in this case the development of one can be also important. Their establishment can help not only the passing on the material and spiritual heritage but they play important part in the forming of community and in the renewal of the city's cultural identity.¹⁹

The forming or renewed cultural districts also play important part in the promoting of the city's economic life. On the other hand we have to see that (in the developed countries) it was not the real reason in the increase of the cultural districts that the local governments have discovered suddenly they require the high culture but they realised that the forming of cultural districts is a good chance for the promoting of the local economy and their cities will become attractive places for investors.²⁰ The renewed, restored environment can make chance for the civilized administration, shopping, entertainment facilities and relaxing. Among the buyers there are more and more tourists in the pedestrian streets. Naturally the tourists' attitude depend on their motivation (why did they visit the place), their social status (their wallet's size), but the cities themselves can offer different kind of relaxation and entertainment facilities.²¹

¹⁹ János Gömör, J. "Egy városrész új szerepe az urbanista szemével" [The role of a new quarter from an urbanist's perspective], in *A kulturális negyed, mint városfejlesztési stratégia* [The cultural quarter as an urban development strategy], ed Balázs Berkecz (Pécs, Európa Centrum Kht., 2007) 100.

²⁰ Wessely, "Városi kultúrák...", 23.

²¹ Bálint Kádár, "Spatial Patterns of Urban Tourism in Vienna, Prague and Budapest", in *Metropolitan Regions in Europe*, eds Viktória Szirmai and Heinz Fassmann (Budapest, HVG Press Kiadó, 2012) 278.

*Figure 1 The concentration of cultural institutions in Debrecen
(1 City centre 2 Great Forest 3 Kassai Street)*

As a result of the conscious city planning, qualitative city environment was developed by the city renewal. The popular pedestrian

streets as a magnet attract both the inhabitants of the city and the tourists. The cafés and bars are open till late hours in the most popular pedestrian streets. Tourists can buy souvenirs in different points of the city. Quality souvenirs can be bought not only in the main street (Piac Street), but in the shops' streets as well. The shops' streets, which usually have direct connection with the main street, can be found behind the doorways. Some of them were formed by the help of the house or block restorations some years ago.

In the north part of Debrecen, in the wider surroundings of the Great Forest (within the University City) the institutions of the cultural economy become denser. The area of the three campuses with the main building of the university, the building of chemistry, - ecology, mathematics – informatics and the life science building can be found there. The botanical garden, the psychology, the foreign language centre and the building of the conservatory can be added to the previous list. The area of clinics was joined to the area of the central campus after the university integration. The campus of the Centre for Agricultural is attached to the other two campuses' area by the buildings of MTA (Hungarian Academy of Science) Debrecen Regional Committee and Újkert Cultural Centre. The cultural and tourist institutions of the Great Forest (Aquaticum Thermal Baths, Cultural Park, open-air theatre, the stadiums) are in the immediate neighbourhood of the University City.

The university education has favoured part in Debrecen's life. Debrecen with its university institutions is one of the most important regional centres of Hungary. It is supported by the great number of university students and the diversity of the facultative courses. What is more after the integration the University of Debrecen it has become the biggest employer in the city. The gravitational area (similar to the public health) of the higher education of Debrecen is very important and it surpasses the scope of the city's agglomeration. We can also notice that the students mainly come from northeast Hungary.²² In the case of the

²² Károly Teperics, "Debrecen szerepe Kelet-Magyarország humán erőforrásainak képzésében" [Debrecen's role in teaching of East Hungary's human resources], in *Tanulmányok Debrecen városföldrajzából III.* [Studies from Debrecen's urban geography III], ed István Süli-Zakar (Debrecen, Kossuth Lajos Tudományegyetem Társadalomföldrajzi és Területfejlesztési Tanszék, 1998) 263-280.

education the gravitational area extends over the border of the country. Lots of Hungarian beyond the frontier learns at the University of Debrecen, too. Their percentage is about 3 or 4%. They come from mainly Romania and the Ukraine. The faculty of medicine of the university is chosen by more than 3000 foreign students year by year.

There are many colleges, which can ensure lodgings to the students in the city. The bigger half of the students live as lodgers while the smaller part of them as flat owners live in the different districts of Debrecen. Many of them buy flats in the district of Újkert, near the buildings of the university. (Újkert is one of the biggest housing estates of the city.) The big number of the student householders, in those districts which are near to the university's buildings, reflects the fact that Debrecen is a university city.²³ The presence of these students leaves its mark on the society of these districts. Because they are in great number in these districts so those institutions or shops, which belong to the cultural economy and offer different services to them, can appear in a short time. These institutions do not belong to the faculties of the university and they are small businesses, which are in private property. Internet cafés, bookshops, stationeries, book binderies, copies etc. can belong to these institutions. The pizzerias, cafés, confectioneries, fast food restaurants, which can be found here, also try to conform their services to the students' demands. The crowd of the young people in the streets and the bustling night life are contradiction to the housing estates' society's degradation that is perceptible in the western countries and has already occurred in Hungary as well. It is clear that this phenomenon owns to the neighbourhood of the university and the students' residences.²⁴

The number of the inhabitants of Debrecen is reduced by the negative balance of demographic statistics but the growing rate of the

²³ Ilona Ekéné Zamárdi, "A vándorlás szerepe Debrecen népesedésében" [The migration's role in the Debrecen's population], in *Tanulmányok Debrecen városföldrajzából II.* [Studies from Debrecen's urban geography II] ed István Süli-Zakar (Debrecen, Kossuth Lajos Tudományegyetem Társadalomföldrajzi Tanszék, 1996) 124-137.

²⁴ István Süli-Zakar, Károly Teperics, Ilona Ekéné Zamárdi and Gábor Kozma, "A kulturális gazdaság szerepe Debrecen versenyképességének fokozásában" [The cultural economy's role in the improvement of Debrecen's competitiveness], in *A magyar városok kulturális gazdasága* [The Hungarian cities' cultural economy], ed György Enyedi and Krisztina Keresztély (Budapest, MTA Társadalomkutató Központ, 2005) 196-198.

students and qualified employees among the newcomers helps the development of the city's society towards the positive direction.²⁵ As the city is attractive for the qualified people after the leaving of the university (maybe because of the better possibilities of work or the cultural, and entertainment possibilities) so many of them settle down in Debrecen later.²⁶ Consequently Debrecen has influence on one part of its graduate students and it can keep them. The graduate students of the university mean the intellectual capital in this region. The presence of the graduate employees raises the city from its surroundings and makes (through the traditional cultural services) the centre of the region. We can say that the University of Debrecen has good effect on the human source of power and the competitiveness of the region furthermore the part of the university is indisputable in the settlement of the knowledge economy work, qualified workforce. Almost one third of the students in the local higher education come from Debrecen. Among them the clinging to the city is typical and three-quarters of them stay Debrecen.²⁷

If we look into the matter from the point of view of the society we can establish that the great number students who stay in the city have favourable influence on the cultural economy and its strengthening in Debrecen. The successful development of the city needs the strong and qualified middle class. This middle class has strong need for non-material things. This class wants to spend its money in those cities, which have attractive cultural, natural and built surroundings. A prosperous city's inhabitants expect for the continued aesthetic building of the city squares, the high quality flats, and the varied cultural life.²⁸

The Kassai Street campus and its surroundings is the youngest concentration centre of the cultural economy in Debrecen. Among others, the faculty of law and economics, the general health centre and a multi-function building (Lovarda), which plays increasing part in the cultural life of the city, can be found here. Hódos Imre Sport Hall and the Főnix Hall, which plays important part in the international sport and cultural life, can be found

²⁵ Ibidem, 198-201.

²⁶ Ekéné Zamárdi, "A vándorlás szerepe...", 124-137.

²⁷ Süli-Zakar, Teperics, Ekéné and Kozma, "A kulturális gazdaság...", 203.

²⁸ György Enyedi, "A sikeres város" [The succesful city], in *Tér és társadalom*, 1997. 4. sz. [Place and Society, 1997. Vol. 4.], p. 4.

in the right neighbourhood of the Kassai Street campus. The building of the faculty of technical is a bit further from the Kassai Street campus.

The local authority (as the maintainer, the organizer of the cultural life) has a great part in the cultural economy of Debrecen. Different educational and cultural institutions (Csokonai National Theatre, Vojtina Puppet Theatre, Debrecen Cultural Centre etc.) are under the control of the local authority. The institutions, which are under the control of the local authority, satisfy first of all the inhabitants' demands. The visitors of Méliusz Library, the audience of Csokonai Theatre or the concert halls' comes mainly from the city.²⁹

The audience of the different programmes gets out considerably from Debrecen and the nearby settlements and the only exception may be the Flower Carnival. Visitors often double Debrecen's population during the Carnival. It is an important thing that these programmes can provide possibility for the renewal and the renovation of the ruined districts and for the extension of functions.³⁰ Naturally, by the help of the cultural programmes the city's attractive force grows. The attention of the media that follows the programmes ensures free of charge advertising for the place and the name of this place (where the programmes take place) gets on the mental map that is in the people's head. If the name of a place is already on this map, then it will be more stressed and its notoriety rises as tourist destination and a potential investment region.³¹

The organization or the arrangement of the different cultural programmes links with the name of Főnix Program Organizer Ltd, which was established in 2003. Its tasks are (among the others) the organization of different programmes and the operation of those institutions, which belong to the Főnix.³²

The function of the Főnix can be divided into four groups:

²⁹ Süli-Zakar, Teperics, Ekéné Zamárdi and Kozma, "A kulturális gazdaság..." 206-212.

³⁰ Gábor Kozma, "Terület- és településmarketing" [Region- and settlement marketing], (Debrecen, Kossuth Egyetemi Kiadó, Egyetemi jegyzet, 2005) 111-112.

³¹ Ibidem, oldalszám.

³² István Süli-Zakar (ed), "A Főnix Rendezvényszervező Kht. szerepe Debrecen kulturális gazdaságában" [Főnix Program Organizer's role in Debrecen's cultural economy], (Debrecen, Róna-Régió Kft., 2007) 4.

- The running of Kölcsey Centre and the organization of its programmes,
- The running of Főnix Hall,
- The running of Apollo Art Cinema,
- The organization of Debrecen's most important programmes.

The Főnix Program Organizer wants to entice (through its programmes) the inhabitants of Debrecen and its surroundings. About 15 large programmes are organized by the Főnix every year. These programmes are arranged in different points of the city and they can differ from each other in genre. The best known are the next: Flower Carnival, Debrecen Jazz Festival, International Festival of Military Bands and Béla Bartók International Choir and Folklore Festival. Főnix has determinant part in the development of the cultural economy of Debrecen. It increases (with its cultural programmes) the tourist force of attraction of the city and influences 'the sale' of cultural goods of Debrecen. Besides it helps to form a positive image from the city greatly, it contributes to the improvement of the inhabitants' quality of life, their civilized amusement, the reproduction of their generating energy and the building of the healthy parochialism, too.³³

We also have to mention those (mainly gastronomical) programmes that were held in the main square in the near past (Debrecen Turkey Festival, Mangalica – a breed of pigs – Festival, Goose Feast etc.). In relation to the city's programmes, in general the former statement is true that mostly the inhabitants of Debrecen visit these programmes and it is difficult to entice the inhabitants of the neighbouring settlements.³⁴ We cannot forget that the high quality arrangement of the different programmes needs that high quality infrastructure, which was developed during the last years.

In the case of the programmes' financial balance we can state that the incomes, which come from the selling of tickets, sponsorship and competition money generally do not cover the expenses. Therefore we cannot expect that the cost of every programme will be refunded.³⁵ Naturally the arrangement of a successful programme can be more

³³ Ibidem, 83-86.

³⁴ Kozma, "A városmarketing elemeinek alkalmazása...", 81.

³⁵ Süli-Zakar, Teperics, Ekéné and Kozma, "A kulturális gazdaság...", 211.

profitable. It is important because the image of a city, which has been developed or the city has created itself, can continue to live.³⁶ The favourable impressions and the positive image of a city, that the tourists take home have much more importance in a longer way.

The cultural economy and the tourism in Debrecen's life from the point of view of urban renewal

The required economic background is (as we saw it above) the condition of the realization of the urban renewal projects. The realization of the necessary reconstructions and developments needs lots of money. The city rehabilitation projects animate the economy and attract the investors. Either demolition or building, these ensure possibility of work for the surroundings' enterprises. The investors make investments into the projects with more pleasure if they see the possibility of the refund.

We can find lots of examples in connection with the European city (centre) renewal in the scientific literature. The recipe is similar almost everywhere: The local authorities strive for the renewal of the built environment and the formation of the liveable cities by the help of the function extension city rehabilitation.³⁷ In the course of Debrecen's city centre rehabilitation the authority has put great emphasis on the creation of the ordered environment, the increase of the green areas and it has made the civilized amusement possible. We saw how the centre of Debrecen underwent different transformations during the city rehabilitation. Both the inhabitants of Debrecen and the tourists are the favoured of these transformations and developments.

The ordered environment is not enough for the tourists' enticement to the city, beside those attractive programmes, civilized entertainment

³⁶ János Rechnitzer, "Debrecen és a nagyvárosok innovációs környezete" [Debrecen and the big cities' innovation surroundings], in *Debrecen megyei jogú város makroregionális szerepköre* [Debrecen city's macro-regional role], ed István Süli-Zakar (Pécs-Debrecen, MTA-RKK, 1994) 104-106.

³⁷ Erika Nagy, "Fall and Revival of City Centre Retailing: Planning an Urban Function in Leicester, Britain." In Centre for Regional Studies of Hungarian Academy of Sciences, Discussion Papers, No. 26. (Pécs, 1999) 45-47.

Vanessa R. Hünemeyer, "Urban regeneration by large-scale urban projects: Case studies from Budapest and Liverpool. Urban Regeneration in Liverpool." In *Metropolitan Regions in Europe*, eds Viktória Szirmai and Heinz Fassmann (Budapest, HVG Press Kiadó, 2012) 62-69. Bálint Kádár, "Spatial Patterns...", 278-281.

facilities and recreational activities have to be promised. The city has to provide special programmes or recreational activities which can be found only in the city or in its surroundings. This kind of special programme or recreational activity can be the Flower Carnival or the thermal bath in the Great Forest.

Nowadays the conference-, sport- and the health tourism play more important part in the tourist life of Debrecen. It is true that the conference tourism is just for a special, small part of tourists, but these programmes give occasion for acquisition of knowledge. The importance of conference tourism is on the one hand that it can help the extension of tourist season. On the other hand the participants of these conferences usually spend more money than the ordinary tourists. Their feature is the resort of higher price level services, the prestige consumption.³⁸ Those hotels, which were built (mainly) for the satisfaction of the conference tourism's demands during the last years, can promise high quality services nowadays. Many sports events were also held in Debrecen in the last two decades. The arrangement of these events has induced further developments. The Főnix Hall was built, the athletic stadium was reconstructed and modernized greatly, and a new city swimming pool and an ice rink were built as well. The new Great Forest Stadium with capacity 20.000 was one of the most important projects in the near past. (The Stadium was opened 1st of May 2014.) We can mention among the tourist purpose developments the reconstruction of the one hundred-year-old water tower, which stands right next to the new stadium. A café and a lookout were shaped in the tower in 2015. Beside the reconstruction of the thermal bath and its hotel the city's open-air stage and its environment were also restored. These developments are connected with the Great Forest's reconstruction works.

The financial subsidies that the city competed successfully played great part in the last years' tourist developments. The Debrecen Thermal Bath Ltd. could build in 2003 the Aquaticum Mediterranean Pleasure Baths by the help of the tourism development program of Széchenyi Plan (2000-2004). Hungary joined the European Union in 2004. From this date the country can get different financial supports from the Union. The National

³⁸ Gábor Michalkó, "A városi turizmus elmélete és gyakorlata" [The city tourism's theory and practice] (Budapest, MTA Földrajztudományi Kutató Intézet, 1999) 114-116.

Development Plan Regional Operative Programme (2004-2006) then the New Hungary Development Plan (2007-2013) helped the realization of different plans. Due to the successful competitions further important developments could happen in Debrecen. The Kölcsey Conference Centre joined with the art gallery of MODEM and the Hotel Lycium was built by the support of the Conference Tourist Development Program. We have already mentioned above (connected with the city renewal) those projects (the forming of the new main square, reconstruction of Déri Museum, Főnix Hall, new swimming pool etc.), which were carried out by the help of different competition money. There were some important hotel developments in the studied period. It is worth to mention the four-star Hotel Óbester, which was built near the city centre from the pecuniary assistance of the European Union and (the only five-star hotel in Debrecen) the Hotel Divinius, which can be found in the Great Forest and was built by private investment. The four-star Hotel Platán and the four-star Erdőspuszta Club Hotel also belong to the newest hotels of the city.³⁹ The development of the Aquaticum Debrecen Thermal and Wellness Hotel also happened in the near past.

Since the tourism is influenced by economic situation, so when we want to examine this topic we have to consider the economic changes, too. During the change of regime (when the economic system changed and both the unemployment rate and the inflation became higher) in the case of Debrecen the fall of the tourism could be observed. After the millennium, because of the important tourist developments the statistical indexes got better. The tourist traffic first exceeded the rate of 1990 in 2007. The financial and economic crisis in 2008 retarded the development and (in spite of the efforts) the tourist traffic of Debrecen has diminished since then.⁴⁰ We have to see, that audience of the city's programmes comes mainly from Debrecen and from its surroundings. In other respect the money and the energy that were devoted to the different developments can be recovered many times. The city's hotels, the catering trade and the different enterprises are (beside the inhabitants and the tourists) the beneficiaries of

³⁹ Katalin Martonné Erdős and Mária Vasvári, "Debrecen turisztikai fejlesztései és azok hatásai az ezredforduló után" [Debrecen's tourist developments and their effects after the millennium], in *Emberközpontú társadalomföldrajz* [Human centred social geography], ed Gábor Kozma (Debrecen, DIDAKT Kft., 2013) 103.

⁴⁰ *Ibidem*, 106.

these developments. Not only the hotels and the restaurant owners, but the suppliers, the shops that sell souvenirs and other things, and everybody who is in financial connection with the tourists can make a profit from their visiting. The tourism is that sector of the national economy, that during the production of the goods supports (against other sector of the national economy) wider profitability and with the recycling of the income further income can be obtained.⁴¹

Debrecen (and its surroundings) can only lure the tourists with attractive tourist products and successful marketing policy. It is important that the leaving tourists go home with nice memories and take away the reputation of the city. The different cultural, sports and other programmes can also raise the city's reputation.

We cannot forget that the university's intellectual potential can give the basis for different developments in the city. The university is one of the most important driving forces of the cultural economy, too. The university students, who rent lodgings, use different services or sometimes go out, as cultural consumers appear in Debrecen's economy.

Figure 2 The main building of the university
Source: <http://debrecen.utisugo.hu/latnivalok>

⁴¹ Michalkó, "A városi turizmus elmélete...", 23.

Summary

The education played great part in the development of the historical city. The Reformed College then the establishment of the university helped Debrecen to become school (university) city. The cultural institutions of the city were developed in the last two centuries. The tourism started to play important part in the city's life at the beginning of the 20th century. After the World War II the stress was on the industrialization and the home-building. Though there were some smaller improvement related to the tourism but the general decay of the city environment did not encourage the development of tourism. The city's (and the centre's) renewal was an urgent task after the change of regime. The first bigger renewal projects started at about the millennium in Debrecen.

Nowadays, when we talk about the urban renewal the primary aim is the formation of a liveable, practical cityscape. For the formation a regular cityscape the recipe is same everywhere: the reconstruction of the built environment, the formation of pedestrian squares and streets, the districts' function extension reconstruction and the development of the small trade and the catering trade's level. These processes have taken place in the same way in Debrecen and (despite of the well-known world economic crisis) they have positive effect to the city's economy and the tourist traffic.

Debrecen is in a particular position because of its university. The university is the city's biggest employer and it has important effect on its cultural economy. The university teachers and the several thousand students' demand on the teaching training and the civilized entertainment have positive effect on the cultural economy.

The development of Debrecen's cultural economy has been helped by those projects that have created for the city the necessary institution background. The infrastructure, which is suitable for the arrangement of the different high level programmes, has been developed by now. The cultural, sport and other programmes can attract more and more people. Although the inhabitants of Debrecen take part in these programmes mostly, but the local authority and the concerned people try to do their best in order that the developments can be continued and these investments promote the city's tourism's development.

The qualitative changes, which have occurred during the recent years, have formed a wide-ranging cultural economy in Debrecen. In our

opinion the cultural economy will gain bigger part in the city's life, since with the improvement of living standards and with the increase of the tourists' number the inhabitants will need for the cultural goods and the consumption will rise rapidly. The cultural economy is the most important driving force in Debrecen's life and the primary factor in the city's contention in our days.

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Can the Experience of Visegrad Countries Help Moldova to Integrate in the European Union?

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Abstract: The Visegrad countries (Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland and Slovakia) successfully realized the economic transition to market economy, the fact that allowed the countries to increase their economic performance, competitiveness and to integrate in the European Union. They accumulated wide experience in the economic reform implementation process, allowing them to foster and strengthen the economic progress. The analysis of followed steps and undertaken reforms by these countries allowed identifying and determining some recommendations for the Republic of Moldova to follow, in order to foster the European Integration process, increase its competitiveness and economic growth.

Keywords: Visegrad Group, Economic reforms, transition period, European Integration, market economy, competitiveness.

Introduction

The Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland and Slovakia (known as Visegrad Group) have always been part of a single civilization sharing cultural and intellectual values and common roots in diverse religious traditions, which they wish to preserve and further strengthen. The Visegrad cooperation can currently be referred to as the most clearly profiled initiative in Central Europe. The backbone of this cooperation consists of mutual contacts at all levels—from the highest-level political summits to expert and diplomatic meetings, to activities of the non-governmental associations in the region, think-tanks and research bodies, cultural institutions or numerous networks of individuals.

The Visegrad countries have shown prodigious economic development successes since the fall of communist order in the Eastern

Europe, accumulating extremely important experience in transforming former socialist inheritance into a progressive, market driven economy based on competition. It is obvious that for European integration aspiring nations, such as the Republic of Moldova, Ukraine, Georgia, the experience of the Visegrad states would be a valuable input in raising the country's performance in reform implementing process leading to EU.

The idea of formation of an inter-state platform to increase the cooperation between newly democratized former communist countries from central Europe was proposed in 1991 by Lech Walesa, Poland's President, Vaclav Havel, the president of Czechoslovakia and the prime minister of Hungary, Jozsef Antal. This reunion possessed a symbolic character creating an imaginary historical arch linking the idea of this meeting to the idea of similar meeting, which took place in 1335 attended by John of Luxembourg, King of Bohemia, Charles I of Anjou, King of Hungary, and Casimir III, King of Poland. The main reason for the two reunions was the desire to intensify the cooperation and friendship among the three countries. It was clear, that the new democratic nations should unite their efforts in order to obtain positive synergy in overcoming transition period. Therefore, the proper idea of Visegrad formation was motivated by the necessity of cooperation in social, economic and political fields. In that period, the Visegrad countries were driven by similar reform goals starting with the desire to eliminate the remnants of the communist bloc in the Central Europe, to overcome historical animosities, finishing with the belief that through joint efforts it will be easier to successfully accomplish social economic transformation and thus having the possibility to join the European Union integration process.

Economic, social and political performance of the Republic of Moldova in comparison with Visegrad countries

Nowadays, Poland, Czech Republic, Slovak Republic and Hungary demonstrate high economic results, the bases of which have been put at the beginning of the transition period. Contrary, the Republic of Moldova did not build a functioning market economy since it has not realized efficiently economic reforms. In order to assess the enormous economic development disparity between the Republic of Moldova, on one hand, and Visegrad group states on the other, some macroeconomic indicators are analysed (i.e. GDP, GDP/capita (PPP), competitiveness index, corruption perception index,

human development index etc.). It is worth to be mentioned that, in order to make the analysis more relevant, the analysis cover the entire period of transition of Visegrad countries to the market economy till present (i.e. 1990-2014).

The analysis of GDP/Capita (PPP) in current USD in dynamics for 1990- 2014, highlights the fact that almost all Central European states registered huge increases in their GDP/capita (Figure 1). The highest increases were recorded by: Poland- 251% (\$9,900 in 1990 till \$24,800 in 2014), Slovak Republic-174% (from \$15,800 in 1990 till \$27,500 in 2014), Czech Republic - 169% (from roughly \$18000 in 1990 till \$30,400 in 2014)¹. The modest GDP/capita growth among the Visegrad group countries was recorded by Hungary-168% (from \$14,500 in 1990 till currently \$24,400).

Figure 1. Level of development of Visegrad countries in comparison with Moldova, GDP/capita (PPP)

Source: Elaborated by the authors according to World Bank, World Development Indicators, 1990-2015. Available at: <http://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.PCAP.CD>

In the same period of time, the Republic of Moldova has not succeeded in overcoming the economic difficulties of the transition period, reporting a decrease of GDP/capita by 22% (from \$6,400 in 1990 till almost \$5000 in 2014)² (Figure 1). This fact underlines generally how inefficient and

¹ All data regarding GDP/capita were taken from WB. World Development Indicators, 1990-2015. Available at: <http://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.PCAP.CD>

²WB. World Development Indicators, 1990-15. Available at: <http://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.PCAP.CD>

ineffective were the economic policies promoted by the governments of the Republic of Moldova since 90's.

The huge disparity in the welfare of the population, which occurs, between the Visegrad countries and Moldova is a direct result of the economic efforts undertaken towards increasing competitiveness of the states. Poland, Czech Republic, Slovak Republic, Hungary have been able to build a more flourishing economic environment in comparison with the Republic of Moldova. Czech Republic and Poland are the leaders in the economic competitiveness, positioned in 2014-2015 according to *The Global Competitiveness Report 2014–2015* on 37st and respectively 43rd place worldwide, Hungary and Slovak Republic registering lesser competitive environments, 60th and 75th positions³, the Republic of Moldova being placed on 82nd place (Table 1).

The comparison of the Visegrad countries' performances, in different years, in the field of competitiveness is not relevant, due to the fact that the number of countries in the World's Economic Forum rankings was increasing during the years (Table 1). Therefore, the rankings for 2000 and 2010 do not allow us to assess the real progress registered by the analysed countries in this period. Nevertheless, the interpretation of the 2015 rankings of Visegrad countries and Republic of Moldova, highlight the relative high performance of Visegrad group and relative low performance of Moldova.

Table 1. Global competitiveness and corruption perception index in Visegrad countries and Republic of Moldova (2000, 2010, 2015)

	Czech Republic	Poland	Hungary	Slovakia	Republic of Moldova
Global Competitiveness Index (rankings)					
2000⁴ (out of 75 economies)	36th	41st	32nd	36th	n/a
2010⁵ (out of 139 economies)	36th	39th	52nd	60th	94th

³ SCHWAB, Klaus. *Global Competitiveness Report 2014-2015*. WEF. Geneve 2015, P.7-14. Available at: http://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_GlobalCompetitivenessReport_2014-15.pdf

⁴ Global Competitiveness Index in 2000 was reflecting the competitiveness performance of 75 countries. Therefore, the rankings are out of 75 economies.

2015-2016 (out of 144 economies)	31st	41st	63rd	67th	84th
Corruption Perception Index (rankings)					
2000⁶ (out of 90 countries)	42	43	32 nd	52nd	74th
2010⁷ (out of 178 countries)	53	41st	50th	59th	105th
2015 (out of 168 countries)	37th	30th	50th	50th	103rd

Source: Elaborated by the authors according to the data of WEF. Global Competitiveness Report 2000, 2010, 2015 and Transparency International. Corruption Perception Index 2000, 2010, 2015.

One of the main factors affecting the economic competitiveness of countries is the corruption. The reduction of corruption is perceived as a favourable impulse for economic development, this fact leading to a more lucrative business climate and an increased motivation towards better economic performance. In the period of 2010 – 2015, in all Visegrad countries were undertaken considerable efforts to tackle the corruption. Therefore, the performance of Visegrad countries regarding Corruption Perception Index, elaborated by Transparency International, has been considerably improving since 2010. Czech Republic increased its ranking by 16 positions in the Corruption Perception Index (from 53rd in 2010 till 37th in 2015)⁸, Poland - 11 positions (from 41st in 2010 till 30th in 2015), Slovak Republic - 9 positions (from 59th in 2010 till 50th in 2015)⁹ (Table 1). Hungary

⁵ Global Competitiveness Index in 2010 was reflecting the competitiveness performance of 139 countries. Data Available at: http://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_GlobalCompetitiveness_Report_2010-11.pdf

⁶ In 2000, in the Corruption Perception Index was calculated only for 90 countries. Therefore the rankings of countries are out of 90.

⁷ The 2010 Corruption Perceptions Index shows the performance of 178 countries. Available at: <http://www.transparency.org/cpi2010/results>

⁸ Even if the number of countries taken into account in the Corruption Perception Index in 2010 and 2015 was different, there is an evident increase in the Visegrad countries' performance to fight corruption.

⁹ Transparency International. *Corruption Perception Index* 2010 and 2015. Available at <http://www.transparency.org/cpi2015#downloads>

is the only country that maintained constant its performance in fighting with corruption, maintaining its position in the analysed period on 50th place. The achievements of Republic of Moldova in fighting the corruption were less considerable, Moldova managing to improve its performance with only 2 position in the Corruption Perception Rankings, i.e. from 105th position in 2010 and 103rd position in 2015. (Table 1)

In conclusion, it could be stated that the Visegrad states succeeded in reducing the corruption level and, therefore, managed to boost their internal business activities and improve the overall economic and competitiveness performance. At the same time, one of the main causes of the relative low economic performance of the Republic of Moldova, is the direct impact of corruption. Since a dynamic business environment could not be developed without transparency, this fact spoiled the country's attractiveness.

Is the Visegrad countries' experience in the social field valuable for former communist states such as Moldova? Definitely yes. The impressive accomplishments of Visegrad states in comparison with the Republic of Moldova in the social area, could be evaluated with the help of the human development index. This indicator allows us to appraise upon different characteristics of society starting with life expectancy at birth, standard of living and the possibility of gaining education and knowledge.

All Visegrad countries since 1990 have been improving their situation in the human development field (Figure 2). The highest performance was registered by Poland, that managed to increase its scores the Human Development Index from 0,71 in 1990 to 0,84 in 2014, followed by Czech Republic (the HDI has grown from 0,76 (1990) to 0,87 (2015)), Hungary (0,7 in 1990 to 0,82 in 2015) and Slovak Republic, where the value of HDI augmented from 0,73 in 1990 to 0,84 in 2015¹⁰. (Figure 2)

¹⁰ UNDP. Human Development Report 2015. Available at: http://hdr.undp.org/sites/default/files/2015_human_development_report.pdf

Figure 2. Human Development Index in Visegrad Countries and Moldova

Source: Elaborated by the authors based on UNDP. Human Development Report 2015. Available at: http://hdr.undp.org/sites/default/files/2015_human_development_report.pdf

This situation indicates how the social well-being of the population in the Visegrad group countries increased, how successful the social transformation was achieved and how effective were the governmental policies implemented in this domain. Regretfully, it should be remarked that the successes of social transformation in the Republic of Moldova are not so bright, the achievements being modest, this fact fully determining the lower extent human development index increase in the Republic of Moldova (from 0,65 in 1990 till 0,69 in 2014). Therefore, we can see that the development of Visegrad countries are truly convincing that these countries have pursued a right path regarding the reform implementation, process successfully accomplished, the fact that the Republic of Moldova can learn much from.

Common Communist Past of the Republic of Moldova and the Visegrad Group

In order to learn from the experience of Visegrad countries in social and economic domains, and to make their experience valuable for the Republic of Moldova in pursuing European integration, the common communist past is necessary to be analysed. Despite some small differences of the communist regimes across Eastern Europe, the basic aspects concerning economic development model and social relations structure were similar in the whole “red” camp. The distinctive characteristics of the socialist economy were: the determinant role of communist bureaucracy, planned economy based on five-year period plans, economic development based on heavy industry, low degree of economic openness to third countries and huge reliance on trade with Soviet Union member countries. While, in the social domain, it is possible to distinguish the following characteristics of the Eastern European communist regimes: the determinant role of communist party, restrictions referring to the human freedom, total control of the state over the people etc.

After the 1989-1990’s events affecting the Eastern European countries, the communist regime had finally fall, leading to a difficult time period full of social, economic and political challenges which were necessary to face. Both, Visegrad group countries as well as the Republic of Moldova entered into transition period. The ambition of building a new economy based on the capitalist market driven model was the most important ambition which the former communist states had to pursue. The challenges faced by those countries were more or less the same, beginning with political instability occurred as a result of social democratization, the soviet troops which had not been yet withdrawn, at the moment, from the territories of the countries, finishing with desire to stabilize the financial economic sector and reform implementation. Moreover, countries faced a troublesome process of building new economic relationships, as the previous COMECON (Council for Mutual Economic Assistance) block has disappeared. This situation brought new economic trends in East European post - communist countries, such as state property privatization, denationalization, economic liberalization and hyperinflation.

Summarising, it could be underlined the multitude of difficulties which the states had to solve in order to realize the complete economic and

social transformation and assure basic requirements for a functioning market driven economy. It is necessarily to point out that the transition period, with all these economic trends associated, is the period when the monumental difference in economic field was made between the Visegrad group countries and, respectively, the Republic of Moldova. Thus, it is important to mention that the experience of Visegrad countries, considering the successful economic transition to market economy, is very important for the Republic of Moldova, especially from the perspectives of its European integration aspirations. Nevertheless, the Republic of Moldova has to examine thoroughly this experience in order to have the possibility to implement faster the commitments agreed with EU partners.

The results of reforms' implementation process in the Visegrad countries

Political democratization is the first step which must be taken into account when speaking about the Visegrad countries success and experience. This process was accompanied by the formation and strengthening of countries' institutions, this being an important progress towards social and economic welfare. Hence, strong and democratic institutions mean a functional mechanism of rational economic resources redistribution within the society. Therefore, we can remark the election of Lech Walesa in 1990 as the President of Poland, followed by the election of the first democratic Polish parliament in 1991, which completed the Poland's transition from communist party rule to western style liberal democratic political system. The same happened in Czechoslovakia when Vaclav Havel was elected as president, the fact followed by democratic parliamentary election¹¹. These events were considered as the stronghold of institutional evolution, thus being an imposing guarantee for the democratic transformation of the countries in the democratic manner. Nowadays, the strong institutional framework within Visegrad countries is considered to be one of the most important factors determining the success of reform implementation allowing Hungary, Poland, Czech Republic, and Slovak Republic to join European Union in 2004. Furthermore, the democratization process starting in 1990's created a favourable environment for economic development within the countries members of Visegrad Group, it being

¹¹ History of the Visegrad Group. Available at: <http://www.visegradgroup.eu/about/history>

accompanied by consistency of political stability. This fact means that each change of the government or leading parties does not reverse the internal political vector towards reform implementation, as well as the external vector of European integration. This means the political maturity of ruling elite in Poland, Czech Republic, Slovak Republic and Hungary, allowing the possibility to strengthen the national efforts made towards realization of nations' aspirations. Conversely, the situation in the Republic of Moldova did not appear so consistent, the political instability during 1990's lead to radical changes regarding reform implementation and external orientation. This fact has led to the economic turmoil where the institutions of the state became instruments of realizing individual interests and not the national desiderates.

The second step regarding the experience of the Visegrad countries accumulated since 1990's are the economic reforms implemented in order to successfully realize the economic transition from communist model to capitalist, market driven one. At this point, it can be noted that the economic reforms differed in strategy but not in substance across Visegrad countries. In some states (as for example in Poland) they were radical followed by short term economic instability, but allowing long term economic growth perspectives, while in other countries (Hungary, Czech Republic, Slovak Republic), these were structural, realized during longer periods of time, conducting to the same outcome, and namely to the stability of economic environment and,, therefore tremendous economic growth achievements. The best example, in this way, is the "Balcerowicz" plan, a comprehensive economic reform implementation guide realized in Poland during the first years of transition period. It was also termed "shock therapy", representing a rapid method of transitioning from communist economy based on state ownership and central planning to capitalist market driven economy. It was proposed in 1989¹² by the Polish minister and economist Leszek Balcerowicz and instantaneously approved by the authorities. The plan was elaborated by a commission of experts including outstanding economists from Poland and from the Western world such as Jeffrey Sachs. This commission prepared a plan of extensive reforms that

¹² Balcerowicz Plan – Summary of the proposed Economic program of Solidarity (online original files). Available at: <http://jeffsachs.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/06/Poland-Reform-Memo-1.pdf>

were intended to transform the Poland's economy from obsolete and ineffective central planning to capitalism as adopted by the United States and Western European countries. The "Balcerowicz" plan was based on various acts regarding the systemic changes in strategic areas of economy, including "Act on Financial Economy within State-owned Companies", "Act on Banking Law", "Act on Economic Activity of Foreign Investors" and so on. Consequently, the reforms limited the state influence upon the economy to the creation of a competitive environment for businesses and stimulating entrepreneurial activity, therefore, accelerating economic growth. Moreover, the plan allowed the free competition of supply and demand releasing price fixing for many products meaning better allocation of resources, necessary for state welfare increase. Furthermore, the internal debt was drastically reduced to 3% of GNP, by cutting down the state subsidies to coal, electricity and petroleum. Initially, the social costs of reforms were enormous, 1,1 million workers from state enterprises lost their jobs. However, in only 5 years, two thirds of the workforce was working in the private sector, which in 1994 accounted for almost 2 million enterprises.¹³. The reforms implementation in Hungary and Czechoslovakia were not so radical, however they were based on the same principle, such as: liquidation of central planned economy institutions, liberalization of economy (including the policies annulling thousands of orders and bans and, therefore, allowing foreigners and citizens to become involved in businesses), privatization of state enterprises, liberalisation of foreign trade etc. At this point it is important to mention the high consciousness of political elites from Visegrad countries who understood that the euphoria which followed the collapse of communism would not provide them with unlimited time for unpopular and economic painful steps. Consequently, the reform implementation process in Poland, Czech Republic, Slovak Republic and Hungary had been operative and strictly oriented to the desire of building capitalism. In such a context, the experience of Visegrad countries in economic reforms implementation would be useful for former Soviet Union countries, especially for the Republic of Moldova that shows a

¹³ JEFREY SACHS, *Shock Therapy in Poland: Perspectives of five Years*, Utah, 1994, p 276. Available at: http://tannerlectures.utah.edu/_documents/a-to-z/s/sachs95.pdf

pressing need to restructure all economic sectors, not just partial ineffective policies applied.

The success of Visegrad countries in the progress of European Union integration agenda is absolutely impressive. Alongside with the massive efforts made by the Visegrad countries in economic field and the transition towards truly functioning economy based on market competition, a wide range of reforms, in various areas such as justice, tax and administration, were implemented. It is important to mention that the Visegrad countries managed to organize the privatization process much more efficiently (especially in the industrial field) than the countries from former Soviet Union, including the Republic of Moldova, creating favourable premises for achieving high competitiveness levels. In this context, the incredible successes of Poland, which in the period 1990-1996 reported an 6,61% increase of GDP¹⁴, is worth to be mentioned. Despite the social economic difficulties faced at the moment, Polish government managed to promote and implement an wise industrial economic policy, based not only the preservation of previously inherited capacities, but focused on their efficient restructuring and adaptation to the new conditions of market economy.

In the same period of time (1990-1996), other Visegrad countries managed to nearly keep the same level of GDP as in 1990, as was the case of Czech Republic (including Slovak Republic till 1993), whereas Hungary in the same period registered 16,11% drop of output as compared to 1990's level (Figure 3).

These results compared to those reported by the former Soviet Union states in the same period of time seem to be very good. For example, the Republic of Moldova registered a drop in the GDP of 53% in the analysed period of time, from 3,59 billion USD in 1990 to almost 1,7 billion USD in 1996.

¹⁴ All data concerning the GDP growth are calculated by the authors on the base of World Bank Data, available at: <http://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.KD.ZG>

Figure 3. GDP growth in Visegrad Countries and Moldova in the period of 1990-2014, (annual %)

Source: Elaborated by the authors according to World Bank Data

The situation in other countries from former Soviet Union was even worse. Ukraine reported in the same years 58,55 % decrease of the production while this indicator in the Russian Federation was of 42%. Therefore, it could be remarked that the industrial economic policy promoted by the Visegrad countries was much more competent meaning that the economic potential of former communist industry was not destroyed completely as it happened in some former Soviet Union states.

Moreover, the economic reforms implemented by the Visegrad group countries laid the foundations for an effective industrial development. This fact is expressed by the increasing level of export competitiveness reported by the Visegrad countries since the beginning of 1990's. Figure 4 shows the Visegrad countries' and Moldova's exports of goods and services as % from GDP in dynamics. All Visegrad countries registered increases in their exports. Slovak Republic managed to increase the exports of goods and services from 25,03 % in 1990 till 91,85 % in 2014. Hungary also reported growth from 28,76% in 1991 till 89,25% in 2014 (Figure 4). Czech Republic, at its turn, registered, too, a favourable evolution of the exports of goods and services as % from GDP, starting with 32,20% in 1990 till 83,81% in 2014. Poland, the same, faced an increase from 26,30 % in 1990 till 47,44% in 2014.

Figure 4. Exports of goods and services in Visegrad Countries and Moldova, (% of GDP)

Source: Elaborated by the authors according to World Bank Data

Whereas, the Republic of Moldova has registered a decline from 48,22% in 1990 till 41,63 in 2014. This fact shows us clearly that the industrial development in the Visegrad countries has constantly evolved while in the Republic of Moldova it has decreased, due to low competitiveness of Moldovan industrial goods.

The experience of Visegrad countries in the diplomacy

The political and economic endeavours of the Visegrad countries implemented to successfully overcome the difficulties of the transition period were accompanied by pragmatic diplomatic efforts regarding the necessity of economic re-orientation towards Western world. Pursuing the goal of building new economic relationships was motivated by the opportunities provided by Western market (as the previous ones established within the COMECON had been disrupted as the communist regime fell in the whole Europe). At this point, it is important to mention that the diplomacy departments of Visegrad countries in the transition period were oriented entirely towards European integration negotiation, this fact meaning the possibility of Visegrad countries to enter in a greater economic space boosting their development. The major point regarding the European integration of Visegrad countries was the adaptation of Association Agreements. These encompassed the general framework of EU integration, underlining the most important reforms, political and economic transformations which had to be implemented. This desideratum was

realized in just few years after the fall of the communist in the east European countries, to be more specific Poland and Hungary signed the association agreements with European Union in 1994, while Czech Republic and Slovak Republic in 1995. It is immensely important to mention that the European Union supported the aspiration of EU integration which the Visegrad countries had, releasing the PHARE program which was intended to assist the applicant countries of Central and Eastern Europe for joining the EU. This was originally created in 1989 to foster the economic transformation in Poland and Hungary, named *Poland and Hungary: Assistance for Restructuring their Economies (PHARE)*¹⁵, afterwards it has been expanded from these two countries to assist Czech and Slovak Republics, nowadays covering several other east European countries. The diplomatic efforts of Visegrad countries regarding the EU accession were impressive continuing with further tough negotiations. These were followed by important events for Poland, Slovak Republic, Czech Republic and Hungary: membership application submitted (1995-1996), European Council grants candidate status to Applicants (1997), Commission recommends starting of negotiations (1997-1999), and membership negotiations start (1998-2000) and so on. Moreover, beside the deepening Visegrad countries - EU cooperation, the states made extremely important steps for broadening the cooperation within them. One of these important steps was the establishment of Central European Free Trade Agreement in 1992, which was intended to foster the economic development and commercial cooperation among the Poland, Czech Republic, Slovak Republic and Hungary (REF). These states were joined by other east European countries, thereafter. This was an important economic platform which allowed the countries to develop progressive commercial relations and therefore to speed up the economic development. The CEFTA agreement represented a necessary point towards the realization of European integration. Therefore, the diplomatic efforts made by the representatives of Visegrad countries accompanied by social, political reform implementation made possible EU accession in such a short period of time.

¹⁵ European Parliament. Briefing No 33: The PHARE Programme and the enlargement of the European Union. Available at: http://www.europarl.europa.eu/enlargement/briefings/33a1_en.htm

Poland, Czech and Slovak Republics, Hungary have succeeded in overcoming the transition period difficulties and integrate into European Union, because their internal policies in economic, political, social, judicial fields were harmonized by international commitments each country obliged to respect. Therefore, the economic development of each state's economy, as well as the increase in the welfare level of population, is a direct result of hard working and serious attitude of each state representative from Visegrad countries, regarding the sense of responsibility for the future generations.

Conclusion

In conclusion it can be mentioned that the experience accumulated by Poland, Czech Republic, Slovak Republic and Hungary regarding the European integration could be extremely valuable for the Republic of Moldova, this experience being the most important evidence regarding the fact that all states need perseverance and dedication in order to accomplish the social economic transformation and to meet the European standards.

We are confident that the European integration is the future of the Republic of Moldova. In order to realize this aspiration, Moldova could learn many things subtracted from the experience of Visegrad group. Nevertheless, 5 things could be highlighted:

1. Patriotism - political elite should think primordially of the national interest of economic development, social welfare improvement and not the personal ones;

2. Pragmatism – Republic of Moldova should concentrate the efforts on those fields of reforms which are the most sensible such as justice, eradicating economic monopolies, these areas being the most vital for assuring economic freedom, improvement of business climate. As long as we have realized these reforms the economy as a whole would develop on much larger extents this fact increasing the well-being of the nation;

3. Discipline - as Republic of Moldova has already signed the Association Agreements with the European Union, we must respect totally the reform agenda agreed in order to receive further European support;

4. Cohesion and unity - if we want to integrate into EU we shall work together gaining positive synergy effect of teamwork;

5. Responsibility, the support allocated by the European Union to fund various development projects in the Republic of Moldova should be spent purposefully and surely not to enter into someone's pockets.

The European integration of Moldova is a matter of time and efforts. In order to foster the European integration process, we need to learn much inclusively from the successful experience of the Visegrad group countries.

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The Role of the European Union in the Framework of International Economic Flows

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Abstract: The economic development through cooperative joint effort of several entities operating in the global economic system is a reality of the contemporary world. The management and concentration of the economic resources increase not only at the micro, but also at the macro level. The successes achieved by the European Union are currently followed by many integration groupings. Although the objectives pursued by them are different, as the integration levels and forms differ, their goal is a common one: to ensure better economic growth and development than would be achieved in particular. Nowadays the EU's role may be a subject of analysis from a multitude of perspectives, in the current study the authors have proposed to analyze the role of European integration grouping in the framework of international economic circuit developed through trade, investment and migration flows, as an important premise for the development of one of the geo-economic powers of the contemporary world.

Keywords: geo-economic power, European economic circuit, EU trade flow, EU investment flow, EU migration flow.

The European Union is a leading geo-economic global power. European economic power is determined by the effort of the Member States that have proposed the creation of a common economic system that could compete with other global geo-economic powers. The European Union states usually are divided in two distinct groups: countries with functioning market economy and transition countries, the delimitation of which is conventional. In this context is used the term "Europe of two speeds" (according to the German political analyst Brandt), having regard to

the EU-15 and EU-13, often being presented statistically in this formula. Although we still cannot speak about a full economic union, the harmonization of economic policies continues, and the Member States' common rules in the international economic circuit allow the evaluation of the EU as a single geo-economic actor.

The European Union was formed and functions on the basis of two principles: intergovernmentalism and supranationalism. The first involves the activity of the component parts work on the governmental cooperation basis while preserving the principles of state sovereignty, the second regards the transfer of some competences from the national to the Community level.

In a relatively short period the European Union has succeeded in establishing itself as a world economic power, competing in this respect with other major global powers: the US, China, Japan (tab. 1).

Table 1. The main economic and social characteristics of the EU as compared to the main global economic powers, 2015

Indicators	European Union	US	China	Japan
1. GDP (PPP), tr. \$	19, 510	17, 970	19, 510	4, 658
2. GDP (% of global GDP)	17,1	16,5	17,1	4,6
3. GDP per capita, \$	37 800	56 300	14 300	38 200
4. Population, mill.	513,9	321,4	1 367,4	126,9
5. Population (% of world population)	7,0	4,4	18,6	1,7
6. Unemployment rate, %	9,5	5,2	4,2	3,3
7. External debt (% of GDP)	86,6	73,6	16,7	227,9
8. Government budget deficit (% of GDP)	-3,0	-2,4	-2,6	-6,5
9. Exports, % of world exports	15,1	10,8	15,6	4,5
10. Imports, % of world imports	14,8	16,0	13,0	5,4
11. Trade balance, bn. \$	271	-456	225	-170

Source: elaborated on the basis of: <https://www.wto.org/>; www.cia.gov/library (accessed on 30.03.2016)

The European Union is one of the greatest economic powers in the world. Although it has only 7% of the world population, the Union has

almost 1/5 of the world's wealth reserves, as measured by GDP. The European Union has a significant role in international economic flows.

The European Union is the largest trading power in the world. It ranks first in both trade in services and trade in goods. Overall, EU-28 has the highest value of international trade even if concerning exports of goods it comes after China, and concerning imports - after USA, overall EU-28 has the highest value of international trade (fig. 1).

Source: adapted on the basis of:

https://www.wto.org/french/res_f/statis_f/its2015_f/its2015_f.pdf,
accessed on 31.12.2015

Figure 1. Share of the major world trade powers in trade in services, 2014, %

The EU market is the most attractive in the world. The high absorption capacity is determined by high incomes of Europeans and high degree of liberalization for trading partners. For nearly three quarters (3/4) of imports, the EU does not levy customs duties or it charges very low ones. The customs duties' level in 2014 was only 2.2% for industrial products and 2.6% for all imported goods. In this way, the high degree of liberalization of the EU market for foreign trade partners is confirmed, with which EU has concluded multiple bilateral and multilateral agreements, intra-Community trade is being liberalized completely. Free trade among Member States was one of the principles behind the creation of the EU and the Union is determined to continue efforts to liberalize world trade. European and international consumers and investors benefit from the significant advantages provided by a simplified system in which people, goods, services and money move freely.

Foreign trade in goods holds the main place in the total foreign trade. The EU has a balanced share in trade in agricultural products of about 10% both in exports and imports, and in trade in manufactured goods (14% in exports and 10.3% in imports), with regards to trade in fuels and mining products they register a large gap between imports and exports of about 5 times, which confirms the high dependence of the EU market on these categories of goods and the energy insecurity of it. (tab. 2).

Table 2. The EU share in international trade by product categories, 2014, %

	Agricultural products		Fuels and mining products		Manufactured products	
	Export	Import	Export	Import	Export	Import
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100
EU 28 (extra EU)	10,1	9,8	6,4	26,4	14,6	10,3

Source: elaborated on the basis of www.wto.org (accessed on 29.12.2015)

The world trade is currently concentrated in several trading powers. Thus, the EU, China, the US and Japan hold 50% of imports and 45% of world exports. The EU external trade in goods and services represents 35% of its GDP that is 5 percentage points (p.p.) more than in the case of US. Due to the size of its market, the EU imports agricultural products from developing

countries as many as Australia, Canada, Japan, New Zealand and the United States taken together. Nevertheless, the most important markets for EU export and import remain: the US, China, the Russian Federation and Japan (tab. 3)

Table 3. The EU's main trading partners

	US			China			Russian Federation			Japan		
	2005	2010	2014	2005	2010	2014	2005	2010	2014	2005	2010	2014
EU, import, %	13,4	11,3	12,2	13,6	18,6	18,4	9,6	10,6	10,8	6,3	4,4	3,4
EU, export, %	23,9	17,9	18,3	4,5	8,4	9,7	5,4	6,4	6,1	4,2	3,3	3,1

Source: calculated on the basis of <http://exporthelp.europa.eu> (accessed on 28.12.2015)

The EU is the largest trading partner for about 60 countries of the world. For purposes of comparison, this figure is 36 for China and 24 for the US. Currently, the main EU trading partners are the US, China, the Russian Federation and Japan. China has emerged as a major trading power on the EU market, holding over 18% of the EU exports, surpassing the US in this respect - the strategic trade partner of the EU. The important position of China on the European market is attributed to the low cost of labor force in this country and the large investments made by European capital. The Russian Federation imposed itself on the EU market by a high share in exports of fuels and mineral resources, given the EU energy dependence. Japan also has decreased its presence on the EU market as a result of the Asian strategy implemented on the emerging markets of countries from Asia. With regard to exports the US market remains the most attractive for the EU Member States. The trend of increased exports directed to China is explained by the emergence of the Chinese market and the general tendency of equilibrating trade balance between these two partners.

In the geographical structure of the EU a significant role comes to intra-EU trade which exceeds 60% of trade in goods and 55% of trade in services (tab. 4).

Table 4. Geographical structure of the EU trade, 2014, %

	<i>Trade in goods</i>		<i>Trade in services</i>	
	<i>Export</i>	<i>Import</i>	<i>Export</i>	<i>Import</i>
Total	100	100	100	100
1. EU 28 (intra EU)	63,3	63,6	54,6	59,7
2. US	6,7	6,5	11,6	12,1
3. China	3,6	6,6	1,9	1,6
4. Switzerland	3,0	2,1	6,4	4,1
5. Russian Federation	2,2	3,9	2,0	-
Total 5	78,8	80,6	76,4	77,5

Source: calculated on the basis of www.wto.org (accessed on 29.12.2015)

The European Union holds an important place in the world trade in services. Trade in services both in value and as share is lower than trade in goods, but it currently has a more pronounced upward trend. Due to liberalized trade and investment regime, the EU companies have an increased access to foreign markets for goods and services. Although the share of services in total trade flows of goods and services do not exceed 1/4 of total trade, this proportion sensitively exceeds the global average of about 19%, which indicates the high degree of specialization of the EU in trade in services compared to the world average.

Source: adapted on the basis of https://www.wto.org/french/res_f/statis_f/its2015_f/its2015_f.pdf, accessed on 31.12.2015

Figure 2. The share of the main global trade powers on trade in services, 2014

Another important flow for economic dynamism of the Member States and the European Union as a whole is the foreign direct investment (FDI). The estimated level of the economic development by the GDP and its evolution directly influences both the supply of capital investment and the attractiveness of potential host countries. Studies in the field have estimated that at a rate of growth of GDP in developed countries leads to an increase of 3.5% in FDI inflows to European Union.

European policy on capital investments develops in line with existing international standards that are most relevant to this domain. The European Union seeks to complete bilateral investment treaties concluded by EU Member States. Most bilateral negotiations on foreign direct investments aim mutual protection of investments and further liberalization of them.

FDI stocks held outside the European Union represent approximately 40% of all stocks and 35% of total FDI stocks inflows, confirming the role of the greatest investment power in the world.

In the last decades strong competition aroused between the global countries in terms of creating the most favorable conditions for attracting foreign direct investments. In this context, the international experience shows that improving the investment climate is the main condition for

attracting foreign investors. Even if the last 5 years FDI inflows and outflows in the EU have decreased, it continues to dominate the global investment market with about 1/5 of total investment inflows and outflows, confirming the role of the most attractive investment market (tab. 5)

Table 5. Direct investment inflows and outflows in/from EU, 2010-2014 (mln. US dollars)

	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
FDI inflows	358 644	444 824	364 767	333 084	257 567
% of total global	27,0	28,4	26,0	22,7	21,0
FDI outflows	459 366	519 862	316 726	285 133	280 124
% of total global	33,6	32,7	24,7	21,8	20,7

Source: elaborated on the basis of http://unctad.org/en/PublicationsLibrary/wir2015_en.pdf accessed on 04.01.2016

The main destinations of foreign direct investments of EU countries in the rest of the world at the beginning of 2014 were: North America (USA, Canada), non-EU Europe, Asia and offshore financial centers. Regarding investments in the EU, the main investors in 2014 were North America (USA, Canada), offshore financial centers, Japan, China (Table 6).

Table 6. FDI inflows and outflows in/from EU, 2014, %

	FDI inflow stock in EU	FDI outflow stock in EU
Total	100	100
1. North America, including:	38,7	31,5
USA	33,9	24,6
Canada	4,8	6,9
2. Europa (non UE), including:	22,7	28,2
Switzerland	6,7	6,3
Norway	3,6	7,6
Russian Federation	2,9	6,3
3. Asia	13,0	22,3
4. Financial offshore centers	18,4	9,0

5. Other regions	7,2	9,0
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Source: calculated and adapted on the basis of: [http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/images/b/b8/Foreign_direct_investment%](http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/images/b/b8/Foreign_direct_investment%252C), (accessed on 05.12.2016)

The most attractive to foreign investors of the EU during this period were Great Britain, France, Germany and Belgium.

United States of America was the main holder of FDI stocks in the EU. At the end of 2014, USA held 33.9% of the total stock of FDI in the European Union. United States invested mainly in the financial services sector, followed by manufacturing sector, of which 1/3 of the investments were directed towards production of computers, electronic and optical products. Switzerland and Norway are two European countries with a large share of FDI at inflows, and outflows. Among other major destinations of EU FDI are Russian Federation, China, Brazil etc.

Table 7. FDI inflows and outflows in/from EU by sectors, 2014, %

Activity sectors	FDI inflow stock in EU	FDI outflow stock in EU
1. Services	87,1	62,5
2. Manufacturing industries	10,7	25,2
3. Extractive industries	0,7	9,1
4. Other sectors	2,2	3,2
Total	100	100

Source: elaborated in accordance with http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/images/8/84/Extra_EU-27_FDI_stocks_by_economic_activity (accessed on 05.12.2016)

The European Union has an important role in international migration flows. The EU Member States were not falling within the category of states receiving migrants until 1950 of the 20th century, but in the postwar period they actively make use of foreign workers to restore the economy shaken by the war. Thereby, the Central and Northern Europe receive immigrants from South of the continent and from former colonies. France headed towards significant flows of migrants from North Africa, towards UK - immigrants from India and Pakistan, while the Netherlands had most of the migrants from Indonesia and Suriname, their former colonies. EU States currently has about 20 mln. migrants, which accounts for approximately 4% of their

population. The highest number of migrants have received Germany (9.8 mln. persons), Great Britain (8 mln. persons), France (7.7 mln. persons), Spain (6.0 mln. persons), Italy (5,7 mln. persons). The largest share of the population arrived to the smaller states in the EU (tab.8).

Table 8. Distribution of the UE 28 population by citizenship, at 01.01.2014

	Share of the native population, %	Share of emigrated population, %
EU 28, total	96	4
1. Luxembourg	54,7	45,3
2. Cyprus	86,5	13,5
3. Lithuania	84,8	15,2
4. Estonia	85,1	14,9
5. Austria	87,5	12,5
6. Ireland	88,2	11,8
7. Belgium	88,7	11,2
8. Spain	89,9	10,1
9. Germany	91,3	8,7
10. Italy	91,9	8,1

Source: Eurostat. Population on 1 January by five-year age group, sex and citizenship [migr_pop1ctz] (accessed on 09.01.2016)

After the collapse of the socialist system a large number of immigrants came in the EU from countries of Central Europe and Southeastern Europe. Several countries in the Southern Europe have turned from countries of emigration into countries of immigration.

EU countries currently lead a restrictive policy on immigrants for several reasons: problems related to uncontrolled growth of illegal migration, the pressure made by the population of the Member States to the authorities across the limitation of migrants, particularly on unskilled labor force, destabilization of labor force markets and recently a wave of illegal migration coming from Near and Middle East, on the background of the economic and financial crisis that EU Member States have not yet overcome. Serious demographic problems experienced by most European countries related to population aging, the natural decline, the emancipation

of women and the family institute will determine EU states to review their migration policy.

CONCLUSIONS:

1. On the basis of formation of United Europe stood more premises of historical, economic and social nature. Ensuring economic and social prosperity of Europe within a tough and qualified competition with other centers of economic power in the world has become possible only through cooperation of economic, strategic (politic), social (demographic, civilizational) efforts. The European Union acts as a single actor in international economic circuit, as a proof of international statistics showing the EU in the international economic flows, as a common entity.
2. The EU has an important role in the international trade flow being one of the biggest trading powers in the world. Full liberalization of intra - Community trade and constantly diminishing the economic barriers in relation to third parties determined the positive trend of foreign trade. Intra-Community trade is two times higher than the extra-Community trade. The EU is the first trading partner for about 60 countries of the world, overrunning USA or other rivals trading powers.
3. The EU dominates the global investment market with about 1/5 of FDI inflows and outflows. The major potential invested by EU is an expression of economic power of this integrationist group and the massive inflows shows stability on the investment market and a high absorption capacity within European community.

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Specificul activității de outsourcing ITO și BPO din Republica Moldova în condițiile internaționalizării business-proceselor

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Abstract: The development of outsourcing activity as a forming tool of competitive advantage under the circumstances of globalization represents a modern trend in the contemporary economy. New and complex management objectives extend the application field of outsourcing which assume the prompt implementations of innovations in practice, thus support competitiveness of economic agents. This study reveals the defining features of ITO and BPO outsourcing activity as a specialized area of the national business-consulting market. Author mentions influencing factors and trends manifested in the sphere of IT outsourcing and externalization of business-processes of the enterprise. Also in the article are outlined opportunities for improvement of international outsourcing activity in Republic of Moldova.

Keywords: outsourcing, ITO, BPO, IT, information technology, business-process, consulting.

Introducere: În condițiile globalizării și internaționalizării proceselor de business, agenții economici tot mai frecvent apelează la furnizori specializați din exteriorul întreprinderii deoarece economia globală postindustrială bazată pe cunoaștere nu tolerează lipsa de calitate și neeficiență. Externalizarea anumitor servicii din cadrul unei organizații către specialiști din diverse domenii are ca obiectiv general eficientizarea ideii de afacere. Un prim beneficiu al procesului de outsourcing este optimizarea costurilor. Din acest atu de bază derivă și alte avantaje, precum ar fi acela că, odată cu reducerea costurilor, rămân mai multe resurse financiare pentru investiții ulterioare sau pentru extinderea afacerii. Odată cu externalizarea serviciilor de contabilitate, recrutare, IT, etc. unei firme specializate, utilizatorul serviciilor de outsourcing va putea să se concentreze exclusiv pe domeniul sau de activitate. Concomitent, conceptul de outsourcing s-a cristalizat și din necesitatea de a încredința executarea unor sarcini specifice profesioniștilor, oamenilor abilitați să le realizeze la cel

mai înalt nivel. Trasând aceste idei, dorim să subliniem faptul ca tot mai multe companii apelează la acest model de business, ceea ce constituie un argument puternic pentru ca outsourcingul să devină o alternativă viabilă de luat în calcul la crearea avantajelor competitive ale firmei.

Material și metodă: Noțiunea de "outsourcing" este de origine anglo-saxonă, mai exact, vine din terminologia americană - "*outside resourcing*", cu sensul de a procura din exterior [1, p. 6]. Termenul a fost preluat în limbajul economic pentru a denumi situația, în care întreprinderea recurge la resurse externe pentru dezvoltarea activității sale. Menționăm că în limba română cu același sens se utilizează termenul de "externalizare". Societate transnațională "Koch Industries" abordează outsourcingul ca o "modalitate de aprovizionare din exterior, ce presupune 'cumpărarea' de componente, bunuri sau servicii prin subcontractare" [2].

Caracteristicile distinctive ale outsourcingului, datorită cărora acest concept nu poate fi considerat drept sinonim al achiziției de bunuri sau servicii, sunt prezentate în tabelul 1.1:

Tabelul 1.1: Caracteristicile distinctive dintre achiziția de bunuri / servicii și outsourcing

Caracteristici distinctive	BUNURI și SERVICII	OUTSOURCING
esența activității furnizorului	furnizorul din propria inițiativă produce mărfurile pentru vânzarea lor pe piață.	furnizorul produce marfa sau servicii doar la comanda beneficiarului.
garanția venitului furnizorului	garanția vânzării mărfurilor și încasării profiturilor lipsește, deoarece este determinată de conjunctura pieței.	beneficiarul garantează răscumpărarea mărfurilor și achitarea acestora în termeni prestabiliți.
tipul de bunuri/servicii	bunul/serviciul se produce în conformitatea cu specificul furnizorului și este standard pentru toți cumpărătorii.	bunul/serviciul este produs conform cerințelor tehnice ale beneficiarului.
mecanismul de formare a prețurilor	vânzătorul stabilește prețul bunurilor/serviciilor de sine stătător, iar în anumite cazuri acordă cumpărătorului	furnizorul acordă beneficiarului informații referitoare la costuri, după care, ei împreună

	reduceri de preț.	stabilesc marja pentru bunurile/serviciile furnizorului.
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Sursa: elaborat de autor în baza [3, p.14]

Particularitățile enumerate mai sus sunt destul de complexe, totuși, există o caracteristică mult mai simplă și ușor de înțeles: dacă beneficiarul este în stare să-și acorde serviciul sau să-și producă bunul de sine stătător, dar totuși acesta apelează din anumite motive la un terț - este vorba despre outsourcing. În cazul, în care beneficiarul din start nu poate să-și satisfacă necesitățile de sine stătător, atunci vorbim despre achiziția de bunuri sau servicii [4, p. 66].

Tipurile și rațiunile outsourcingului: În literatura de specialitate se întâlnesc multiple clasificări ale procesului de outsourcing, fundamentală considerându-se clasificarea după tipul proceselor externalizate (figura 1.1):

IT-Outsourcingul (ITO) presupune transmiterea parțială sau totală unei companii specializate a funcțiilor legate de tehnologiile informaționale,

și anume [5, p. 114]:

- Programarea;
- Crearea și administrarea rețelelor;
- Planificarea, proiectarea și gestiunea sistemelor IT cu modernizarea lor ulterioară;
- Plasarea bazelor de date corporative pe serverele companiilor specializate etc.

Accesul la cunoștințele tehnice este principalul motiv, pentru care companiile apelează la IT outsourcing. Furnizorii serviciilor în domeniul IT

investesc în permanență în tehnologii, metodologii și personal. Departamentele din interiorul companiei-client rar pot corespunde unui asemenea nivel. Mai mult ca atât, este foarte costisitor să ții pasul cu inovațiile tehnologice și să le implementezi la momentul oportun, care au o uzură morală rapidă și care necesită un număr mare de specialiști.

Outsourcingul Business Proceselor (BPO) presupune transmiterea în afară spre executare a proceselor care nu formează esența afacerii, dar o deservesc [5, p. 114]:

- Evidența contabilă și auditul financiar;
- Activitățile de marketing și logistica;
- Gestiunea personalului, etc.

Motivul principal pentru care companiile apelează la outsourcingul business proceselor este faptul că acesta le permite să se focalizeze pe activitatea lor de bază [5, p. 114].

Outsourcingul de Producție sau outsourcingul industrial presupune transmiterea unei părți sau etape din procesul de producție unui sub-contractant. Acest tip de outsourcing se utilizează de companii atunci când costurile de producție sunt mai mari decât cele obținute prin apelarea la outsourcing [6, p. 210]. Motivele pentru care companiile apelează la această formă de outsourcing sunt [5, p.115]:

- Outsourcingul de producție permite concentrarea asupra elaborării noilor produse și servicii;
- Flexibilitatea sporită - este mai simplu de restructurat procesul de producție și de diversificat gama produselor finite;
- Acest tip de outsourcing permite deplasarea afacerii pe piețele cu forță de muncă ieftină.

Externalizarea științifică sau *Knowledge Process Outsourcing (KPO)* este cea mai veche dintre toate tipurile de outsourcing și se referă în special la [7]:

- Cercetări în domeniul farmaceutic;
- Cercetări legate de proprietatea intelectuală;
- Redactarea conținutelor unice;
- Servicii în dezvoltarea bazelor de date, etc.

Actualmente în Republica Moldova piața outsourcingului nu este suficient de solicitată, agenții economici autohtoni încă nu au apreciat pe

deplin utilitatea acestui concept. Dat fiind faptul, că acest model nu este utilizat de către întreprinderile naționale, cererea față de serviciile de outsourcing parvine mai mult din partea companiilor străine și vizează domeniile: tehnologiile informaționale (ITO); outsourcing funcțional (BPO); și outsourcingul serviciilor secundare (curățare, securitate etc.).

Practica națională a outsourcingului exclude, cel mai des, funcțiile considerate strategice pentru întreprindere. Obiectivul principal la transpunerea în practică a strategiei de outsourcing de către firmele locale este înțelegerea conceptului și principiilor externalizării pentru a le putea explica.

Etapa a doua urmează să permită participarea la dezvoltarea conceptului de outsourcing pentru a putea îmbrățișa ansamblul activităților pretutindeni unde 'externalizarea devine o necesitate'. În condițiile de tranziție la economia de piață este necesar ca modelul de outsourcing să fie perceput ca o activitate de investiție. Căci, în cele mai frecvente cazuri, măsurile și acțiunile de susținere a activităților de outsourcing au un caracter declarativ, neavând un program bine definit.

Deși principiile de bază ale outsourcingului azi sunt asimilate de conducătorii întreprinderilor, peste 50% din contracte se soldează cu eșec. În plus, mai mult de jumătate din contracte sunt renegociate timp de 18 luni după semnarea lor, din motivul divergențelor semnificative între furnizor și client. Doi factori se află la originea acestor eșecuri:

1. Ajustarea insuficientă a schimbărilor și inovațiilor pe parcursul contractului;
2. Colaborare neeficientă între partenerii implicați în strategia globală de outsourcing.

Acum 10 ani un contract de outsourcing era definit ca o relație exclusivă între un prestator/furnizor și un client/utilizator, constituită pe termen lung. Cele două părți porneau de la principiul, că singurele ajustări posibile pe parcursul acestei perioade s-ar putea referi la costul, calitatea și volumul serviciilor prestate, inclusiv platforma tehnologică a acestor servicii.

Toată gama serviciilor, de la relații cu publicul (PR) până la servicii administrative pot fi externalizate. Finanțele, contabilitatea, informatica, gestiunea resurselor umane și alte servicii dețin circa 60% din proiectele actuale sau preconizate de outsourcing ale companiilor europene. O treime din ele au menționat outsourcingul serviciilor publice ca centre de apel

destinate clienței. Societățile europene, totuși, sunt devansate în domeniul outsourcingului de concurenții lor din SUA, dar peste 50% din ele consideră, că modelul de outsourcing american nu este aplicabil în Europa. Principalele diferențe invocate sunt reglementarea piețelor europene și diversitatea culturală. Întreprinderile ce recurg la outsourcing sunt convinse, că țările lor profită de pe urma acestui proces, în special de o competitivitate sporită și reducerea costurilor.

Totodată, pentru ca outsourcingul să nu se transforme într-o banală cumpărare de servicii, pentru utilizatorul lor este necesar de a stabili care sunt competențele-cheie actuale și de perspectivă ale companiei, precum și de a determina procesele și motivele transmiterii lor spre externalizare. El devine un avantaj concurențial în momentul, când apare sinergia, adică eficiența setului de procese transmise spre outsourcing începe să depășească eficiența activității lor în propria gestiune.

Strategiile de outsourcing a întreprinderilor din Republica Moldova au început să se formeze în anii '90 prin prestarea serviciilor simple, pentru a se extinde mai apoi la domenii de activitate specializate și de o calificare înaltă. Inițial, outsourcingul viza în special, serviciile de curățare și de securitate. La începutul anilor 2000, experții din domeniul externalizării fac primii pași pentru a se impune în domeniul informaticii și gestiunii bazelor de date.

Analizând piața actuală a outsourcingului autohton, ne vom axa preponderent pe cercetarea externalizării ITO (*Information Technology Outsourcing*), deoarece, în opinia autorului, anume Sectorul Tehnologiilor Informaționale și Comunicațiilor (TIC) are potențialul de a deveni una dintre cele mai dinamice și mai productive sectoare economice din Moldova. Mai mult decât atât, poate deveni un promotor al creșterii eficienței și al inovației în sectoarele economice tradiționale ale Moldovei.

Domeniul TIC este unul de o valoare deosebită iar importanța acestuia pe plan mondial este în permanentă creștere. La nivel național, dezvoltarea sectorului TIC exercită o influență pozitivă asupra productivității muncii în întreaga economie. Creșterea productivității înseamnă creșterea competitivității, profituri mai mari, angajați mai bine plătiți, un management și un control operațional mai bun. La rândul lor, aceste efecte pozitive se vor materializa în standarde de viață mai înalte iar unul dintre cele mai importante efecte este creșterea numărului de locuri de muncă disponibile

și bine plătite. TIC este unul dintre puținele domenii ale economiei, unde Republica Moldova înregistrează progrese semnificative. Fiecare al doilea cetățean este utilizator de Internet, mai mult de jumătate din gospodării au cel puțin un calculator conectat la rețea. După viteza de acces la Internet, Moldova se plasează printre primele 20 de state ale lumii.

După cum este arătat în figura 1.2, efectele social-economice ale sectorului TIC derivă din nivelul de dezvoltare și extinderea sectorului (măsurat prin nivelul de penetrare a telecomunicațiilor mobile, a accesului la

Figura 1.2: Procesul de dezvoltare a sectorului TIC

Sursa: elaborată de autor în baza [14] Figura 1.1: Clasificarea

Internet în banda largă și a computerelor).

Este clar că Guvernul și sistemul educațional au un rol crucial pentru punerea în mișcare a acestui ciclu. Principalele acțiuni așteptate din partea autorităților sunt:

- Tratarea egală a tuturor jucătorilor de piață;
- Reglementarea pieței TIC pentru a permite existența unei concurențe sănătoase;
- Climat fiscal clar, simplu și predictibil;
- Politică educațională care ar răspunde așteptărilor sectorului TIC;
- Protecția efectivă a drepturilor de proprietate intelectuală.

Sistemul educațional are un rol nu mai puțin important decât intervențiile guvernamentale. Pentru ca sectorul TIC să își dezvolte la maxim potențialul, instituțiile de învățământ ar trebui:

- Să ajusteze curriculumul de instruire și cercetare la necesitățile domeniului TIC;
- Să instituționalizeze testarea aptitudinilor studenților înmatriculați la facultăți relaționate domeniului TIC.

În cadrul pavilionului Republicii Moldova la Expoziția universală Expo Milano 2015, s-a menționat faptul că: "ponderea sectorul TIC în PIB-ul Republicii Moldova este de circa 8 %, iar exportul serviciilor IT a constituit anul trecut 65,5 milioane USD, fiind în continuă creștere. În același timp, penetrarea serviciilor internet este de 64 %, iar a telefoniei mobile de 123 %. Serviciile 3G acoperă 99 % din teritoriul Moldovei, în timp ce serviciul 4G deja 41 %. Aceste caracteristici poziționează Republica Moldova în rândul statelor cu o infrastructura de comunicații electronice dezvoltată, favorabilă pentru inițierea afacerilor în domeniul tehnologiei informației și comunicațiilor. De asemenea s-a menționat că proiectul de lege privind crearea parcurilor IT virtuale, vine să consolideze toate taxele și impozitele într-un impozit unic de 7 % din volumul de vânzări pentru rezidenții parcurilor. Astfel, se stabilesc reguli simple, clare și transparente de administrare a taxelor, care nu lasă loc pentru interpretare a legislației și corupție" [8].

Infrastructura de telecomunicații, care este pilonul de bază pentru dezvoltarea TIC, s-a extins activ cu rețele de acces de ultimă generație și conectivitate accesibilă. Rețelele de fibră optică acoperă 90 la sută din localitățile țării, telefonia mobilă - 99% din teritoriul țării. Prețurile se află în scădere și corespund celor din țările europene, Moldova fiind clasată pe locul 5 în lume la capitolul cele mai joase prețuri pentru '*broadband*' fix. În ultimul timp se dezvoltă rapid rețele de ultimă generație, care oferă internet mobil la viteză înaltă. Rata de penetrare a internetului e în creștere, astfel că mai mult de 50 la sută din populația țării este conectată la rețea.

Grație avantajelor competitive ce țin de amplasarea geografică, de apropierea culturală cu Uniunea Europeană și Comunitatea Statelor Independente, de capitalul uman multilingv și creativ, de facilitățile acordate de Guvern pentru industria IT , precum și de extinderea pieței TIC autohtone - în ultimii șase ani industria IT a cunoscut o creștere mai rapidă decât alte sectoare economice.

Este adevărat că Moldova oficial este recunoscută cea mai low-cost locație nearshoring din Europa Centrală și de Est, inclusiv pentru domeniul

IT. Totuși, în pofida unor avantaje competitive evidente, Republica Moldova nu dispune de o imagine ca destinație atractivă pentru serviciile IT. Companiile IT din Moldova au o prezență slabă pe piața regională și pe cea globală, concentrându-se, în special, pe serviciile de outsourcing, prin dezvoltarea și adaptarea produselor unor companii IT internaționale. Conform clasamentului efectuat de către 'A.T. Kearney Global Services Location Index', Republica Moldova nu reprezintă o destinație atractivă pentru externalizarea serviciilor IT. Țările din regiune, precum România, Ucraina și Belarus, sunt deja recunoscute pe arena internațională drept locuri atractive pentru externalizarea serviciilor și desfășurarea afacerilor în domeniul IT. Totodată, piețele de export pentru produsele și serviciile IT moldovenești sunt limitate. Așadar urmează a fi întreprinse eforturi în vederea promovării pe piața regională și cea globală a mărcii "Moldova IT", inclusiv prin dezvoltarea parteneriatelor internaționale.

În viziunea noastră, mediul tehnologiilor informaționale, format în special din întreprinderi mici și mijlocii, cu un număr mediu de angajați între 5 și 9 persoane, deseori cu resurse financiare limitate, ar avea de câștigat dezvoltând și aplicând conceptul de outsourcing. În fond, orice agent economic valorifică diferite funcții (informatica, contabilitatea, logistica) care sunt instrumente de funcționare a întreprinderii, dar care nu fac parte din domeniul ei de specializare. Aceste preocupări consumă resursele umane și financiare ale întreprinderii fără ca să apară o plus-valoare tangibilă, mai mult, ele prezintă mai degrabă inconveniențe decât avantaje și întreprinderea ar câștiga externalizându-le.

Domeniul TIC este unul complex, compus din patru industrii, dintre care industria IT este vârful lanțului valoric, iar celelalte trei: comunicațiile, producerea și vânzarea echipamentelor - reprezintă industrii de suport. În viziunea autorului, valorificarea oportunităților de externalizare din Republica Moldova trebuie axate pe consolidarea competitivității industriei IT, deoarece ea creează o valoare adăugată semnificativă, are una din cele mai mari perspective de creștere, precum și contribuie cel mai mult la transformarea și eficientizarea economiei per ansamblu.

Pentru evaluarea cantitativă a pieței ITO din Republica Moldova, vor fi analizate activitățile de: 1. consiliere din domeniul sistemelor de calcul (K72100) și 2. realizarea de programe și consultanță în domeniul dat (K72220), care în esența lor nu sunt alt ceva decât structuri ale activității de

consiliere, ceea ce în viziunea autorului denotă interconexiunea conceptelor de outsourcing și business-consulting pe segmentul tehnologiilor informaționale.

În baza datelor primare oferite de BNS, pentru anii 2007-2014, autorul a evaluat piața serviciilor IT la valoarea de 173,18 milioane MDL în 2007 și 1046,27 milioane MDL în 2014, ceea ce denotă o expansiune de 6 ori timp de 8 ani (*figura 1.3*). Această creștere se datorează dezvoltării sectorului tehnologiei informației și a serviciilor conexe. Accentuăm aici faptul că potrivit estimărilor experților europeni (www.oDesk.com), exportul IT din Moldova, asigurat de 'freelanceri' și, respectiv, nereflectat în balanța de plăți, constituia în anul 2011 aproximativ 15 milioane USD, deci constatăm că date statistice oficiale au un caracter destul de relativ.

Considerăm foarte ilustrativ și momentul că în anul 2007, înainte de criză, industriile consultanței și serviciilor ITO se aflau pe aceeași treaptă din punct de vedere a volumului piețelor, 173,18 milioane MDL reveneau

Figura 1.3: Evoluția pieței ITO față de piața serviciilor de consultanță din R.M.

sectorului ITO și 176,09 milioane MDL business-consultingului. La finele lui 2014 însă, tehnologiile informaționale au depășit rezultatele sferei de consultanță pentru afaceri de 2 ori, 1046,27 milioane MDL în IT față de 521,52 milioane MDL în activitatea de consulting (*figura 1.3*). Acest salt impresionant încă o dată reliefează potențialul Republicii Moldova în dezvoltarea outsourcingului IT față de alte industrii chiar și atât de prospere

precum este consultingul. În perioada anilor 2012-2014 rata medie ponderată de creștere a domeniului IT a constituit 26,52% anual.

Chiar dacă piețele de export constituie elementul fundamental de motivare a creșterii (principalele destinații de export fiind Marea Britanie, SUA, Franța, Germania și România) piețele locale IT sunt la fel de importante. În această ordine de idei, evidențiem că totalul de cheltuieli pentru IT în anul 2014 a constituit 1305,45 milioane MDL, atestând o creștere cu 589,8 milioane MDL față de anul 2006. Cu toate că achizițiile de componente hardware predomină (67% din totalul pieței), în anul 2013 s-a observat o creștere a procurărilor de software cu circa 30% față de anul 2010 [9].

În opinia specialiștilor, elaborarea programelor software în Moldova este construită integral pe modelul de outsourcing. În acest domeniu pot fi evidențiate câteva forme prioritare: (a) outsourcingul sarcinilor principale; (b) al resurselor și proceselor; (c) serviciilor din domeniul tehnologiilor informaționale. Practic, procesul de producție este dictat de societățile occidentale, care asigură fluxurile financiare, dar forța de muncă se află în Moldova. Majoritatea absolută a companiilor locale din domeniul IT lucrează pentru piața externă. Piața locală este slabă, pe teritoriul național, anumite firme se ocupă de introducerea și deservirea programului 1C, uneori obțin comenzi din partea ministerelor, se ocupă de elaborarea softurilor pentru sectorul financiar-bancar.

Pe lângă companiile din domeniul IT, de elaborarea programelor în Moldova se ocupă specialiștii particulari – *freelance*-ri, despre care am menționat ceva mai sus. Ei elaborează cite-uri, creează biblioteci grafice, algoritmele jocurilor, structurează bazele de date pentru proiecte bine definite. Comenzile sunt găsite prin Internet sau prin relații personale. Remunerarea programatorilor din Moldova este mai ieftină de 2-4 ori decât în occident, ceea ce face externalizarea proceselor IT în țara noastră extrem de avantajoasă din punct de vedere a costurilor.

Azi mai mulți clienți din străinătate înaintează cererea, ca proiectele de elaborare a softului să fie instalate în Vest, iar fragmentele acestor proiecte - în țările Europei de Est. Una din aceste țări este România, unde sunt prezente practic toate corporațiile mondiale - Oracle, Microsoft, Dell, Sun, IBM. Nici unul din lideri IT nominalizați mai sus nu sunt prezenți pe piața Republicii Moldova, mai întâi de toate, din cauza deja menționată -

lipsa unei "imagini IT", în al doilea rând - situația geopolitică care descurajează noi investiții. Totuși, în opinia autorului cauza principală rămâne a fi mediul de afaceri imperfect pentru businessul IT. Conform studiului "*Doing Business 2014*" efectuat de Banca Mondială, în clasamentul '*Ușurința de a face afaceri*', Moldova este plasată pe locul 78 din 189 de țări [10]. Specificul companiilor din industria IT se caracterizează prin investiții capitale fixe minime în afacere, ceea ce permite o flexibilitate înaltă în relocarea afacerii în altă regiune sau țară. Astfel, companiile IT își desfășoară activitatea antreprenorială în țările cu un mediu mai atractiv, precum este România de exemplu. De aceea se impune reducerea poverii administrative pentru companiile IT, prin ajustarea procedurilor administrative, în vederea reducerii timpului și costurilor nemonetare la etapa de intrare în afaceri. Totodată, instrumentele fiscale manifestate prin facilitățile fiscale pentru personalul companiilor IT sunt stabilite pentru o perioadă determinată, până la finele lui 2016. Pentru asigurarea dezvoltării durabile și planificarea afacerilor IT este importantă crearea unui mediu de afaceri și a unui cadru de reglementare previzibil pe termen lung.

Totodată, se observă lipsa unor politici bine definite, orientate spre dezvoltarea industriei IT și a infrastructurii acesteia, precum și insuficiența cooperării dintre industria IT și mediul educațional-științific. Astfel, se impune crearea unui ecosistem favorabil pentru dezvoltarea antreprenorialului și a inovațiilor în domeniul dat prin introducerea unui regim fiscal și economic special pentru companiile IT.

Deși pe piață încă nu sunt prezenți giganți de talia Oracle sau Microsoft, investițiile străine în sectorul IT din Moldova cresc, ceea ce demonstrează avantajele noastre competitive în această industrie. În piața locală au investit cei mai importanți actori regionali: Allied Testing, Endava, Solveit Software și Pentalog, acestea planifică în viitorul apropiat să atragă sute de profesioniști din Republica Moldova în domeniul IT, motivele principale fiind capitalul uman și faptul că cultura țării noastre este compatibilă atât cu lumea occidentală cât și cu cea vorbitoare de limbă rusă [11],[3].

Capitalul uman este cel mai important activ al industriei IT. În prezent, în Moldova se constată o insuficiență de specialiști calificați în sfera IT, chiar dacă numărul absolvenților în acest domeniu este de circa 2000 pe an. Aparent, volumul de absolvenți este suficient pentru a asigura cererea

creată pe piața tehnologiei informației, în realitate însă, metodele de instruire și curriculum sunt depășite. Doar un număr mic de absolvenți pot fi implicați în proiecte cu valoare adăugată înaltă, majoritatea având nevoie de o instruire preliminară pentru a fi angajați [12].

Outsourcingul funcțional sau BPO (Business Process Outsourcing). Ca și în cazul serviciilor din domeniul IT, firmele prestatoare de outsourcing funcțional lucrează, în mare parte, pentru întreprinderile străine. De exemplu, printre clienții PwC Moldova (PricewaterhouseCoopers) 75% sunt străini, și numai 25% constituie întreprinderile locale. La fel operatorii BPO prezenți pe piața locală, lucrează în regim offshore, fiind firme-filiale ale liderilor mondiali: EY, Deloitte & Touche, Roedl & Partner etc. Aceste companii oferă o varietate de servicii pentru procesele care nu constituie o activitate de bază a întreprinderii-client, dar care are o influență majoră asupra prețurilor acestora - serviciile contabile, auditul financiar, serviciile juridice, marketing, logistica, gestiunea personalului etc. Cu atât mai mult că întreprinderile locale de outsourcing funcțional au o specializare mai îngustă, există firme ce oferă servicii juridice (L&B Consulting Group, BSMB, Legal Counsellors, Sovilex Consultiv, Legitimus), de contabilitate (Audit-Concret, Audit-Exact, Businss Audit Group) etc.

Outsourcingul nu este o soluție de minune pentru rezolvarea tuturor problemelor de eficientizare a întreprinderii și nici nu există o formulă unică pentru abordarea acestuia. Estimările trebuie făcute în fiecare caz aparte, ținând cont de caracteristicile fiecărei întreprinderi și flexibilitatea structurii sale. Pentru ca outsourcingul să aducă realmente beneficiile așteptate, este important ca partenerii să partajeze o cultură de afaceri orientată spre schimbare. În fond, problemele legate de outsourcing nu se limitează doar la alegerea intrinsecă a externalizării, dar vizează la fel analiza proceselor, selectarea partenerului, redactarea contractului și aprecierea rezultatelor. Mai mult, observăm, că intenția managerială de a reorganiza întreprinderea nu este singura provocare. Existența unui mediu concurențial dezvoltat este un stimulent real care poate influența introducerea și utilizarea modelului de outsourcing la nivel național [5, p. 114].

Ca urmare, trebuie evaluate riscurile care ar putea apărea, adică costurile excesive și dificil cuantificabile, pierderea controlului tehnologic asupra activităților externalizate, antrenând o dependență de furnizor, o ireversibilitate în alegerea strategiei sau obstacole sociale legate de

managementul schimbării. Cum a fost menționat, outsourcingul nu poate fi improvizat. El trebuie conceput într-o viziune strategică, concomitent largă și ofensivă. Trebuie depășită viziunea pe termen scurt a outsourcingului, întreprinderea trebuie să-și afirme proiectul pentru a ameliora lanțul de valori. În plus, trebuie regândită strategia de diferențiere, integrând avantajele externalizării și formând alianțe pentru a permite întreprinderii să-și mărească considerabil capacitățile.

Outsourcingul trebuie gestionat în mod specific. Miza economică și organizațională sunt suprapuse, și nu pot fi tratate separat. În fond, cu sau fără transfer de personal, externalizarea antrenează schimbări profunde. Acesta este printre altele, motivul pentru care se aplică, în scopul de a provoca o ameliorare. Nu trebuie să fie nici o mirare față de reacția de frică sau rezistență. O soluție este negocierea, anticiparea, respectul salariaților care au și ei de câștigat.

Evoluția este ireversibilă spre o economie a cunoștințelor pe bază de alianțe, interdependență și responsabilitate reciprocă. Azi putem vorbi despre o mișcare evolutivă spre imaterial și conexiunea care generează noi factori de competitivitate, legați, în special, de capacitățile cognitive ale infrastructurii; asocierea web-ului și tehnologiilor clasice face să explodeze frontierele întreprinderilor, apar noi servicii de tip logistică electronică etc. Aceste noi aspecte funcționale, rețele de interdependență și mobilități redefinesc formele contractului comercial. Se avansează spre angajamente de rezultat și nu doar de mijloace. Toate acestea pun probleme de încredere și confidențialitate, de partajare a riscurilor și raportului de forțe, uneori de proprietate intelectuală și evidențiază, în general, problema refacerii angajamentelor sociale.

Întreprinderile mai frecvent fac apel la prestatori externi, reieșind din necesitățile lor de producție sau încredințându-le sarcinile considerate conexe (secundare), deoarece economia globală postindustrială nu tolerează lipsa de calitate și neeficiența. Anume din acest motiv mai multe funcții sau activități ale întreprinderii necesită outsourcing. Majoritatea întreprinderilor ce recurg la prestatori externi o fac pentru a transforma costurile fixe în variabile și să obțină mai multă flexibilitate cu o mai bună calitate a serviciilor și o eficiență mai înaltă. Conform studiului Outsourcing Andersen, 30% din întreprinderi recurg la externalizare pentru cel puțin trei funcții. Obiectivul urmărit de întreprinderii nu se rezumă doar la 'o mai bună

gestiune a afacerii', dar și la 'accelerarea ciclului de producere'. În ultimele două decenii s-a constatat că recursul la outsourcing a sporit în special în cazul STN [14, p.136].

Totodată într-o economie influențată de adaptabilitatea afacerilor, dezvoltarea informatică și sofisticarea crescândă a produselor, întreprinderile mici și mijlocii sunt și ele tentate de a reduce costurile fixe și de a se concentra asupra activității de bază. La fel, și ele recurg tot mai des la externalizarea mai multor din activitățile industriale sau terțiare.

Mai mult, externalizarea permite utilizarea beneficiilor acordate de țara gazdă. Pentru a pătrunde efectele outsourcingului trebuie să fim la curent cu cadrul internațional al ISD și comerțul internațional. Avantajele ISD ce însoțesc outsourcingul în țara-gazdă depind de:

- Efectele asupra ocupației forței de muncă (în cazul dacă există șomaj);
- Creșterea capitalului (în țările în care există penurie de capital);
- Propagarea tehnologiei ce permite externalizarea în țara gazdă;
- Amploarea legăturilor cu economia locală.

Prezența sucursalelor străine stabilite în procesul de outsourcing se face în platforme de export, unde este exportată producția. În asemenea circumstanțe există o deplasare neesențială a întreprinderilor locale și puține efecte asupra economiei locale. Nu trebuie minimizezate dificultățile de măsurare a incidențelor locale, căci ele au mai multe forme, cum ar fi transferul de tehnologii, investiții în infrastructură de care pot profita firmele din țara gazdă, efectele de demonstrare pentru a-i inspira pe întreprinzătorii locali.

Experiența mondială din trecut ne arată, că schimbarea tehnologică a provocat majorarea productivității și veniturii. Outsourcingul este însoțit de adaptarea industrială și de schimbări în structura ocupației, a căror amploare în țara de origine depinde de nivelul inovației și viteza cu care întreprinderile se vor adapta, la fel, de flexibilitatea pieței muncii și formării forței de muncă. Mutațiile provocate de procesul de outsourcing vor fi percepute în câțiva ani ca și cele ce au însoțit comerțul electronic.

O importanță crescândă a serviciilor se datorează în particular, fenomenului de outsourcing, care a provocat o creștere a cererii la servicii, căci numeroase întreprinderi fac apel la prestatori pentru efectuarea unor activități conexe sau unor activități de bază, în scopul sporirii flexibilității.

Concluzii și recomandări: Piața actuală a outsourcingului național nu este suficient de bine structurată. Modelul de outsourcing nu este larg utilizat de întreprinderile naționale, cererea la servicii parvine preponderent din partea companiilor străine. Conducătorii întreprinderilor din Moldova percep outsourcingul ca un instrument de realizare a economiilor, decât un mecanism de creștere a competitivității datorită aplicării unor noi resurse intelectuale și tehnologii avansate. Instabilitatea mediului național de afaceri, de asemenea nu contribuie la dezvoltarea outsourcingului. Întreprinderile autohtone sunt orientate spre relații contractuale pe termen scurt, pe când outsourcingul presupune încheierea contractelor pe termen lung. În consecință, spre externalizare se transmit procese standard, ce nu necesită formarea și/sau aplicarea noilor cunoștințe, ca rezultat, impactul asupra competitivității firmei este nesemnificativ

În condițiile actuale din Republica Moldova este necesar, ca modelul de outsourcing să fie perceput ca o activitate de alocare a investițiilor, implementând următoarele măsuri:

- De a defini un program complex de promovare și stimulare a conceptului de outsourcing ca business-model;
- De a elabora și de a gestiona strategiile naționale de utilizare a acestui model de afaceri, prin intermediul reorganizării cadrului legislative existent, ce ar avea efecte benefice pentru dezvoltarea economiei naționale;
- De a contribui la crearea asociației naționale de outsourcing, ce ar reuni agenții economic ce aplică soluții de outsourcing, precum și agenții economici, ce furnizează astfel de servicii;
- De a coordona activitatea firmelor membre ale asociației, organizând tranzacții de outsourcing și relații de afaceri comune;
- De a acorda suport și consultanță profesională privind diferite probleme în legătură cu utilizarea inadecvată a strategiei de outsourcing;
- De a organiza reuniuni de afaceri pentru a stimula schimbul de experiență reciprocă, inclusiv în formarea și recrutarea persoanelor calificate în domeniul respectiv;
- De a stabili relații de colaborare cu asociația europeană de outsourcing și asociațiile naționale din România, Ucraina etc. ce dețin experiență în domeniul respectiv.

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ISTORIE POLITICĂ / POLITICAL HISTORY

Good Practices of Government Coalition. The Experience of European States

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Abstract: In the article the authors highlight complex political processes on which we meditate daily, because now politics permeates all areas of social life. Successes and failures of the government influence on living and working conditions. In search of a better life and wanting to be more demanded by social groups and the community, we adopt a proactive, critical, constructive approach to all parts of the political system, asking them to honor their promises and obligations. To this end, the authors have proposed to update the good practices of government coalition, made by European states.

Keywords: coalition government, Europe, political process, political system, politics.

In the contemporary world the sphere of influence in politics is growing continuously. Nowadays, politics no longer complies with the definition of Plato *the activity area of the chosen people*, but it concerns all of us. In the 21st century, people, professionals in certain socially-useful fields cannot accept sentences like: I only know my field -medicine and public health, training and education, construction, automotive industry, journalism etc., because all social reality phenomena and processes are interdependent. Being involved in education, learning and professional training in the field of international relations, we often face with the inability to solve problems observed at the institutional level, because the elements of a system interact and produce new situations. To understand what is happening in Moldova's political system is important to assimilate the experience of developed European countries, which have managed to

strengthen the functionality of democratic political institutions, under the terms of multi-party system and pluralism. Governance is a process that considers the ability of political forces to seize and maintain power for a period provided by the Constitution.

The coalition government is a sensitive phenomenon to the political reality in Moldova. Capitalization / resizing of the experience gained by the democratic states, the European Union Member States, governed by coalitions, will enable Moldovan citizens to understand that we live in different times, and that the following proverb can no longer be a consolation: *every nation gets the government it deserves*. To provide society with arguments in favor of the thesis that the coalition government can serve the national interest, can manage effectively the social, economic and political processes, can serve the people, meeting its expectations, reacting to inputs of political system, can be honest and upright, the authors conducted this study. The authors also seek to justify the second thesis, according to which the dynamics of the transition in Moldova has posed new challenges for both the government and the entire society, and the political components were not able to respond timely and adequately to them.

Great philosophers of antiquity seek to define the general principles of good governance. In the dialogue *The statesman*, Plato exposes more policy definitions. The philosopher states that although it is a royal art, politics is a science concerned with deciphering theoretical models / methods to rule the men. The philosopher stresses that people may be led by persuasion and coercion / violence. Some statements of philosopher deserve to be updated and learned. For example: politics is the art and science of caring people through laws, freely or under duress. Plato places politics above that case law, eloquence, divine worship. The philosopher argued: *as human virtue is the reason, as the driver is under perfect knowledge, wisdom that controls every action of the state, because the art of politics is a synthetic science*¹.

In the work *Policy* Aristotle mentions that *politics is a practical science* because it seeks not only knowledge but also action, offering its rules. In the classification of forms of government, Aristotle accepts the

¹ Платон, Сочинения. Т.3, М., 1994

opinion of Plato about good and bad forms of government, defining and governing principles that can be involved in as many citizens. The political theory of Aristotle, *politeia* plays a special role, because this form of government is the potential of the middle class and social position. Aristotle was convinced that the government can ensure social stability, can provide a decent life for all citizens, provided that they will control the ratio between wealth and poverty and the middle class will support activities. Guarantor of social stability is consolidated middle class and co-opted at the government².

In contemporary political science good governance is designated by the term *legitimacy*, conceptualized by Max Weber. *Political dominance*, according to Max Weber, is a combination of two elements: on the one hand, a legitimacy that gives stability, and on the other hand, an authority that gives it shape. Thus introduced into scientific circulation notion of legitimacy of political power by Max Weber, requires the establishment and functioning legally through support from the population. Legitimacy of power is fundamental in maintaining political order and social cohesion. Without it, leaders can rely on coercion to maintain power, coercion but will not ensure long-term system stability. Political legitimacy is strength acceptable, meaning those which are required its subordinate commands³. Legitimacy is a term designating a set of beliefs and mental representations that exploit the qualities that governments must possess to be accepted. Thus, adherence to democratic values is based on the legitimacy of the authorities and the decisions taken by them.

Specialists in the field are asking: What is the way we can establish the legitimacy of the exercise of power by a group of people? Which is the way of justification that a social institution is right? In political practice is recognized the mechanism of justification or foundation of the legitimacy of a social institution called contractualism⁴. The political philosophy analyzes the contractualist mechanisms to justify social and political institutions. The skilled construed the majority rule that allows a group of people to lead.

² Voiculescu Marin, *Tratat de politologie*. – București: Editura Universitară, 2002, - 445 p.

³ Chagnollaud D. *Dicționar al vieții politice și sociale*. București: Editura All, 1999, p.27.

⁴ Roșca Ludmila, *Filosofia. Ghidul afacerii de succes*. – Chișinău: S.n. 2013 (Tipogr."Print-Caro", p. 301.

Political experience of European countries reflects the establishment of coalition governments that support reforms, while respecting the principle of continuity. Coalition governments are the expression of social complexity, diversity of individual interests and group options. Without knowledge of concepts: consensus, cooperation, collegiality, tolerance, interest etc. members of coalition governments cannot honor its promises arising from electoral programs. The finality of the political activity of coalition governments depend on the capacity of all political actors to assume personal responsibility and collective act of governance. To justify the matters set out, we explore the experience of Italy, Germany, Norway, states that in different periods of their contemporary history have been governed by coalitions, managed to solve the acute problems of all areas of social life. We can infer lessons from each experience. For example, the coalition of Social Democrats Italians ruled the country for 50 years and produced "economic miracle" and the constitutional monarchy in Norway provides a model of functioning democratic political institutions concerned with creating knowledge-based society. Germany's experience is valuable in terms of the territorial and unify the country, and to solve the economic problems of East Germany.

Italy is a unitary state, a parliamentary republic led by multiple government coalition. During 1948-1994, the Italian political system is driven by post-election coalitions, which have focused their efforts on initiating recovery / reconstruction of the national economy. In terms of post-election political governments were concerned with removing the totalitarian state structures and strengthening democratic institutions. In the period 1958-1963, Italy had remarkable results, expressed by the formula "Italian economic miracle". The success of governance is explained by analysts in collaboration with other Christian Democrats police forces, supporting them by the people, mitigating the impact of traditional protectionism, replaced by professionalism trained specialists in all branches of the Italian economy. Respecting the rules and norms of political dialogue, consensus and coalitions have formed a stable government, democratic, political and economic renaissance centered on Italy.

In the period 1980-1992, political forces in Italy Partito Ponta formed coalition, supported by the Christian Democrats (DC), the Socialists (PSI), Social Democrats (PSDI), Republicans (PRL), and Liberals (PLI). This coalition

formed seven governments, because corruption has covered many areas of life, including it became the main feature of the political system. The government coalition from 1989 faces many critical situations in Italian society multiplies forms of absenteeism, people demanded change in the political class and reforming state institutions. Civil society leaders have used the referendum with maximum efficiency; so on June 9, 1992, 30 million people went to vote. As a result of population mobilization prosecutor in Milan has processed files by posting information called Tangentopoli, confirming the relationship between all political actors and structures of Coza Nostra mafia. Christian Democrat party was destroyed⁵,

In 1994, Italy introduced the majoritarian electoral system, which determines the political parties to form pre-election coalitions. In 1994, the election faces three coalition led by Silvio Berlusconi, Achille Occhetto and Mariotto Segni. They will fight for power until 2008, occupying different regions of Italy: Il Popolo della Liberta - party center-right, led by Silvio Berlusconi enjoys influence in Northern Italy; Partido Il Democratico - center left, Matteo Renzi, southern Italy. In recent years the political situation in Italy is characterized by instability⁶. Political analysts highlight several factors of instability, among which: *partitocracy* (the excess of party's daily influence). In Italy political power is distributed between the parliament and the political parties represented in the government. *Partitocracy (authoritarianism of a party)* is usually associated with clientelism, cronyism, and illegal actions.

Germany is a parliamentary republic in which the head of government is elected by parliament and confirmed by the President. Driving constitutional organs of the state are: the Federal President, appointed for a period of 5 years from the Federal Assembly; Federal Parliament - Bundestag (current legislature composed of 603 deputies), elected by the people for a period of 4 years. An important feature of the German political system is political stability, enthroned during the government of Helmut Kohl in 1982. Helmut Kohl managed the largest political performance of the twentieth century, the reunification of Germany in 1990. And difficulties in the conditions of the complicated unification of

⁵ <http://www.ecol.ro/content/miracolul-economic-italian-0>, vizualizat la 01.03.2016).

⁶ <http://www.europalibera.org/content/article/24913486.html>, vizualizat la 01.03.2016).

West Germany, which took huge financial resources, the economic reconstruction of East Germany, and managerial skill has allowed the Chancellor to maintain system stability.

Any political government is facing financial problems. So in 1999, the CDU violated the regulations of the German parties, did not declare any received donations and the consequence is known as "black money scam." Kohl refused to make public the names of donors and journalists suspected that there is no donor and the money came from bribery. As a result, Gerhard Schröder defeats Helmut Kohl and forms a coalition between the SPD and Alliance '90 / The Greens. Gerhard Schröder result in public scandal defeats Kohl and form a coalition between the SPD and Alliance 90 / The Greens. On 21 July 2005, Federal President Horst Köhler dissolved the Bundestag, as a result of the vote of no-confidence that received Chancellor Schröder. On 18 September 2005, early federal elections were held, a result of which came to power the vast coalition between the parliamentary groups CDU / CSU (so-called "Christian Union") and SPD, with Angela Merkel (CDU) as a chancellor. It is curious that formally the FDP achieved the best result from the last 15 years, but not the majority for Budenstag, even in coalition with the CDU and CSU. A coalition with the Green Party and SPD was not approved by the party leadership. Finally, the vast coalition of the CDU + CSU and SPD was formed and the leadership was taken over by Angela Merkel, but the FDP remaining opposition. The "Grand coalition" that has governed Germany for four years, managed to achieve some of its projects, other cases have failed due to differences between conservatives and social-democrats. Nevertheless, the coalition's achievements are remarkable: a million jobs; as they were engaged in the fall of 2005, an increase in the VAT rate by three percentage points, from 16 to 19 percent. To stop the growth of public deficits, the government released 500 billion euro to support ailing banks, over 80 billion euro for the "real" economic recovery. In a country like Germany marked by a very low rate of birth, where women encounter difficulties in harmonizing motherhood and professional life, the "vast coalition" has set a parental salary granted for a

maximum of 14 months and invested heavily in the construction of nurseries⁷.

In 2009 CDU and CSU form a single parliamentary faction in the Bundestag called "Christian Union". As a result of these elections there appeared a new coalition government consisting of CDU / CSU and FDP, led by Chancellor Angela Merkel (CDU). In September 2013, after the general elections, leaders of the biggest parties - the Christian-Democratic Union / Christian Social Party and Social Democratic Party have reached a provisional agreement to form a grand coalition government, and negotiations lasted several weeks. The negotiation script may enter into Chrestomathy. Last session lasted 17 hours and ended with the signing of an agreement in which Conservatives and Social Democrats were to finalize the negotiations by November 27. The last day of negotiations gathered 75 participants who discussed the outstanding issues and differences of opinion between the two sides. Eventually a compromise was reached, but one theme remains unsolved related to the funding arrangements of the various Government commitments. But this issue was also resolved by party leaders in private discussions. Finally, the draft agreement was signed by all delegates present at the negotiations. An important clause stipulated – the coalition government consists of parties which together cover over 60% of German voters. Other controversial issues on which the parties agreed during marathon negotiations are laws on dual citizenship, minimum wage, pension reform (who proposed it since 2005, scheduled for 2012-2029) and the introduction of a tax on the use of German Autobahn for foreign visitors (if such a law will conform to EU law)⁸.

The Government program was presented on 27 November 2013, without establishing the names of future ministers. In the Merkel's new cabinet - Socialists hold six portfolios, five Christian Democrats hold five and the Bavarian Christian Social - three. Re-election of Angela Merkel as a federal chancellor of Germany occurred on December 17, 2013⁹. The coalition government can be effective and rational only in terms of high political culture and the exclusion of political selfishness manifested by the

⁷ http://www.apd.ro/files/publicatii/25plus2_Model_electorale_I_Sisteme_electorale.pdf (vizualizat la 01.03.2016).

⁸ *Enciclopedia Universală Britanică*, Editura Literca, Vol. VI. – București, 2010, 360 p.

⁹ Guceac Ion, *Constituțiile statelor lumii*, Editura Cartier. – Chișinău, 2016, 908 p.

leaders of parliamentary parties. The coalition government demonstrates once again that in politics should take priority the national interest and not the interest of the party.

Norway is a constitutional monarchy with a parliamentary system of government. The Parliament (Storting) is unicameral and consists of 169 representatives. Parliamentary elections are held every four years. Under the Constitution, it is not possible to organize early elections. In adopting or amending laws, the Storting operates on a "bicameral" system and a quarter of its members (41 MPs) meet in the Upper House (LAGTING) and the other in the Lower House (ODELSTING). The Government is formed by a right-wing coalition (Conservative Party, Progressive Party) and is led by Ms. Erna Solberg (Conservative Party). As Head of State, the King is the unifying symbol of all state authority. He opens every new session of parliament; presides over the meetings of the State Council and approves all decisions taken under it; it represents Norway in the meetings and official visits of other heads of state. Until the introduction of parliamentarism in 1884, the Government remains in office as long as the King wanted. But from 1884, the Government formation requires the vote of confidence from the Parliament. The government consists of the party / parties that constitute the majority in the Storting or the minority able to govern. Therefore, the Government is elected indirectly, meaning that general elections can lead to changing the Government, but not necessarily. However elections do not ensure the change of government, only if it loses the confidence of the Parliament. Sometimes the Government has the support of the majority of deputies in the Storting, in this case we call it the Majority Government. If it is the Minority Government, in any case it should win the confidence of the parliamentary majority providing proof of its effectiveness to ensure the promotion of projects by the Storting in the future. Also there is the possibility of forming a coalition government. Norway is one of the oldest democracies in the world. It has a multi-party political system. The common factor linking Norwegian parties to the democratic principle, according to which political bodies govern based on norms established by law. Central authorities (Parliament) or local (regions and municipalities) are formed on the basis of free, direct and secret elections. The coalition government proposed a plan of recovering and improving the economic level of Norway. Therefore, the Conservative Party and the Progressive Party received

approval from the parties supporting them to use almost 3% of the national fund to cover budget deficit in 2014. The amount is higher than that proposed by the previous government, which lost elections in September. In 2015 the Norwegian Ministry of Finance has initiated on the proposal of the International Forum of Sovereign Wealth Funds the accession of the Global Pension Fund to the Santiago Principles:

- Maintaining a stable financial system and a free investment and capital flow;
- To comply with all the regulations required from the countries that receive investment from SWFs;
- Making investments based on financial and economic considerations arising from the assumption of risk and return;
- A structured and transparent governance that provides for effective control over its operations and assume the risks and responsibilities.

The Norwegian government promotes further cooperation between research communities and the private and public sectors at both national and international level. In the 2014-2019 period, there were partially and will still be allocated 150 million to business projects through the "Innovation Norway". The cooperation between universities, colleges and the business sector is supported and leads to the establishment of a number of enterprises that base their work on the latest achievements of scientific knowledge.

Conclusion

The coalition government is an actual subject and should be included on the agenda of scientists, analysts, commentators, journalists, opinion makers in Moldova. The assumption of governance by the participants in the coalition imposes several behavioral restrictions to the leaders, members of parliamentary factions. Germany's experience is also valuable through the way of negotiating the Agreement, signed by participants in the coalition government. The ability to negotiate, to yield, to reach consensus is a characteristic of the human state: virtuous, honest, gifted with strategic thinking, patriotic, wise. The higher education system in Moldova must be focused on the education / training of politicians for whom virtue, the common cause, honesty and fairness, responsibility and the sense of debt - are professional values.

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The Innovative Eastern Partnership Multilateral Dimension: an Additional Instrument for EU Normative Promotion in Moldova

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Abstract: The Eastern Partnership was established not only to fill main gaps but also boost strengths of initial ENP with Eastern neighbours, in accordance with European standards. Among measures, a new multilateral track was included as a complement for traditional bilateral relations. The latter is characterized by offering a new interactive scenario between EU and Eastern partners. Step by step, it becomes a useful tool for normative promotion that has reached certain results. Even in the case of front-runners (like Moldova) that usually paid a greater attention to bilateral link.

Keywords: Eastern Partnership, multilateral dimension (Thematic Platform I, Euronest Assembly, Civil Society Forum), European core values, normative impact and Moldova.

I. Introduction

The Eastern Partnership was constituted to reinforce and go beyond the previous framework and, therefore, offer Eastern neighbours the maximum possible based on mutual commitment to rule of law, good governance, respect for human rights and so on¹. The most innovative measure was to set up a new multilateral track, which could address one of European Neighbourhood Policy (ENP)'s weakness. Since, its establishment in 2004, it was noted that non- promotion of horizontal links constituted a significant shortcoming due to it prevented from certain cooperation among, at least, states located in the same region. The latter issue was even more visible in the Eastern area². To this must be added that Eastern regional organizations didn't show significant advances like, for example,

¹ Commission of the European Communities, *Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council "The Eastern Partnership"*, Brussels, 3.12.2008, (COM [2008] 823 final).

² LAURE DELCOUR, *Shaping the Post- Soviet Space? UE Policies and Approaches to Region-Building* (Surrey: Ashgate Publishing Limited, 2011).

GUAM³ or Independent State Community in which countries like Georgia is no longer involved. Therefore, it was necessary to insist on a first encouragement of a multilateral dialogue and collaboration.

The European response was to establish a new multilateral dimension at the core of the Eastern Partnership⁴. The latter was born as a complement of bilateral track where, traditionally, relations with neighbours were conducted and, in the case of frontrunners, it constituted a priority area. Thus, EU provided Eastern neighbouring states with an additional instrument (based on share information, collaboration and interaction) through which common challenges could be addressed⁵. And, finally, it could encourage a more ambitious normative approach implicit in the regional initiative⁶.

The new track is characterized by embracing not only institutional meetings, but also specific projects that accompany process of reforms at bilateral level⁷. Among them, the most significant and dynamic initiatives (that are interconnected) are the following three: Thematic Platforms, the Euronest Assembly and the Civil Society Forum on which we will concentrate to know how EU normative impact has been on the Republic of Moldova⁸, considered one of the ENP front-runners⁹. The relevance of them remains in the fact that they promote European norms at an executive, parliamentary, and civil society level, respectively. Therefore, they cover not only traditional

³ GUAM doesn't present important results. But, there are some advances at energy sector. See: TARAS KUZIO, "GUAM as a Regional and Security Organisation", at *National Security and Foreign Policy of Azerbaijan Conference*, St Michael's College, University of Toronto (28, March, 2008).

⁴ Rosa Balfour, "Debating the Eastern Partnership: Perspectives from the European Union", *IPG*, 3, (2011): 29.

⁵ Commission of the European Communities, *Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council "The Eastern Partnership"*.

⁶ At the hearth of the Eastern Partnership, it is found promotion of values such as democracy, the rule of law or respect for human rights. See: Council of Europe, *Brussels European Council 19- 20 March 2009 Presidency Conclusions "Annex 2"*, point: 2.

⁷ Presently, multilateral projects are the following: thematic platforms, Euronest Assembly, Civil Society Forum, The Conference of Region and Local Authorities of the Eastern Partnership, and Eastern Partnership Business Forum.

⁸ Hereafter referred to as Moldova.

⁹ In spite of political instability in Moldova after the baking fraud in 2014, it is still found among the most advanced states in the ENP.

interaction (executive) but also parliamentary and civil society fields that are essential to success in rule transfer¹⁰.

In Addition, we shall address respectively the greatest interest in the area regarding democracy, human rights, good governance and stability. This field is considered to be the most relevant and dynamic. And, at the same time, it deals with European core norms, which are very significant in the study of European normative promotion¹¹. Regarding normative impact, it should be observed through socialization, partnership and ownership, as I. Manners argues¹². The latter aspects will be considered in our study. Nevertheless, owing to the complexity of the socialization process, the notion of I. Manners will be enriched by J. Checkel's contributions in this field. In particular, we will mention the three mechanisms of socialization (strategic calculation, role playing and normative suasion), which facilitate to switch from logic of consequences to logic of appropriateness¹³.

Furthermore, another phenomenon will be included. The reason lies in the fact that, to the same extent, it can explain the rule transfer in the Eastern neighbourhood and, mostly, Eastern Partnership frontrunners like Moldova. In particular, the phenomenon deals with how process of active legitimacy-seeking with the EU strengthens subjective perception of accession prospects, as T. Casier stresses¹⁴. In other words, the more those countries can show better results to European institutions in their rule approach, the more subjective perception of membership is reinforced. It

¹⁰ Normative transformation must be promoted by Government and, not only with parliamentary support but also civil society's involvement. The latter issue can be observed in, for instance, the fight against corruption where measures must be supported at executive, parliamentary and civil society level to eradicate this scourge.

¹¹ The five core European norms are peace, liberty, democracy, rule of law, respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms. See: Ian Manners, "Normative Power Europe: A contradiction in terms?", *Journal of Common Market Studies*, 40, 2, (2002): 235.

¹² Ian Manners, "The European Union's Normative Power: Critical Perspectives on the Critical", in *Normative Power Europe: Empirical and Theoretical Perspectives*, 226-24, (Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2011).

¹³ Jeffrey T. Checkel, "International Institutions and Socialization in Europe: Introduction and Framework", *International Organization*, 59, (Autumn- 2005): 801 and Michael Zürn and Jeffrey T. Checkel, "Socialized to Build Bridges: Constructivism, and Rationalism, Europe and the Nation State", *International Organization*, 59, 4 (Autumn- 2005): 1045.

¹⁴ Tom Casier, "To Adopt or Not to Adopt: Explaining Selective Rule Transfer under the European Neighbourhood Policy", *Journal of European Integration*, 33, 1 (January 2011): 37.

encourages Eastern partners to continue with reforms, which could influence on a greater rule transfer. Although the latter aspect has a higher impact, or at least, more visibility at a bilateral level, it can be found in the multilateral sphere, too. In this sense, peer pressure increases competition among frontrunners to demonstrate better results in the initiatives. Thereby, the interest of being considered as the most reliable partner facilitates a higher impact.

II. Thematic platform I, a new support in Moldovan transformation

Beyond summits and ministerial meetings, thematic platforms covers rule transfers at an executive level due to its participants are senior officials and other civil servants. Thus, normative promotion within this framework is highly important since participants are same civil servants who have to start up and implement agreed reforms.

There are four platforms¹⁵ being the first one which tackles with the issues of democracy, good governance and stability. It is composed by panel on the fight against corruption, panel on improved functioning of the judiciary, panel on integrated border management, panel on migration and asylum, panel on public administration reform, panel on Common Security and Defence Policy cooperation (CSDP) and, finally, the ombudsman project.

As we can observe, platform I covers very appealing subjects to Moldova. On one hand, it deals with some priority areas like fight against corruption or judiciary system. Therefore, its treatment at a multilateral level can support more advances. On the other hand, this project tackles issues in which partners can show great progress. For instance, in migration, asylum and border management areas Moldova has better results. The latter issue is linked to the phenomenon mentioned in the Introduction, which strengthens European normative promotion with Eastern partners and, especially, top neighbours (like Moldova). This tendency invites Eastern partners to keep on agreed and pending reforms. The phenomenon takes place in the multilateral sphere at whole (with a lower incidence at civil society level), which introduces a certain competition that acts as an incentive to impulse certain reforms.

¹⁵ The four thematic platforms are focused on I) democracy, good governance and stability; II) Economic integration and convergence with EU policies; III) energy security and IV) people to people contacts.

In particular, most of panels present a high activity where the EU offers expert meetings, workshops, seminars and so on¹⁶. Most of them are strongly supported by Council of Europe (with EU financial support¹⁷) that reinforces normative promotion in areas where it has an extensive experience, such as judiciary reform. Likewise, member states' role is significant and it facilitates more activities beyond European institutions. Among the latter, those that joined the EU in the last decades, such as Poland or Rumania, play a key role in Eastern neighbourhood. That is why they had to face up to similar challenges in their *acquis* approach as consequence of a common past within the fold of USSR. Finally, we have to stress the involvement of Civil Society Forum, as an observer¹⁸.

In the case of Moldova, socialization (basically, through normative persuasion instrument¹⁹) and association have reached certain goals in most of the cases²⁰. Nevertheless, panel on integrated border management has

¹⁶ See, for further information: "Implementation of the Eastern Partnership: Report to the meeting of Foreign Affairs Ministers, December 13, 2010" (13 December 2010); European Commission and High Representative of the European Union for Foreign Affairs y Security Policy, *Joint Staff Working Paper "Implementation of the European Neighbourhood Policy in 2010 Report: Eastern Partnership"*, Brussels (25 de mayo de 2011), (SEC [2011] 641); or European Commission and High Representative of European Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy, *Joint Staff Working Paper "Implementation of the European Neighbourhood Policy in 2013 Regional Report: Eastern Partnership" Accompanying the document Joint Communication to the European Parliament, The Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions Neighbourhood at the Crossroads: Implementation of the European Neighbourhood Policy in 2013*, Brussels, 27 March 2014, (SWD [2014] 99 final).

¹⁷ From 2011 to 2014, the European support was addressed by Eastern Partnership Facility, with funding of € 4.8 million. Later, the Pragmatic Cooperation Framework of Eastern Partnership Countries, which started last year, has followed it.

¹⁸ In practice, countries such as Belarus limit its involvement since it considers certain issues outside the scope of civil society. Laure Delcour, "The Institutional Functioning of the Eastern Partnership: An Early Assessment", *Eastern Partnership Review*, 1, (October, 2011): 24.

¹⁹ Checkel, "International Institutions and Socialization in Europe: Introduction and Framework".

²⁰ María Victoria Rodríguez Prieto, *La Asociación Oriental como expresión de la política europea de vecindad: refuerzo de la actuación normativa con los Estados vecinos de Moldavia y Georgia 2009-2015*, PhD, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, (Madrid, 2015), www.ucm-eprints.com

the greatest impact on Moldovan case. This is the result of rule promotion through panels, seminars and other items, but mainly activities on the ground that allow real implementation of European standards. In this way, European action goes beyond socialization and partnership aspects in the development of ownership being a key element in the reach of a greater normative impact.

The main difference of this panel lies in the extra financial funds received from the so-called «flagship initiative». In Addition, we have to highlight support of Frontex and certain member states, the majority being Poland, Rumania or Check Republic, which is highly useful for the Eastern partners, as we pointed above. However, transmission not only takes place from member states to neighbouring countries, but also from neighbouring states to other neighbours. In this peer-to-peer learning, Moldova plays a key role since it has a superior position in this area²¹ being useful for countries like Armenia or even Georgia. On the other hand, the high involvement and participation of Moldova let a greater impact.

III. European Parliament as main promoter of Euronest Assembly: a multilateral forum from which to foster a more approach towards European standards

Another multilateral initiative is the Euronest assembly, which aims to promote a greater political association and economic integration

²¹ Moldova's advances in this field can be seen at: European Commission and High Representative of the European Union for Foreign Affairs y Security Policy, *Joint Staff Working Document «Implementation of the European Neighbourhood policy in the Republic of Moldova in 2013 and recommendations for action»*. Accompanying the document *Joint Communication to the European Parliament, the Council, The European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, Neighbourhood at the Crossroads: Implementation of the European Neighbourhood Policy in 2013*, Brussels, 27 March 2014 (SWD [2014] 93 final). And, European Commission and High Representative of the European Union for Foreign Affairs y Security Policy, *«Implementation of the European Neighbourhood Policy in the Republic of Moldova Progress in 2014 and recommendations for actions»*, Accompanying the document *Joint Communication to the European Parliament, The Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions Implementation of the European Neighbourhood Policy in 2014*, Joint Staff Working Document, Brussels, 25 March 2015, (SWD [2015] 69 final).

between the EU and Eastern partners²². This meets a long-standing demand of European Parliament²³ and constitutes an innovation in the framework of the ENP towards East²⁴ that, finally, was integrated in the Eastern Partnership in 2009. Its singularity remains in introducing new ways of understanding and cooperation at parliamentary level, with the Eastern region at whole (except for Belarus²⁵), in tune with European norms.

Members of European Parliamentary and Eastern assemblies work in it together on a wide range of issues²⁶. Specifically, this project includes 60 members of European Parliament and also 10 members from each of six Eastern neighbouring chambers (with the exception of Belarus). Regarding European parliamentarians, most of them are from Eastern member states, like Poland²⁷. And, as it happens in thematic platforms, their involvement is very useful in *acquis* approach for Eastern neighbouring partners. In the case of Moldova, members of national parliament, who belong to different parties like Democratic Party or Party of Communists, composed its delegation. At this moment, Lupu Marian (Democratic Party) is head of the Moldovan delegation in Euronest²⁸ since he substituted Igor Corman in 2013.

²² Euronest, Euronest Parliamentary Assembly “Rules of Procedure Adopted on 3 May 2011 in Brussels, amended on 3 April 2012 in Baku, on 29 May 2013 in Brussels and on 18 March 2015 in Yerevan”, article 1.

²³ European Parliament, *European Parliament Resolution on of 15 November 2007 on strengthening the European Neighbourhood Policy* (P6_TA(2007)0538).

²⁴ While this is true that there were parliamentary committees at bilateral level in the framework of Partnership and Cooperation Agreement, Euronest goes beyond due to it introduces the whole region at all.

²⁵ After all reported irregularities during local elections of December 2010 and arrest of opposition leaders, European Parliament rejected participation of Belarus in Euronest Project.

²⁶ The areas of collaboration are the same as thematic platforms. Euronest, *Euronest Parliamentary Assembly Constituent Act of the Euronest Parliamentary Assembly*, Brussels, 3 May 2011, article 2.

²⁷ See: Delegation to the Euronest Parliamentary Assembly, <http://www.europarl.europa.eu/delegations/es/depa/home.html> (accessed 5 April 2016).

²⁸ List of the delegation of the Parliament of the Republic of Moldova to the Parliamentary Assembly of the Eastern Partnership (EURONEST), www.euronest.eu (accessed 11 April 2016).

While this is true that European Parliament is the main promoter, other actors are involved in Euronest project. In particular, European External Action Service (EEAS) or European Commission participates in some meetings to offer further information. Thereby, European Parliament's normative exportation is strengthened. Finally, Civil Society is included in this initiative, as an observer, too. Otherwise, in contrast to thematic platform I, Council of Europe doesn't get involved in Euronest. It has been criticised by the organization²⁹.

Mainly, the Euronest assembly is characterized by taking European Parliament's project as a model. That is to say, Euronest copies the main features of the European Parliament; hence, this is why we can find similarities in its organization³⁰, and more importantly, the working methods (elaboration of reports, discussion or even voting). Nevertheless, we can find some differences like, for example, distribution of seats that is determined not by political families but alphabetical order (by surname).

In particular, the greatest outcome of Euronest lies in the adoption of certain resolutions at the core of plenary sessions³¹, whose drafts were elaborated and approved by committees previously³². The singularity is found in the way of dealing with controversial issues belonging to the area of democracy, human rights, good governance and stability, in accordance with European perspective. Resolutions, in turn, include mention of art. 49 TEU that has a high interest to Moldova being the promoter of it. For the moment, the most ambitious resolution was the following: «Resolution on challenges for the future of democracy, including the question of free and

²⁹ Conseil de L'Europe, "Le Conseil de l'Europe et le Partenariat oriental de l'Union européenne", 9 February 2011, <http://assembly.coe.int/ASP/Doc/XrefViewHTML.asp?FileID=13077&Language=FR>

³⁰ Its core structure includes a plenary assembly, bureau, committees and secretariat. Euronest, *Euronest Parliamentary Assembly Constituent Act of the Euronest Parliamentary Assembly*, Brussels, 3 May 2011, article 5.

³¹ Since 2011, Euronest has celebrated four plenary sessions. That is to say, one meeting per year with the exception of 2014 since it coincided with European Parliament elections. In fact, the last session was held in Yeveran (16- 18 March, 2015).

³² There are four committees focused on: 1) Political Affairs, Human Rights and Democracy, 2) Economic Integration, Legal Approximation and Convergence with EU Policies; 3) Energy security and 4) Social affairs, Education, culture and civil society.

independent media in Eastern Partnership and EU countries», approved in Baku (2012)³³.

Relating to Moldovan, the Euronest assembly reinforces its approach towards the *acquis communautaire* by means of socialization (strategic calculation and persuasive normative instruments³⁴), association and, in a lesser degree, appropriation³⁵. Nevertheless, Euronest fulfilment is incomplete. The main factor is that resolutions are not binding due to Euronest assembly is not a legislative chamber. Therefore, implementation is in the hands of political willingness, which could prevent reaching the ownership of EU norms. Furthermore, though resolutions address issues of interest, its treatment is often vague. In particular Moldova found a high level of ambiguity in the texts; the reason being that these matters of interest would not be approved by so many different countries otherwise. In this regard, further specification is necessary to guide transformation.

Finally, the dispute over Nagorno-Karabakh between Armenia and Azerbaijan hinders more ambitious advances. Indeed, tensions emerge in every meeting being why the conflict is harmful to the Euronest project at whole.

III) Eastern Social Forum: a more ambitious normative agenda but lower impact on Moldova due to complexity of the project

The third multilateral project is the Civil Society Forum, which is composed by a large number of NGOs and civil organizations from EU and Eastern partners, mainly those that work in the aim of European integration. It follows the purpose of strengthening civil society of Eastern countries and also accompanying executive and parliamentary efforts at multilateral level. The accompaniment deeps on raising awareness and society involvement that is a key aspect in the reach of a successful normative promotion, as previously stressed.

³³ Euronest Parliamentary Assembly, *Resolution on challenges for the future of democracy, including the question of free and independent media in Eastern Partnership and UE countries*, 3 April 2012.

³⁴ Checkel, "International Institutions and Socialization in Europe: Introduction and Framework".

³⁵ Rodríguez, *La Asociación Oriental como expresión de la política europea de vecindad: refuerzo de la actuación normativa de la Unión Europea con los Estados vecinos de Moldavia y Georgia 2009-2015*.

Regarding Moldova, a high number of organizations are involved in the forum. The national platform embraces associations that deal with concerns about fight against corruption, transparency, environmental issues and so on. Nowadays, Ion Manole (Promo-LEX) is the main coordination of Moldovan platform. But, in the past it was lead by Lilia Carasciuc (International Transparency) or Sorin Mereacre (Eastern Partnership Foundation).

In democracy, human rights, good governance and security area, by way of contrast with thematic Platform I and the Euronest assembly, Civil Society Forum has encouraged a deeper and more ambitious normative agenda. In particular, a deeper treatment on human rights and democracy issues make a difference. In fact, both areas are key aspects at the hearth of this project where different initiatives have been developed. In our view, it is leap forward to a deeper promotion of the *acquis communautaire* in the multilateral sphere.

In Moldova, Civil Society Forum has a moderate impact. The reason remains in the complexity of the project that required a long time to set up and operate properly. Therefore, it has become effective over the last few years. Additionally, there is a regular rotation of its members. While it is true that this encourages a wider participation, it may also adversely affect European impact insofar as Eastern participants do not have long-term contact with EU norms and practices. But above all else, there is a necessity to launch more measures beyond index, conferences and reports³⁶. Thus, European normative exportation could go beyond socialization or association and reach appropriation of norms. However, electoral missions are the exception that should be the role model at the core of Civil Society Forum.

³⁶ Some actions driven by Civil Society Forum are: Eastern Partnership Civil Society Forum, "Report from the Eastern Partnership Civil Society Forum meeting of Working Group 1 on Democracy, Human Rights, Good Governance and Stability", 2010, http://www.eap-csf.eu/assets/files/publications/WG1_EaPCSF_mtg_report.pdf (accessed 12 April 2016); Eastern Partnership Civil Society Forum, "Judicial Independence in the Eastern Partnership Countries (Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Georgia)", 2011, http://www.eap-csf.eu/assets/files/publications/Judicial_Independence_in_the_EaPCountries.pdf, (accessed 12 April 2016).

Lastly, we should mention the non-participation of organizations from the independent region of Transnistria. Although there is a timid attempt in the Moldovan platform, certain involvement would be constructive since it could facilitate some contact at civil society level.

Nevertheless, it is necessary to recognize some progress³⁷. Notably, Civil Society Forum has great relevance in the involvement of Eastern society voice, not only at a European level but also in a domestic context. In fact, the forum has become an interlocutor, which is gaining influence little by little. In this respect, national platforms play a key role since their comments and reports are taken into consideration by EU institutions, which do not hesitate on using them to ask for accountability from those who govern. Equally important is its presence at a national level where platforms collaborate with government, that, in the case of Moldova, it is at an early stage.

Conclusions

The Eastern Partnership promotes a more ambitious normative promotion and it has enabled Moldova to reach significant achievements. The main reason remains in a more adequate EU answer, which characterized by being closer to needs and interest of Eastern partner. Such answer has been carried out by means of new measures, at both bilateral and multilateral levels, with a higher economic support. The relevance of measures remains in encouraging increased collaboration and interaction with EU in tune with its core values.

Focusing on the multilateral track, it has become a dynamic forum for exchange and cooperation³⁸. Special attention will be devoted to the multilateral projects of thematic platform I, Euronest Assembly and Civil Society Forum. The latter have supported undertaken changes by Moldova at executive, parliamentary and civil society level. In particular, thematic platform I has had the greatest normative impact on the area of

³⁷ Grzegorz Gromadzki, "The Eastern Partnership after Five Years: Time for Deep Rethinking", (Brussels: Directorate General for External Policies, European Parliament), 2015.

³⁸ European Commission and High Representative of the European Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy, *Joint Communication to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions "Review of the European Neighbourhood Policy"*, Brussels, 18.11.2015, (JOIN [2015] 50 final).

management border. Nevertheless, the other side of the coin shows us that European impact on it is minor in other areas, which requires an impetus, such as human rights. Otherwise Euronest Assembly and Civil Society Forum have reached a moderated impact. But, it is gaining more relevance little by little³⁹.

But, in general terms, the three multilateral projects (thematic Platform I, Euronest and Civil Society Forum) allow an initial and greater approach to the *acquis communautaire* concerning democracy, human rights, good governance and stability area. Indeed, they act as additional instruments in the normative adoption led by Moldova.

In summary, the Eastern Partnership has had an impact on undertaken transformation by Moldova. Therefore, the EU has been able to get closer (at least in the case of Moldova) to the aim states in article 8 TEU⁴⁰. This achievement is due to the EU, as a normative power, has become more attractive and persuasive; principally through establishment of new and innovative measures. However, this advance represents a turning point in Moldova, which has to keep on more pending reforms and, even more, so if we consider its political instability that will require major progress.

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³⁹ *Joint Declaration of the Eastern Partnership Summit* (Riga, 21-22 May 2015)

⁴⁰ Article 8 states to: «1. The Union shall develop a special relationship with neighbouring countries, aiming to establish an area of prosperity and good neighbourliness, founded on the values of the Union and characterised by close and peaceful relations based on cooperation. 2. For the purposes of paragraph 1, the Union may conclude specific agreements with the countries concerned. These agreements may contain reciprocal rights and obligations as well as the possibility of undertaking activities jointly. Their implementation shall be the subject of periodic consultation». *Consolidating Version of the Treaty of European Union, OJEU*, 24.10.2012, C 326, p.1.

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Domeniul de securitate în Acordul de Asociere Republica Moldova – Uniunea Europeană

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Abstract: As is known, the security of major importance in the Moldova-EU dialogue. The increased interest of the EU to create an area of stability and prosperity Eastern Europe led to the inclusion of Moldova ENP (European Neighborhood Policy) which through its instrument of implementing the Association Agreement Moldova - EU allowed the connection rules and institutional system Moldovan Community standards. Finishing the work of the ENP has shown that many problems remain unresolved and EU interest has not diminished for this region. Here's why conceived another policy that comes as a logical continuation of the ENP, eliminating its operating deficiencies. PE (EaP) aims to strengthen the reports between the EU and Eastern European region which remains one of the main sources of insecurity for Europe. Only through the support and logistical help countries in the region can solve their problems benefiting from programs and community projects.

Keywords: Association Agreement, Eastern Partnership, European Union, Moldova, policy, security.

Securitatea națională a Republicii Moldova nu poate fi concepută în afara contextului securității europene. Luînd în considerare faptul că Uniunea Europeană este un factor stabilizator, important pentru sistemul de securitate națională, Republica Moldova va depune eforturi pentru a avansa în procesul de integrare europeană. Aderarea în perspectivă la Uniunea Europeană va consolida securitatea țării, Republica Moldova devenind beneficiar și sursă de stabilitate și securitate. Negocierea unui cadru de cooperare care să reflecte fără echivoc perspectiva de aderare rămîne un obiectiv strategic pentru Republica Moldova. O atenție deosebită în cadrul eforturilor de integrare va fi acordată intensificării cooperării cu UE pe linia Politicii Externe și de Securitate Comună (CFSP) și CSDP, orientată spre consolidarea securității naționale și a celei regionale. Republica Moldova va coopera cu UE în domeniile prevenirii și soluționării conflictelor, gestionării

crizelor, neproliferării armelor de distrugere în masă. Finisarea perioadei de implementare a Planului de Acțiuni Uniunea Europeană - Republica Moldova (PAUEM) necesită elaborarea unui nou cadru politico-juridic în relațiilor dintre Republica Moldova și Uniunea Europeană în perioada post-implementare a PAUEM. Autoritățile de la Chișinău sau pronunțat pentru negocierea unui nou document-cadru cu structurile europene care ar reprezenta o etapă mai avansată decât cea ce propun documentele deja semnate cu UE.

Vectorul nostru european a fost puternic influențat de apropierea geografică cu UE. Chiar de la început a apărut problema esenței acestui fenomen pentru țara noastră: fie că este o predifinire geopolitică, fie o dorință clară a politicii și societății noastre. Suntem de părerea că aceasta trebuie să fie o alegere de politică internă¹ [25, p. 114] ceea ce ar garanta includerea plenară a RM în structurile comunitare într-o perioadă relativ scurtă. Transformarea RM ca vecin direct al UE începînd cu 2007, prin integrarea României la UE, oferă posibilitățile aplicării în practică a prevederilor art. 49 din Tratatul de la Nisa precum și ale art. 237 al Tratatul de la Roma, în care este prevăzut că orice stat european poate deveni membru al UE² [71, p. 138], deci Moldova are aceste șanse cel puțin teoretic, conformîndu-se la majoritatea cerințelor de ordin geografic și istorico-cultural. În același timp conștientizăm că acesta este un proces îndelungat și complex, dar care ar putea avea o finalitate pentru Moldova. În Republica Moldova, PEV a dat naștere la mari speranțe în ceea ce privește șansele țării noastre de a se integra rapid în spațiul UE. Atât autoritățile centrale, cât și principalele partide parlamentare sperau că PEV va deschide Moldovei drumul spre integrarea în UE. Speranțele clasei politice, precum și ale opiniei publice din țara noastră s-au împlinit, însă, doar parțial.

PEV a recunoscut aspirațiile europene ale Moldovei, dar nu i-a acordat o perspectivă clară de aderare la UE într-o perioadă previzibilă. De asemenea, deși țării noastre i s-a oferit, pentru prima oară, perspectiva integrării treptate în spațiul economic al UE, colaborarea bilaterală între Chișinău și Bruxelles a rămas în continuare dominată de limitele și constrângerile legale și instituționale impuse de Acordul de parteneriat și

¹ Cebotari S., *Politica externă a Republicii Moldova în contextul proceselor integraționiste: interes și priorități*. Chișinău, 2007. 169 p.

² Цыганков П., *Теория международных отношений*. Из. Гардарики. Москва, 2004. 590 с.

cooperare (APC). APC plasase relațiile moldo-comunitare pe traiectoria unei cooperări pe orizontală și, prin urmare, nu mai corespundea cu aspirațiile de integrare europeană ale Moldovei. Mai mult decât atât, țara noastră a fost inclusă în PEV alături de un șir de state sud-mediteraneene din Africa de Nord și Asia Mijlocie.

Pentru impulsionarea dialogului politic dintre UE și statele vecine a fost concepută Politica Europeană de Vecinătate (PEV), prin care se dorea crearea unui cerc de prieteni prin democratizarea lor și ca urmare a ridicării nivelului de prosperitate național³ [67, p. 75]. În același timp aceasta nu este o politică pentru state cu perspectivă de aderare la structurile europene ci, este mai degrabă crearea unei zone de influență europeană și excluderea posibilității apariției noilor linii de demarcare pe continentul european. Pentru perioada 2000-2006, UE a alocat în acest scop 8,4 miliarde euro prin programele MEDA, TACIS ș.a., iar Banca Europeană Pentru Investiții a oferit 2,5 milioane euro, ceea ce demonstrează un interes sporit al europenilor pentru această zonă. Pentru perioada 2007 – 2015, se preconizează că UE va oferi asistență statelor participante în cadru PEV în volum de circa 13,9 milioane euro. La capitolul dialog politic moldo-comunitar, se înregistrează o activizare a comunicării între autoritățile moldovene și reprezentanții Comisiei Europene, Consiliului UE și Parlamentului European, atât în cadrul instituțional stabilit de APC, cât și în contextul inițiativelor regionale din Europa Centrală și de Sud-Est. Concomitent, o atenție aparte este acordată valorificării oportunităților și potențialului oferit de cooperarea politică bilaterală a Moldovei cu statele membre ale UE.

Republica Moldova va utiliza activ cadrul de cooperare cu Uniunea Europeană, cadrul de cooperare multilaterală, oferit de ONU, de Consiliul Europei, de OSCE, de NATO, de Inițiativa Central Europeană, de Procesul de Cooperare din Sud-Estul Europei, de alte organizații și inițiative internaționale, precum și programele și inițiativele orientate spre prevenirea și reglementarea conflictelor regionale și a celor interne, spre abordarea și soluționarea problemelor de securitate globală și regională cu impact asupra securității naționale, spre combaterea terorismului internațional, contracararea crimelor transfrontaliere, prevenirea degradării mediului

³ Smith E., *Politica externă a Uniunii Europene*. Ed. Trei. București, 2004. 344 p.

ambiant și bolilor contagioase, a proliferării armelor de distrugere în masă, spre eliminarea sărăciei și promovarea dezvoltării etc. Luînd în calcul persistența conflictelor ce amenință securitatea regională și afectează integritatea teritorială și independența statelor suverane, Republica Moldova sprijină crearea și eficientizarea, în cadrul organizațiilor internaționale relevante, în particular al ONU, UE și al OSCE, a mecanismelor de mediere, de prevenire și de gestiune a crizelor și a conflictelor, precum și a mecanismelor de control al onorării angajamentelor asumate de statele membre. Participarea la operațiunile internaționale sub egida ONU, UE și OSCE se va înscrie în contextul contribuției Republicii Moldova la eforturile internaționale de asigurare a securității. Dezvoltarea capacităților necesare participării la operațiunile internaționale umanitare, de pacificare și de salvare-deblocare, precum și mărirea amplitudinii acestei participări fac parte integrantă a planurilor de dezvoltare și de reformă a Forțelor Armate și a structurilor sectorului de securitate națională⁴ [29, p. 92-96].

În calitate de membru responsabil al comunității internaționale, luînd în calcul producerea și traficul ilegal de arme din zonele aflate în afara controlului guvernelor țărilor afectate de conflicte interne, Republica Moldova sprijină eforturile care urmăresc sporirea măsurilor de încredere, consolidarea și extinderea regimurilor internaționale de control al armamentelor, prevenirea proliferării armelor de distrugere în masă și a unor categorii de arme convenționale. Republica Moldova va participa activ la eforturile direcționate spre revitalizarea regimului de control asupra armamentului convențional în Europa și a principiilor fundamentale pe care se bazează acest regim de control, în primul rînd a principiului internațional recunoscut al necesității acordului liber exprimat al statului gazdă pentru staționarea de forțe militare străine pe teritoriul său. Implementarea angajamentelor asumate anterior în acest context va crea condițiile necesare pentru instituirea unui nou regim de control asupra armamentului convențional în Europa. Cooperarea în cadrul CSI în domeniile ce țin de securitate este condiționată de angajamentele asumate la momentul aderării la această organizație, potrivit cărora Republica Moldova nu participă la abordarea problemelor politico-militare. Astfel, prioritate se va

⁴ Desmond D.(coord.), Originile și evoluția Uniunii Europene. Ed. Știința. Chișinău, 2010. 376 p.

acorda dimensiunii economice, comerciale cu impact asupra securității economice și energetice a Republicii Moldova, precum și cooperării bilaterale cu țările membre ale CSI⁵ [67, p. 12-16].

În acest sens, merită evidențiate parteneriatele europene existente de facto între Moldova și statele UE, precum Lituania, Ungaria, Polonia, Cehia, Suedia și Marea Britanie. România este în continuare un promotor natural și ferm al aspirațiilor europene ale Moldovei în UE, însă animozitățile politice bilaterale împiedică Chișinăul și Bucureștiul să pună bazele unui parteneriat european eficient. Cercurile politice autohtone au avut păreri diferite în ceea ce privește includere RM în cadrul PEV. Cei care susțineau includerea statului nostru în cadru acestei politici aduc ca argument îmbunătățirea în orice caz a relațiilor moldo-europene. Însă participare noastră în această politică europeană stopează în perspectivă scurtă și medie aderarea noastră plenară în UE, fiind prevăzută în însăși conceptele PEV că este o politică europeană pentru statele care nu au perspective europene pe o perioadă scurtă și medie, RM fiind plasată la același nivel cu statele din Africa de Nord sau Caucazul de Sud. Diplomația moldovenească a hotărât să folosească această politică ca o punte de legătură pentru un cadru politico-juridic mai avansat cu UE⁶. O bună activitate a RM în cadrul PEV ar însemna o mai bună prestație în cadrul PSESE și includerea RM în grupul statelor Balcanilor Occidentali, adică perspective de scurtă durată pe calea aderării la UE. Excluderea noastră din Pactul de Stabilizare și Asocierie din cauza unei imagini proaste în Occident ca stat est-european, la care s-au adăugat problemele interne ca: insecuritate social-economică, separatism, crimă organizată, proliferarea armelor convenționale, instabilitate politică, a zădărnicit planurile ambițioase ale diplomației moldovenești. Autoritățile moldovenești invocă lipsa de echitate, statele din regiunea Balcanică confruntându-se cu probleme similare, dar fiind facilitate de programe europene mai avansate decât cele destinate pentru Moldova.

După cum și era prevăzut în cadrul PEV, instrumentul principal de realizare va fii Planul Individual de Acțiuni. RM a semnat cu UE în februarie 2005 acest plan, ceea ce reprezintă o oportunitate de a se apropia de UE la nivel economic, politic, social și cultural. Însă PAUEM nu corespunde în linii

⁵ Smith E., *Politica externă a Uniunii Europene*. Ed. Trei. București, 2004. 344 p.

⁶ Fuerea A., *Instituțiile Uniunii Europene*. Ed. Universul Juridic. București, 2002. 318 p.

marii dorinței noastre, deoarece nu prevedea aderarea RM la UE, dar totuși recunoaște aspirațiile europene ale RM. În plus, realizarea acelor reforme politice, economice, sociale ne vor permite pe viitor o integrare în structurile europene. Implementarea s-a petrecut neuniform, astfel în domeniul politic s-au înregistrat progrese la capitolul cooperare cu CoE; colaborarea autorităților centrale cu societatea civilă; managementul frontierelor care au progresat datorită activității programului EUBAM la frontierele moldo-ucrainene. UE a fost atrasă în soluționarea conflictului transnistrean⁷ [65, p. 91], ceea ce a permis instalarea unui echilibru de forță între RM și Transnistria, prin aplicarea formatului de negocieri "5+2".

Reglementarea diferendului transnistrean este unul din domeniile prioritare de pe agenda relațiilor UE-RM. Problema conflictului nesoluționat creează o serie de riscuri *hard și soft* la adresa securității europene, care provin din lipsa unui regim constituțional în regiune, proliferarea activităților ilicite și staționarea unui larg contingent de trupe și muniții rusești fără acceptul sau supravegherea Republicii Moldova și contrar angajamentelor internaționale ale Federației Ruse. Aceste riscuri au devenit mai proeminente odată cu aderarea României la Uniunea Europeană, la 1 ianuarie 2007, ceea ce a dus zona de conflict la o distanță și mai mică de frontiera UE. Mai mult, existența conflictului „înghețat” și lipsa controlului de facto al Republicii Moldova asupra teritoriilor din estul Nistrului constituie un obstacol major pentru dezvoltarea politică și socio-economică a RM, deci și pentru realizarea obiectivelor Politicii Europene de Vecinătate vizavi de Moldova.

Participarea mai activă a RM în cadrul politicilor UE, pune sub semnul întrebării calitatea noastră de membru a CSI. Rusia este statul care exercită și în continuare cea mai mare influență asupra RM în plan politic, economic, social și cultural⁸. Confluența zonelor de interes europene și rusești prin conceptele "vecinătății apropiate" și "cercului de prieteni", pune RM în situația de a deține complicatul statut de dublu vecin atât al Rusiei cât și al UE și imposibilitatea de a alege o direcție strategică în politica externă. În conformitate cu barometrul opiniei publice pentru luna aprilie a.c., mai mult de 70% din respondenți s-au declarat pentru aderarea RM la UE, în același

⁷ Serebrean O., Despre geopolitică. Ed. Cartier. Chișinău, 2009. 176 p.

⁸ Bărbulescu I. Gh., Sistemul instituțional. Ed. Tritonic. București, 2007. 238 p.

timp doar 20% din respondenți consideră că parteneriatul strategic al Moldovei trebuie să fie cu UE și 52% cu Rusia, ceea ce demonstrează încă o dată nedeterminarea politică nu doar la nivelul elitelor politice, dar și al populației. Clasa politică în mare măsură realizează dolianțele electoratului nedeterminat în probleme de politică externă. Populația așteptă de la colaborarea atît cu Rusia cît și cu UE o îmbunătățire a condițiilor de trai în Moldova. Dar nu trebuie să neglijăm interesul UE, acceptarea unui nou membru, este extrem de problematică în cazul RM, chiar și în perspectivă medie. La moment poziția europenilor poate fii definită prin fraza "obosit și ocupat"⁹, obosit de valuri de extindere și noi state aderate cu multe probleme și ocupat cu instituționalizarea internă.

Analizînd istoric, constatăm că valurile de extindere s-au produs la interval mare de timp și de obicei în grupuri. RM este o țară mică cu o economie care nu poate reprezenta riscuri pentru ceilalți membri ai organizației¹⁰, deaceea se presupune că europenii nu ne vor stopa/îngreuna calea spre UE. RM are două variante de a acționa în raporturile sale cu UE. Prima ar fi finanțarea sporită din partea UE, lucru care a și fost folosit o perioadă foarte lungă de timp de autoritățile de la Chișinău. În acest caz există o serie de riscuri ca finanțarea de la UE să aibă o eficiență scăzută, ceea ce ar duce la un rezultat absolut invers decît cel scontat ca extinderea fenomenului corupției, slăbirea structurilor instituționale, lipsa mecanismelor proprii de dezvoltare economică, statul fiind doar în așteptarea ajutorului din afară. Acesta ar duce la dispariția autonomiei RM față de UE și întărirea unor relații de dependență a statului nostru față de actorii străini. În plus, ar duce la eliminarea posibilităților viitoare de atractivități pentru Transnistria pentru care dezvoltarea durabilă a RM ar putea constitui un argument puternic de apropiere benevolă.

Relațiile cu NATO se înscriu în limitele Parteneriatului pentru Pace (PfP), ale Consiliului Parteneriatului Euro-Atlantic (EAPC) și se realizează în practică potrivit Planului Individual de Acțiuni al Parteneriatului (IPAP) Republica Moldova-NATO. Dezvoltarea acestor relații reprezintă o contribuție a țării noastre la consolidarea securității și stabilității europene, care, la rîndul său, are un impact favorabil asupra securității naționale. O

⁹ Brzezinski Z., Marea tablă de șah. Supremația americană și impereativele sale geostrategice. Ed. Univers Enciclopedic. București, 2000. 240 p.

¹⁰ Sava I N., Studii de securitate. Ed. CRSR. București, 2005. 304 p.

asemenea strategie va asigura Republicii Moldova trecerea de la calitatea de consumator la cea de sursă a securității și a stabilității regionale, iar participarea în continuare la PFP și EAPC îi va permite să utilizeze și să implementeze experiența internațională în reformarea sectorului de securitate și de apărare.

Cooperarea Republicii Moldova cu NATO se înscrie în limitele Consiliului Parteneriatului Euro-Atlantic și ale Parteneriatului pentru Pace, ceea ce nu aduce atingere statutului constituțional de neutralitate permanentă al țării și nu excede cadrul constituțional respectiv. Prin procesul de individualizare și de aprofundare a cooperării cu NATO odată cu lansarea în 2006 a Planului Individual de Acțiuni al Parteneriatului, Republica Moldova urmărește să confirme vectorul de acțiune europeană pe care și l-a asumat, să obțină instrumentele și practicile necesare pentru edificarea unui sector de securitate națională funcțional, capabil să facă față amenințărilor și riscurilor de tip nou, precum și celor convenționale, cu care continuă să se confrunte statul și, implicit, să treacă din categoria de consumator la cea de generator de securitate în regiune¹¹ [49, p. 26-30].

Republica Moldova va valorifica, de asemenea, cooperarea cu NATO în scopul dezvoltării capacităților naționale de pregătire, de prevenire și de gestionare a situațiilor excepționale, precum și a consecințelor acestora. În acest sens, autoritățile relevante vor intensifica schimbul de experiență și consultările cu NATO în vederea preluării și implementării celor mai bune practici în materie. Cooperarea cu NATO în domeniul științific urmărește dezvoltarea potențialului științific și tehnic al Republicii Moldova, aplicarea standardelor adecvate cu impact asupra securității, precum și perfecționarea capacității statului de a reacționa la amenințările societății moderne.

Lansarea Parteneriatului Estic(PE) a avut loc la Bruxelles la 3 decembrie 2008¹², fiind un parteneriat ambițios și strategic, dar care în același timp nu prevede și nici nu presupune expres perspective de aderare și, este mai degrabă o etapă în procesul integraționist decât un mecanism de integrare. PE nu este menit să asiste statele pe parcursul căii de aderare, sau

¹¹ Huntington S., Ciocnirea civilizațiilor și refacerea ordinii mondiale. Ed. Antet. București, 2007. 280 p.

¹² Busek E., Mikulitsch W., Uniunea Europeană și drumul spre răsărit. Ed. Institutul European. Iași, 2005. 232 p.

să urgenteze acest proces. Republica Moldova(RM) s-a arătat deranjată de faptul că a fost inclusă în aceeași politică cu state ca Azerbaidjan sau Belarusia care nu au perspective de integrare pe termen scurt și mediu, ceea ce presupune și diminuarea șanselor de integrare și pentru țara noastră. Integrarea europeană reprezintă o prioritate constantă și ireversibilă a politicii externe și interne a Republicii Moldova, pentru realizarea căreia se vor utiliza permanent toate posibilitățile existente¹³, stabilind modalitatea de integrare europeană a Republicii Moldova, creînd un spațiu de comerț liber profund și comprehensiv cu UE, și fixînd un proces clar de avansare a liberalizării regimului de vize și consolidare a legăturilor de cooperare în domeniile sectoriale.

PE pornește de la necesitatea consolidării și diversificărilor ofertelor comunitare în Europa de Est, într-o măsură mai mare decît oferea Politica Europeană de Vecinătate(PEV). Facînd parte din cadrul multilateral, PE propune șase inițiative emblematice pentru a da un impuls suplimentar, mai mult conținut și mai multă vizibilitate procesului integraționist. Aceste inițiative atrag fonduri de la diferite Instituții Financiare Internaționale precum și investiții din sectorul privat¹⁴.

Cele șase inițiative sunt:

- *Gestionare Integrată a Frontierelor (GIF)*. Acest concept facilitează mobilitatea cetățenilor prin asistarea partenerilor din țările terțe în dezvoltarea de strategii GIF, prin armonizarea regulilor de gestionare a frontierelor și prin adoptarea de bune practice conforme cu standardele UE. GIF include domenii precum comerț, vamă, vize, delimitarea frontierelor, securitate (contrabandă și trafic de ființe umane) și coridoare de transport pan-europene.

- *Mecanism pentru Întreprinderile Mici și Mijlocii*. Acesta are ca obiectiv consolidarea rolului întreprinderilor mici și mijlocii (IMM) din țările partenere prin îmbunătățirea climatului de afaceri. Prin acest mecanism se oferă fonduri, asistență tehnică și sfaturi IMM-urilor cu scopul de a îmbunătăți cadrul legislativ. Instrumentul IMM este susținut de BERD și de BEI, dar este deschis și spre alte Instituții Financiare Internaționale.

¹³ Bărbulescu I. Gh., Sistemul instituțional. Ed. Tritonic. București, 2007. 238 p.

¹⁴ Moldoveanu D.(coord.), Integrarea Europeană a Republicii Moldova : premise, avantaje și oportunități pierdute. Ed. Știința. Chișinău, 2009. 160 p.

- *Piețe electrice regionale, eficiență energetică și energie regenerabilă.* Au ca scop integrarea piețelor energetice din UE și din țările partenere și interconectarea rețelelor lor pentru a crește eficiența energetică, a îmbunătăți securitatea aprovizionării și pentru a contribui la obiectivele schimbării climatice.

- *Diversificarea aprovizionării cu energie.* Inițiativa prevede dezvoltarea cooperării cu partenerii estici pentru a garanta accesul la surse și rute de tranzit alternative de aprovizionare cu energie cu scopul de a evita viitoare crize energetice. Atingerea acestui obiectiv presupune o cooperare mai strânsă între producători, consumatori și operatori pentru a garanta o siguranță de aprovizionare cu energie spre Europa și spre țările partenere. De asemenea, aceasta mai înseamnă și îmbunătățirea condițiilor de aprovizionare pe termen lung și a angajamentelor de achiziționare, a garanțiilor de tranzit și a infrastructurii de securitate care ar putea fi atrăgătoare atât pentru țările terțe furnizoare, cât și pentru investitorii potențiali de infrastructură.

- *Prevenirea, pregătirea și răspunsul în cazul dezastrelor naturale sau provocate de om.* Pentru a preveni catastrofele naturale sau cele provocate de om (inundații, incendii, riscuri de afectare a sănătății, poluare maritimă) precum și efectele schimbării climatice, această inițiativă prevede consolidarea capacităților pentru evitarea și gestionarea catastrofelor, la nivelul local, regional și național. Acest obiectiv este atins printr-o cooperare strânsă între UE (Mecanismul Comunitar de Protecție Civilă) și partenerii estici și între țările partenere, bazându-se pe inițiative existente¹⁵.

- *Governanța Ecologică.* Această inițiativă promovează protecția mediului și soluționarea schimbării climatice, tinde spre o soluționare multilaterală a poluării, printr-un mixt de acțiuni la nivelul internațional, regional și intern. Governanța ecologică cuprinde o serie de acorduri formale și informale ca de exemplu: cum sunt gestionate provocările și oportunitățile legate de folosirea resurselor naturale și a mediului, ce determină care comportament este considerat ca fiind acceptabil, și care reguli și sancțiuni ce afectează modul de folosire a resurselor și a mediului sunt aplicate. Inexistența unei poziții unice a statelor membre a Uniunii

¹⁵ Mazilu D., Integrarea europeană. Drept comunitar și instituții europene. Ed. Lumina Lex. București, 2001. 483 p.

Europene(UE) îngreunează dialogul și parteneriatul cu statele din Estul Europei și nu permite depășirea proiectelor și programelor oferite de PEV. Pentru eficientizarea procesului decizional și consolidarea rapoartelor în interiorul Uniunii s-a propus organizarea întâlnirilor periodice o dată la doi ani la nivelul șefilor de state sau guverne a statelor membre și a celor partenere. Structura operațională a cadrului operațional a PE este ierarhizat în patru trepte:

1. Reuniuni bianuale la nivel de Șefi de Stat și de Guvern;
2. Reuniuni anuale la nivel de Miniștri de Externe ai UE și partenerii din Europa de Est care vor evalua progresele Parteneriatului Estic și vor trasa noi obiective;
3. Reuniuni la nivel de înalți funcționari ce se vor organiza pe patru platforme tematice de cooperare, și anume: democrația, buna guvernare și stabilitatea; integrarea economică și convergența cu politicile UE; securitatea energetică; contactele interumane;
4. Reuniuni la nivel de experți, care, de asemenea, se vor întruni pe cele patru platforme tematice menționate mai sus¹⁶.

PE trebuie să depășească cadrul politico-juridic creat de Acordul de Parteneriat și Cooperare(APC), care nu corespunde situației geopolitice și politice de pe continentul European, care a suferit schimbări după aproape două decenii. Scopul noii politici comunitare este de a extinde cooperarea bilaterală, cu posibilitatea pentru statele partenere de a-și ramifica și aprofunda politicile de integrare. În același timp, prin intermediul acestei politici se creează mecanisme permanente de colaborare dintre UE și cele șase state est europene. Vecinii estici ai UE au teoretic o a doua alternativă și anume intensificarea relațiilor și transformarea acestora în unele strategice cu Rusia, ori pot încerca să balanseze între partenerii estici și cei vestici, cu o politică multivectorială, reieșind din imperativul menținerii puterii și nu a finalizării procesului de integrare. Atît Rusia cît și UE tratează statele din zonă drept spațiu pentru extinderea influenței, piețe de realizare a producției proprii și ca izvoare pentru materie primă. UE însă oferă un set de beneficii care argumentează necesitatea participării statelor din Europa de Est la Parteneriatul Estic, chiar fără o perspectivă clară de aderare.

¹⁶ Moroff H., Europa lărgită – conceptul de vecinătate al Uniunii Europene // Republica Moldova și integrarea europeană. Elemente de strategie. Ed. IPP. Chișinău, 2003. 412 p.

Astfel statele vor avea posibilitățile privind:

- Diversificarea și consolidarea ofertelor PEV pe dimensiunea estică;
- Crearea unei poziții unice în cadrul UE privind Europa de Est;
- Mărirea asistenței politice și economice;

Domeniile cheie o reprezintă facilitarea regimului de vize¹⁷, astfel UE urmînd să ofere statelor participante "Foi de Parcurs" în care sunt stabilite condițiile și acțiunile necesare de întreprins pentru state și cetățenii acestora pentru a beneficia de regimul liberalizat de călătorie în spațiul comunitar. Un alt scop este înființarea unei Zone de Comerț Liber, bazat pe o rețea de acorduri comprehensive comerciale dintre statele UE și cele șase state participante. PE îmbunătățește asistența comunitară în reformarea și modernizarea sectoarelor politico-sociale și economice în conformitate cu standardele europene, ajutorul tehnic și financiar permite eficientizarea eforturilor comune în transformarea statului folosind instrumentele financiare a PEV, sau a resurselor alocate prin intermediul Băncii Europene de Investiții(BEI) și Banca Europeană pentru Reconstrucție și Dezvoltare(BERD). Această politică își propune, nu în ultimul rînd, intensificarea contactelor inter-umane prin colaborările academice, studentești și structurilor non-guvernamentale.

Promovarea stabilității unei bune guvernări și a dezvoltării economice în vecinătatea estică este strategică pentru UE. Participarea la PE nu vor micșora dar nici mări șansele de integrare. Valorile ca democrația, statul de drept, respectarea drepturilor omului, principiile economiei de piață, dezvoltarea durabilă și buna guvernare vor reprezenta baza parteneriatului. Angajamentele și susținerea UE va fi în funcție de progresele realizate de fiecare stat în parte¹⁸. Cooperarea multilaterală va fi realizată în paralel cu parteneriatul bilateral.

José Manuel Barroso, fostul președinte al Comisiei UE, a declarat: „Obiectivele de asociere politică și integrare economică ale Parteneriatului Estic nu pot fi realizate decît dacă ambele părți dau dovadă de o voință și un angajament politic ferm. Trebuie să investim și mai mult în stabilitatea și prosperitatea reciprocă. Aceste eforturi vor fi compensate rapid prin

¹⁷ Robinson P., Dicționar de securitate internațională. Ed. Publishing. Cluj-Napoca, 2010. 254 p.

¹⁸ Canton J., Provăcările viitorului. Principalele tendințe care vor reconfigura lumea în următorii 5, 10, 20, de ani. Ed. Polirom. Iași, 2010. 365 p.

beneficii politice și economice importante și vor duce la o mai mare stabilitate și securitate atât pentru UE, cât și pentru partenerii noștri răsăriteni.”. Parteneriatul Estic stabilește patru platforme tematice cu obiective și intensificare a domeniului politic la nivel multilateral. Aceste platforme sunt folosite atât ca un forum pentru discuții deschise cât și pentru a evalua progresele înregistrate. Ele includ reprezentanți (la nivel înalt) ai ministerelor și ai agențiilor naționale, ai parlamentelor, ai societății civile, ai organizațiilor internaționale (precum OSCE, Consiliul Europei și OECD), ai instituțiilor financiare internaționale, ai sectorului privat, precum și partenerii economici și sociali. Participarea în proiectele, activitățile și reuniunile platformelor tematice se face pe bază de voluntariat și poate include țări terțe, în anumite cazuri. Lucrările acestor platforme tematice sunt susținute de un număr de grupuri de lucru, activând în diverse domenii. Cele patru platforme tematice sunt:

- *Democrația, buna guvernare și stabilitatea.* Această platformă tematică promovează reformele democratice și economice în țările partenere, concentrându-se pe dezvoltarea unor instituții democratice stabile (inclusiv prin standarde electorale, un cadru legislativ pentru mass media și lupta anticorupție) și a unor structuri de stat funcționale. De asemenea, se promovează o implicare mai mare a societății civile în acest proces. Platforma tematică se concentrează și pe politica de securitate, promovarea stabilității, suveranității și integrității teritoriale a țărilor partenere, prin măsuri de consolidare a încrederii și sisteme de alertă timpurie.

- *Integrare economică și convergență cu politicile UE.* Aceasta platformă are ca scop integrarea economică și armonizarea legislativă cu UE. Aceste obiective sunt atinse prin stabilirea pe termen lung a unor acorduri de liber schimb aprofundate și cuprinzătoare (și chiar a unor acorduri regionale de liber schimb) între țările partenere și UE și între țările partenere¹⁹.

- *Securitatea energetică.* Această platformă se concentrează asupra unor probleme legate de securitatea energetică, a tranzitului, a diversificării și a interconectării crescânde între UE și țările partenere. De asemenea, platforma lucrează în direcția armonizării politicilor și legislației din țările

¹⁹ Balaban C-Gh., *Politica europeană de vecinătate*. Ed. Universitară. București, 2009. 122 p.

partenere cu practicile și acquis-ul UE. Prin această platformă se promovează dezvoltarea dialogului privind securitatea energetică și se consolidează strategia în cazul unei crize energetice, pentru a evita pe viitor astfel de situații care ar afecta atât UE cât și țările partenere, prin colaborarea strânsă cu UE NESCO (Rețeaua UE a Corespondenților pe Securitate Energetică), Grupul de Coordonare pentru Gaz, Grupul pentru Aprovizionare cu Petrol și Comunitatea Energetică.

- *Contacte între cetățeni.* Această platformă se concentrează asupra dezvoltării contactelor între cetățenii din UE și din țările partenere, punând accentul mai ales pe tineret, inclusiv prin dezvoltarea societății informaționale și media. Alte domenii care sunt promovate prin această platformă sunt cooperarea culturală, educația și cercetarea. Contactele între cetățeni sunt considerate ca fiind un element esențial pentru promovarea reformelor în țările partenere.

UE va iniția cu statele din regiune Pacte de Mobilitate și Securitate care vor trasa condițiile obligatorii de îndeplinit pentru a facilita mobilitatea populației din statele est-europene în spațiul comunitar. Astfel, aceste pacte vor cuprinde angajamente comune și unilaterale în domeniul contracarării migrației ilegale, modernizarea instituțiilor naționale de azil conform standardelor UE, stabilirea structurilor integrate de control a frontierelor în concordanță cu legislația comunitară, precum și îmbunătățirea abilității poliției și sistemului judiciar în vederea combaterii eficiente a corupției și crimei organizate²⁰. De asemenea, Pactele de Mobilitate și Securitate ar urma să contribuie la liberalizarea treptată a regimului de vize în spațiul UE. Parteneriatul Estic va institui un nou cadru multilateral de cooperare între UE și statele PEV din Europa de Est. În viziunea Comisiei Europene, noul cadru multilateral ar urma să sprijine evoluția relațiilor bilaterale ale UE cu vecinii săi din Est, care vor continua să fie guvernate de principiul diferențierii, ceea ce înseamnă că ritmul și profunzimea dezvoltării lor va depinde de nivelul ambițiilor și capacitățile fiecărui stat în parte. Totodată, noul cadru multilateral va fi mai mult decât un forum de dialog, el va avea menirea să faciliteze elaborarea și realizarea unor poziții și acțiuni concentrate pentru a face față în mod solidar unor provocări comune. De fapt, noul instrument multilateral va imprima substanță concretă asocierii

²⁰ Waltz K., Teoria politicii internaționale. Ed. Polirom. Iași, 2006. 328 p.

politice ce se va stabili între statele din Europa de Est și UE în baza Acordurilor de Asociere²¹ [43].

Moldova consideră următoarele elemente ca fiind esențiale pentru dimensiunea bilaterală a Parteneriatului Estic:

- Aprofundarea cooperării politice, inclusiv în domeniul Politicii Externe și de Securitate Comune a UE;
- Crearea unei Regim Aprofundat și Comprehensiv de Liber Schimb;
- Noi oportunități pentru integrarea economică, inclusiv convergența cadrului regulatoriu și armonizarea legislativă în domeniile relevante ale economiei;
- Dezvoltarea în continuare a avantajelor comparative generate de participarea activă a Moldovei în procesele de cooperare în Europa de Sud-Est;
- Cooperarea strânsă cu UE în vederea îndeplinirii condițiilor necesare pentru a beneficia într-o perioadă previzibilă de regimul de călătorii fără vize în spațiul UE. Prin urmare, liberalizarea regimului de vize pentru cetățenii Moldovei ar urma să fie implementată gradual în cadrul Parteneriatului Estic;
- Instrumente de consolidare a dezvoltării regionale în baza experienței și mecanismelor UE²².

Apropierea de UE depinde în mare măsură de calitatea și viteza reformelor implementate în fiecare stat participant la PE, UE recunoaște și respectă principiile suveranității, independenței și integrității teritoriale a RM. Includerea pleneră în această politică comunitară va permite Republicii Moldova apropierea graduală de structurile europene. PE este necesar de a fi abordat ca o etapă indispensabilă în procesul de aderare la UE și are menirea de a pregăti și coordona statul la sistemul normativ-instituțional și tehnic al standardelor comunitare. Dialogul și cooperarea în domeniul Politicii Externe și de Securitate Comune (PESC) au drept scop convergența treptată, inclusiv privind Politica de Securitate și Apărare Comună (PSAC) și va aborda în particular chestiunile legate de securitate, prevenirea conflictelor și gestionarea situațiilor de criză, stabilitatea regională, dezarmarea, ne-proliferarea, controlul armelor și controlul exporturilor.

²¹ Gilles F (coord.), Dicționarul Uniunii Europene. Ed. Polirom. Iași, 2001. 288 p.

²² Moroff H., Europa lărgită – conceptul de vecinătate al Uniunii Europene // Republica Moldova și integrarea europeană. Elemente de strategie. Ed. IPP. Chișinău, 2003. 412 p.

Cooperarea în acest domeniu se va baza pe valori comune și interese reciproce și se va axa pe sporirea convergenței și eficacității politice, utilizând forurile bilaterale, internaționale și regionale. În particular:

- promovarea soluționării pașnice a conflictelor și stabilității și securității internaționale pe baza multilateralismului efectiv;
- dezvoltarea cooperării cu privire la regimul de sancțiuni al UE;
- promovarea respectării principiilor suveranității și integrității teritoriale, inviolabilității hotarelor și independenței, conform celor stabilite în Carta ONU și Actului Final de la Helsinki al OSCE;
- sporirea cooperării practice în prevenirea conflictelor și gestionarea situațiilor de criză prin facilitarea participării Republicii Moldova în operațiunile de gestionare a situațiilor de criză civile și militare conduse de UE și în activitățile de consultare și instruire în domeniul PSAC (în baza Acordului – Cadru de Participare în vigoare de la 1 iulie 2013 și în cadrul multilateral al Panelului Parteneriatului Estic privind PSAC).

Lansarea și încheierea negocierilor privind Acordul UE – Republica Moldova cu privire la procedurile de securitate pentru schimbul de informație secretă privind chestiunile legate de PSAC, ca urmare a Acordului dintre Republica Moldova și Uniunea Europeană care stabilește cadrul pentru participarea Republicii Moldova în operațiunile Uniunii Europene de gestionare a situațiilor de criză, în vigoare de la 1 iulie 2013. Menținerea participării constructive a Părților în procesul de negociere condus de OSCE axat pe soluționarea conflictului transnistrean. Menținerea cooperării efective dintre UE și Republica Moldova îndreptată spre soluționarea conflictului transnistrean, în formatele convenite, inclusiv consultările asupra aranjamentelor post- reglementare. Consolidarea dialogului în scopul explicării beneficiilor Acordului de Asociere și asigurării aplicării sale pe întreg teritoriul Republicii Moldova. Continuarea dialogului constructiv cu toți omologii relevanți privind problemele de frontieră care vizează conflictul transnistrean. Îmbunătățirea în continuare a gestionării frontierelor și menținerea la un nivel înalt a controalelor la frontieră și supravegherii frontierelor, precum și extinderea și modernizarea facilităților de supraveghere video fixe și mobile. Îmbunătățirea imaginii situaționale la nivel național și local prin continuarea reglării analizei riscurilor, gestionării informației și fluxului de date. Asigurarea în continuare a infrastructurii adecvate, echipamentului tehnic, sistemelor TI, resurselor financiare și

umane în conformitate cu Strategia și Planurile de Acțiune a Republicii Moldova de Management Integrat al frontierei. Susținerea și extinderea în continuare a programelor de instruire și măsurilor anticorupție. Exploatarea în continuare a oportunităților de acțiuni comune, instruire și consultanță de specialitate din partea EUBAM, Frontex și statelor membre ale UE. Utilizarea efectului de pârghie al prezenței EUBAM pentru a intensifica și dezvolta în continuare cooperarea cu Serviciul de Grăniceri al Ucrainei, inclusiv în domeniul schimbului automatizat de date nominale. Explorarea oportunităților cu partenerii ucraineni pentru crearea punctelor de trecere a frontierei comune suplimentare și patrularea în comun a frontierei, inclusiv pe segmentul central al frontierei Moldova-Ucraina.

În baza studiu efectuat în acest paragraf poate fi sintetizate următoarele concluzii Parteneriatul Estic (PE) trebuie să depășească cadrul politico-juridic creat de Acordul de Parteneriat și Cooperare (APC), care nu corespunde situației geopolitice și politice de pe continentul European, deoarece s-a produs deja schimbări profunde, în special în ultimul deceniu după aproape două decenii. Integrarea europeană reprezintă o prioritate constantă și ireversibilă a politicii externe și interne a Republicii Moldova, pentru realizarea căreia se vor utiliza permanent toate posibilitățile existente. Astfel, se va stabilind modalitatea de integrare europeană a Republicii Moldova, creeînd un spațiu de comerț liber profund și comprehensiv cu UE, și inițiindu-se un proces clar de avansare a liberalizării regimului de vize și consolidare a legăturilor de cooperare în domeniile sectoriale cu spațiul comunitar.

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INTERCULTURALITATE / INTERCULTURALITY

Les relations interpersonnelles et interculturelles: la politesse dans la culture européenne

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Abstract: In our interpersonal relationships, we are exposed to the other person's point of view, his opinion and interpretation of us, as he is to ours. In these relations, the communication consists of a verbal or nonverbal exchange of information usually bound to a set of rules, or boundaries which differ according to particular human customs. However, nowadays, we live in a world of increasing violence and aversion to authority, where citizens lose their regulatory marks and their self-control towards others. Politeness, formerly known as "Civility" is the fundamental educational, social and cultural tool. It is one of the principles that implies a form of regulation of instincts, self-control, emotions and feelings, and is sadly a dying concept. In this world where interpersonal and intercultural contacts are essential, it is very important to bring back and to understand the notion of politeness. Our study consists of defining this term, by researching its history and literature, but mainly by a reflection of its perspective in intercultural communication.

Keywords: relations interpersonnelles, relations interculturelles, politesse et culture européenne. les rituels ou rites.

Les Européens et particulièrement les Français sont fiers de leur histoire, de leur patrimoine, de leur langue et culture ce qui fait que certains comportements qui leur sont innés ou acquis, depuis des siècles ou depuis quelques années, peuvent paraître aux vues d'une personne étrangère, d'un touriste comme inadéquats, trop insistants, incompréhensibles et même ridicules. Tout ceci s'explique par le fait que les normes ou rituels français, dont la politesse, sont différents d'une autre culture ou pays et il serait bon de les connaître pour mieux pouvoir les pratiquer, lors de rencontres, dans des lieux et conditions différents. Mais avant tout, il est important de définir ce qu'est un rite ou rituel.

1. Les rituels ou rites

Nous avons plusieurs définitions qui ont toutes une base commune

mais qui se différencie par certaines spécificités. Ainsi, le «rituel» est à la base un terme issu du latin *ritus* qui veut dire un «ordre prescrit», un comportement répétitif et codifié dont la fonction est essentiellement symbolique. Plus encore, il est «une séquence de comportements réglés qui montrent l'appartenance à un groupe social, à une identité de genre, à des traditions religieuses, à un pays, au genre humain»¹. Freud, quant à lui, le définit comme une manière de réguler les pulsions du corps², tandis que René Girard (*La violence et le sacré*) estime que le rite vise la régulation de la violence en la détournant sur un bouc émissaire. Maisonneuve ajoute à ces définitions que les rituels sont «un ensemble (ou un type) de pratiques prescrites ou interdites liées à des croyances magiques et/ou religieuses, à des cérémonies et à des fêtes, selon les dichotomies du sacré et du profane, du pur et de l'impur.» (J. Maisonneuve, «Les rituels», 1988, cité dans De Salins: 6). De Salins définit ce terme comme un «ensemble de règles d'habitudes liées à la coutume ou aux habitudes comportementales de toute communauté, il recouvre les rites substantiels et cérémoniels et les expressions figées liées aux actes sociaux»³ et que les rituels sont des actions complexes et inhérentes de la vie sociale (cf. D. Picard, 2006).

D'après ces quelques définitions, nous pouvons voir que les rituels sont principalement des normes conventionnelles, des «systèmes de signalisation à partir de codes culturellement définis»⁴, une sorte de formalisme justifié par des valeurs comme l'engagement, l'adaptation, l'équilibre, le respect, la discrétion et la distinction. Finalement, nous pouvons dire que tout rituel est un comportement qui nous caractérise et

¹ Denis Jeffrey. *La civilité à l'école*. [En ligne] URL/DOI: https://www.violence-ecole.ulaval.ca/fichiers/site_chaire_cbeaumont/documents/Presentations_ACFAS_2014/Jeffrey_ACFAS_2014.pdf (vu le 24.05.2016)

² Monique David-Ménard, «Les pulsions caractérisées par leurs destins: Freud s'éloigne-t-il du concept philosophique de Trieb?», *Revue germanique internationale* [Online], 18 | 2002, <http://rgi.revues.org/924>

³ Yue Zhang. Pour une approche interculturelle de l'enseignement du français comme spécialité en milieu universitaire chinois. *Linguistics*. Université du Maine, 2012. French. <NNT: 2012LEMA3010>. <tel-00793142>, p. 40.

⁴ Rivière Claude. Maisonneuve (Jean) *Les Rituels*. In: *Archives de sciences sociales des religions*, n 67/2, 1989. p. 305. www.persee.fr/doc/assr_0335-5985_1989_num_67_2_1390_t1_0305_0000_2

qui caractérise le groupe auquel nous appartenons, c'est une forme de démarcation et d'intégration bienfaisante et même nécessaire à la vie en société. Le rituel séculier ou convivialité quotidienne qu'est la politesse permet de s'engager, favorise les contacts, aide à la communication, favorise l'échange et la sociabilité. C'est aussi par elle que l'on reconnaît et estime l'autre mais l'on attire aussi l'estime à soi.

2. Définition de la politesse

La politesse, du latin *politus* qui signifie uni, lisse, brillant, est issu du verbe *polire* qui signifie l'action de polir (sens propre), et celle d'orner avec élégance (sens figuré). Ce mot subit ensuite l'influence du mot italien *pulitezza* (désignant l'élégance et le soin), puis au XVI^e siècle, *politus* finit par donner le mot français «politesse», et le sens actuel daterait probablement du XVII^e siècle. Ainsi nous pouvons le définir comme « *un ensemble des usages sociaux régissant les comportements des gens les uns envers les autres* »⁵. Le terme de politesse fut au premier abord associé à celui de civilité, mot qui était et est resté assez ambigu, pour ensuite en être dissocié et même signifié le contraire.

Quoiqu'il en soit, la politesse appartient au domaine du rituel et chaque société a ses propres formes d'expression de la politesse. La politesse est constituée de normes sociales ayant pour base des formalités. Ces us et coutumes relatives à la politesse varient selon le lieu et l'époque. Ces règles sont acquises par l'éducation, facilite les rapports interhumains, la vie en communauté par des échanges équilibrés et respectueux mais elles sont aussi l'expression d'un «savoir-vivre». Henri Bergson (cf. H. Bergson, 2008) distingue trois formes de politesse:

a. la politesse des manières qui est une application de codes et de règles, «des civilités» qui ne s'identifient pas à la civilisation car «les gens les plus civils ne sont pas toujours les plus civilisés»;

b. la politesse de l'esprit qui est un talent: celui de savoir valoriser ses interlocuteurs et leur accorder l'exacte qualité d'attention qu'ils attendent de vous. La politesse de l'esprit est la capacité d'un homme de pouvoir dans toute occasion parler de ce qui l'intéresse, qui a ses propres réflexions et positions et se distingue par elles ;

⁵ <http://www.larousse.fr/dictionnaires/francais/politesse/62182>

c. La politesse de cœur ou la vertu: sorte de charité faite de modération.

Ces trois formes de politesse définies par Henri Bergson nous introduisent dans un monde idéalisé, un monde de l'esprit démocratique et libre.

A part les formes, nous avons aussi deux degrés de politesse; celui qui est constitué par les salutations, les remerciements et les excuses qui sont respectés par une bonne partie de la population, puis celui qui est plus spécifique, la politesse dite mondaine et qui n'est promulguée que par une petite partie de la population. Cette dernière revêt un caractère beaucoup plus exclusif.

La politesse est une manifestation de la vie quotidienne, verbale basée sur des formules ou formulations (règles, usages et habitudes sociaux) et non verbale basée sur les comportements (les gestes, les attitudes, l'allure, la conduite et les manières) (Pu, 2003: 39).

Tout au long de notre recherche, nous avons été amenée à côtoyer deux termes pour lesquels on note une fluctuation ainsi qu'une interchangeabilité qui rendent leur distinction plus difficile. Il s'agit des termes de «savoir-vivre» et «politesse». Notons que dans le Petit Robert, la «politesse» est défini comme un ensemble de règles qui gèrent les usages dans une société donnée ainsi que «le fait et la manière d'observer ces usages»; alors que le «savoir-vivre» serait plus spécifiquement «la qualité d'une personne qui connaît et sait appliquer» ces règles. Nous nous guiderons et baserons ultérieurement sur ces définitions.

3. L'histoire de la politesse

Il est intéressant de voir que certaines des règles de politesse sont immuables et perdurent tout au long des siècles. Il est possible d'en retrouver certaines ayant subi que très peu de modifications ou de changements et cela dans des sociétés différentes, tandis que d'autres ont totalement disparues ou bien ont évolué d'une façon inattendue. Bon nombre d'entre elles ont été répertoriées dans des traités dits de «civilité» ou de «savoir-vivre». Certaines d'entre elles nous sont expliquées dans ces traités tandis que d'autres nous sont offertes comme telles sans probables explications.

Dans les pays européens, nous pouvons dire que la politesse a une longue histoire. Elle démarre bien assez tôt, à Athènes, où le citoyen

s'engageait à respecter les règles de la cité au nom du civisme démocratique et donc de l'égalité entre tous devant la loi. Ces citoyens grecs pratiquaient la Dialectique ou le dialogue intérieur par l'auto-examen ou l'introspection et apprenaient à se connaître soi-même et donc à réguler leur ardeur animale et instinctive par la politesse et l'autocontrôle. A leur sujet, Furgault (*Recueil historique d'antiquités grecques et romaines*) estimait qu'ils étaient, en général, le peuple le plus poli de l'antiquité et que la ville d'Athènes était le véritable centre des sciences et des beaux-arts mais aussi celui de la politesse. Les écrits de nombreux orateurs, philosophes grecs et plus précisément athéniens sont là pour nous démontrer ces faits.

Dans la Rome antique, la rusticité et la vie champêtre et guerrière des Romains furent un frein au développement des normes de politesse. Cependant, les relations politiques et commerciales qu'ils développèrent avec les Grecs leurs ont ouvert la voie vers la civilisation et la culture où les sciences, les beaux-arts ont trouvé une place prépondérante comme les bonnes mœurs, les bonnes manières et les bons comportements. Plus tard, dans la Gaule romaine, cette notion de politesse fut plus spécifiquement développée comme un respect à l'égard des femmes. On leur montrait des égards et des complaisances tant en public qu'en privé. De même, les personnes âgées comme les personnes de qualité ou à estimer- les plus grands que soi, étaient aussi respectées à leur façon.

Au Moyen Âge, nous retrouvons ces mêmes complaisances ou respect envers les femmes. Elles sont identifiées sous le nom de «courtoisie» lequel provient du mot «cour» qui est à l'opposé de celui de «vilainie» provenant du mot «villa» qui veut dire «ferme» en latin. De ce fait, la courtoisie représente les valeurs qui dirigeaient la vie des nobles à la cour, comme le courage, la fidélité à son suzerain et à sa suzeraine et surtout l'amour. «La courtoisie admire l'art de vivre, l'élégance morale, la politesse de conduite, la générosité, l'humilité envers les dames, le souci de se faire passer pour honorable, le refus de tous mensonges et de toutes lâchetés»⁶.

Plus tard, au XVIe et surtout au XVIIe siècle, ce terme s'identifie plutôt à la «bienséance», ou à la «galanterie»: volonté de posséder le bon

⁶ <http://www2.istp.org/studentscorner/academiccorner99-00/WebCollege/MoyenAge5May2000/we-bcoutoi-sie/texte/LaCourtoisie.html>

goût et le raffinement des manières. Cette bienséance est réservée à une certaine élite sociale, chez les hommes comme chez les femmes (Pu, 2002 b: 40). Le terme de politesse est aussi identifié à un véritable «savoir-vivre» (terme déjà mentionné un peu plus haut dans notre étude) dont Mme de Scudéry consacra un de ses dialogues. Il ne faut pas oublier aussi de mentionner l'emblème de ce «savoir-vivre» qui n'était autre que le roi Louis XIV. Ajoutons à cela que, selon Saint-Simon, ce roi était un véritable «parangon» de politesse, un homme poli par nature. Il avait, dit-on, le don de savoir «mesurer» sa politesse dépendamment de «l'âge, le mérite, le rang» de la personne avec laquelle il s'entretient. Cette «galanterie» à la française devient un lieu commun même à l'étranger.

Durant la période des Lumières, les philosophes, écrivains et artistes ont eux aussi participé à leur façon à l'expression de ce rituel bien que l'on parle d'une égalité dans la société entre les hommes donc entre les genres. On observe une certaine évolution de la politesse vers l'informel. Un véritable changement culturel se mettait en marche avec une présentation de soi tout à fait informelle. Cependant la distinction des termes de politesse, de civilité et de galanterie reste à cette époque assez confuse. Il fallait attendre Chr. Losfeld, avec son *Politesse, morale et construction sociale. Pour une histoire des traités de comportements (1670-1788)*⁷, pour proposer une distinction solvable entre ces termes. Ainsi, au XVIIIe siècle, «la civilité [devient] une notion qui s'adresse à tous et permet d'assigner à chacun une place dans la hiérarchie existante, la politesse est le «caractère distinctif par excellence de la noblesse», alors que la galanterie serait «le summum de la distinction au sein d'une sociabilité aristocratique»⁸. La période du règne de Louis XVI est une période phare de la construction ou plus exactement de la restructuration des normes civiles. Ainsi durant la seconde moitié du XVIIIe siècle français, Jean-Jacques Rousseau a été une figure marquante de ce bouleversement que J.Revel a nommé: «la revanche

⁷ Christophe Losfeld, *Politesse, morale et construction sociale. Pour une histoire des traités de comportements (1670-1788)*, Paris: Honoré Champion, coll. «Les dix-huit siècles», 2011, 488 p., EAN 9782745319869.

⁸ Laurent Turcot, «Civilité, politesse & galanterie au XVIIIe siècle», *Acta fabula*, vol. 12, n 4, Notes de lecture, Avril 2011, URL: <http://www.fabula.org/revue/document6278.php>, page consultée le 28 mai 2016.

de l'intimité»⁹. L'auteur plaidait la sincérité dans la politesse, une sincérité qui n'était pas de mise au siècle précédent et même durant la première moitié du XVIIIe siècle. Ainsi il affirmait dans *l'Émile*: «*Considérez premièrement que, voulant former l'homme de la nature il ne s'agit pas pour cela d'en faire un sauvage et de le reléguer au fond des bois; mais qu'enfermé dans le tourbillon social, il suffit qu'il ne s'y laisse entraîner ni par les passions ni par les opinions des hommes; qu'il voye par ses yeux, qu'il sente par son cœur, qu'aucune autorité ne le gouverne, hors celle de sa propre raison.*» (p. 292)

Après la Révolution, la bourgeoisie voulut retourner aux valeurs anciennes: la civilité qui maintenant était accessible aux gens du peuple fut de nouveau dévalorisée et la politesse quant à elle retrouva une valeur morale reposant sur la position sociale. Aux XXe et XXIe siècles, les incivilités interpersonnelles ainsi que celles entre les peuples prennent souvent l'apparence d'une cause nationale. Dans les médias, le mot «respect» est plus commun, plus présent dans la communication que celui de politesse, cependant nous estimons qu'en exigeant le respect, en fait c'est aussi la politesse qui est revendiquée. A notre avis, ces deux termes sont complémentaires et même sont devenus quasi-synonymes.

4. La littérature sur la politesse

Des siècles durant, des guides spirituels, des éducateurs ou des moralistes se sont efforcés de définir les bonnes manières ou l'art de bien se conduire en société. Ils ont enseigné ces principes à leurs élèves ou leurs disciples au travers de traités. De ce fait, toutes les grandes cultures occidentales possèdent aujourd'hui au moins un ouvrage ainsi que quelques déclinaisons de celui-ci qui décrivent l'art de vivre de son élite sociale et qui servent de référence¹⁰.

⁹ Jacques Revel, «Les usages de la civilité», *Histoire de la vie privée, 3. De la Renaissance aux Lumières*. sous la dir. de Roger Chartier, Paris, Seuil, 1999 (1985), p. 203.

¹⁰ Nombreuses sont les rééditions des anciens traités ou ouvrages. Ainsi nous avons les ouvrages de Didier Érasme de Rotterdam, Jean-Baptiste de La Salle & Henri Bergson, *La Bienséance, la civilité et la politesse enseignée aux enfants*. Textes réunis et présentés par Jean-Pierre Seguin. –Bruxelles: Le Cri; Paris: Jean-Michel Place, 1992. Celui d'Antoine de Courtin, *Nouveau traité de la civilité qui se pratique en France parmi les honnêtes gens*, présentation et notes de Marie-Claire Grassi, Saint-Étienne, Publications de l'Université de Saint-Étienne, 1998. Celui de François de Grenaille, *L'honnête fille : Où dans le premier livre*

Donc la politesse est véritablement un art qui s'enseigne depuis des siècles, mais la littérature de la civilité proprement dite, reste encore une affaire de traités, lesquels sont rédigés sous formes ou genres multiples: en prose ou en vers, sous forme de sermons ou romancés, en passant par des questions futiles à des propos d'envergure nationale – certaines grandes questions du XVIIe siècle n'étaient plus d'actualité au siècle suivant. Véritablement, ce n'est qu'au XIXe siècle que l'on voit une réelle expansion de la littérature de la politesse où des traités de «savoir-vivre» sont publiés dans l'intention de produire une certaine normalisation de la politesse ainsi que de son enseignement – question de pragmatisme selon les événements et les situations. Ces traités deviennent de véritables guides de la vie quotidienne, une codification des relations sociales, de véritables rituels sociaux.

De façon plus précise, nous pouvons dire que durant l'Antiquité apparaissent des textes assez succincts, où sont énoncés les différents principes à suivre lors de certaines circonstances ou événements. Il s'agit ici de comportements à table, lors de fêtes, de cérémonies. Des textes de plus grande envergure, comme ceux de Cicéron ou de Sénèque, ont aussi été retrouvés lesquels arboraient la question de la politesse et de la bonne tenue placée au rang de l'éthique. Cette tendance à l'écriture de ce genre de traités ira de façon exponentielle. Ainsi au Moyen Âge, apparaîtront un nombre impressionnant d'ouvrages qui seront traités comme les ancêtres des traités contemporains du savoir-vivre¹¹. Les textes médiévaux étaient surtout influencés par les règles monastiques qui seront ensuite transmises dans le domaine séculier (J.C. Schmitt, 1990, *La raison des gestes dans l'Occident médiéval*, Paris: Gallimard). Les principes inculqués sont stricts, rigoureux et très explicites. Ainsi nous avons tous les détails en ce qui concerne la vie quotidienne (hygiène, habillement, comportement, etc.); du comment se tenir en différentes occasion (à table, à l'église, à la maison, lors de fêtes et des cérémonies, lors de rencontres officielles ou officieuses);

il est traité de l'esprit des filles, édition critique par Alain Vizier, Paris, Honoré Champion, 2003.

¹¹ Dans l'évolution du «savoir-vivre», on peut déterminer deux moments: le premier est celui de la «littérature de civilité», genre littéraire qui s'est développé dans le monde occidental au XVIe siècle, et le second est celui du «savoir-vivre moderne» qui s'est développé particulièrement en France au XIXe siècle.

du comment avoir un maintien modeste (avoir la tête baissée, les yeux peu mobiles, les jambes non tendues, avoir des gestes sobres); du comment marcher (le dos bien droit, ne pas faire de grands pas, etc.).

Puis au XVI^e siècle, apparaît la «littérature de la civilité» - nouveau genre littéraire qui ne cessera d'évoluer avec le temps. Il s'agit ici d'une véritable «éducation sociale». Deux ouvrages seront les piliers de cette nouvelle tendance littéraire: *le Libro del Cortegiano* (Le Livre du courtisan) de Baldassar Castiglione qui paraît en Italie en 1528 ainsi que *De civilitate morum puerilium* (De la civilité des mœurs puérides) d'Erasme qui paraît à Bâle en 1530. Ce dernier, particulièrement, constitue l'acte de naissance du mot «civilité». Il faut savoir qu'il n'y a rien de proprement inventé car il s'agit bien plus d'une reprise de certains principes et conseils de bon comportement et d'hygiène lesquels existaient déjà dans la tradition médiévale. Cependant, les données sont ici plus concentrées. En Italie du XVI^e siècle, il y eut de nombreux imitateurs des conceptions de Castiglione comme Giovanni Della Casa et son *Galatée* (1558). Son optique était un peu différente et avait pour but de rendre la vie plus agréable, avec moins de conflits et de heurts. Il ne faut pas aussi oublier de mentionner l'ouvrage du grand théoricien de «l'honnêteté», François de Grenaille, *l'Honnête fille*, qui est un traité suffisamment fouillé sur la vieille Querelle des sexes pour connaître plus de quarante ans de succès.

En Europe, entre le XV^e et XVII^e siècle, on parle de domestication de la noblesse ou «curialisation» dans le but de constituer des cours royales et princières. Cette noblesse devra se soumettre à un véritable mécanisme de civilisation des mœurs. Les nobles vont devoir apprendre à dissimuler leurs sentiments et dire et donc simuler de manière à respecter une étiquette (Norbert Elias: *La civilisation des mœurs*).

En France, cette civilité, au XVII^e et XVIII^e siècles, est vue comme une vertu mondaine et chrétienne, ce que nous découvrons dans le *Nouveau traité de la civilité qui se pratique en France parmi les honnêtes gens* d'Antoine de Courtin (1671) où le comportement se distingue selon la condition, l'âge, le lieu et le moment – caractéristiques qui sont encore actuelles aujourd'hui. Ici, la question de la chrétienté est sous-entendue ce qui n'est pas le cas des *Règles de la bienséance et de la civilité chrétienne* de Jean-Baptiste de La Salle (1703), ouvrage dans lequel elle est majeure et donc largement explicitée.

En tant qu'ouvrages de la fin du XIXe siècle, nous ne citerons que la série de la baronne Staffe, et particulièrement *Usages du monde. Règles du savoir-vivre dans la société moderne* (1899), ouvrage qui est tout à fait actuel et se positionne comme un véritable traité de référence.

Les écrits et réflexions de Norbert Elias¹², célèbre sociologue du XXe siècle, vont offrir une nouvelle dimension au processus de civilisation et particulièrement à la question des règles de convenance. L'on remarque que suite à l'évolution des modes de vie et des valeurs, les changements de style, de ton, les formes d'écriture diffèrent, donc nous pouvons parler d'une véritable évolution ou changement en ce qui concerne les traités de bons comportements. Puis, Michel Malherbe, fameux philosophe français, s'interroge dans *Qu'est-ce que la politesse?* sur l'accommodement d'une personne à une autre, sur les problèmes de convenances quotidiennes. De grands noms des sciences sociologiques et philosophiques se sont distingués au cours du XXe et XXIe siècles, comme Emile Globot (*La Barrière et le Niveau*, 1925), Pierre Bourdieu (*La Distinction. Critique sociale du jugement*, 1979), l'historien Roger Chartier, dans le *Dictionnaire raisonné de la politesse et du savoir-vivre* publié sous la direction d'Alain Mantandon, lequel exploite une dimension qui nous paraît complémentaire qui est celle de l'interculturalité de la politesse dans les différents pays d'Europe.

5. La politesse: facteur d'interculturalité

La politesse est affaire du quotidien, et avant tout de la «présentation de soi».

Avoir un «bon» paraître est primordial car l'aspect esthétique est l'image de votre aspect moral. Il faut être présentable, soigné, proprement habillé car la propreté physique trouve son pendant dans la propreté morale. Ensuite, il y a le principe de l'«harmonie»: celui de savoir combiner, arranger, marier différentes tenues, couleurs et accessoires (Antonin Courtin); harmonie de l'aspect physique comme celui du langage. Puis, il y a le principe de la «discretion» qui est le fondement de la distinction. Une femme distinguée ne doit pas attirer l'attention par sa tenue, son maquillage mais être la plus naturelle possible dans ses manières comme dans son habillement (baronne Staffe). Le dernier principe est celui du

¹² Elias Norbert (1973 [1939]), *La Civilisation des mœurs*, Paris, Calmann-Lévy. Elias Norbert (1975 [1939]), *La Dynamique de l'Occident*, Paris, Calmann-Lévy. Elias Norbert (1985 [1969]), *La Société de cour*, Paris, Flammarion.

«maintien», de la bonne tenue: savoir contrôler son langage, son corps, ses sentiments.

La politesse passe aussi et forcément par l'utilisation de termes comme *bonjour, au revoir, bienvenue, s'il vous plaît, je vous en prie ou merci*, et par des attitudes: sourire à qui vous parle, adapter sa tenue aux circonstances, car la politesse c'est aussi la façon de s'habiller et de se comporter.

A l'aube du XXI^e siècle, dans un monde où les incivilités se côtoient, nous estimons qu'il est nécessaire de posséder et de mettre régulièrement en pratique cet art de vivre ensemble qu'est la politesse. L'utilisation de la politesse est un prérequis identitaire, un code qui est d'abord enseigné par la famille, puis ensuite au niveau éducationnel et lequel est synonyme de culture et de personnalité. En apprenant à respecter les règles de civilité, on apprend aussi l'égalité devant les règles, le respect réciproque, la confiance mutuelle, à être capable d'autodiscipline, à se connaître soi-même. On apprend à se décentrer de sa propre personne et à se préoccuper du bien d'autrui. Cependant pour être poli, il ne suffit pas de connaître et suivre les règles: la «vraie» politesse, c'est celle que l'on ne remarque pas, qui sait se faire oublier, qui paraît naturelle, qui vient du plus profond de soi.

La fonction essentielle de permettre le contact en évitant le minimum de risques aux faces et aux territoires des acteurs demeure dans de nombreuses cultures bien qu'elles peuvent diverger dans leurs pratiques ou selon les dimensions de l'espace, du temps, du contexte de communication lesquelles sont arbitraires, imposés et/ou acquises. Méconnaître ces principes culturels peut engendrer des incompréhensions, malentendus ou conflits. C'est pour cela qu'il est important de les connaître et de savoir les employer au moment importun car toute rencontre entre individus de cultures différentes peuvent tendre à des quiproquos, à des malentendus (D. Picard, «Communication interculturelle et rituels sociaux», *Guide de l'interculturel en formation*, Retz, 1999). Ainsi dans la culture européenne, laisser sa place assise à une personne plus âgée ou enceinte est de coutume et est une forme de politesse, le fait de ne pas cracher dans la rue, de vouvoyer une personne que l'on ne connaît pas ou peu, tenir la porte à la personne qui vous suit, ne pas parler la bouche pleine, ne pas couper la parole, utiliser des formes épistolaires, tels «madame» et «monsieur» et suivre les évolutions (on n'emploie plus le terme de

«Mademoiselle»), utiliser les règles épistolaires lorsqu'on écrit une lettre officielle. En occident, par exemple, dans le face-à-face, on préfère le respect de la vérité alors que dans d'autres cultures ceci peut être mal interprété ou ne porte pas à convenance et donc il est préférable d'utiliser la ruse, l'esquive à la place de la vérité. Ces malentendus peuvent être notion de territoire. Au Danemark, en Espagne ainsi qu'en Belgique, on passe facilement au tutoiement, mais ceci peut choquer un Français trouvant cela trop familier ou de condescendance. Chez les Occidentaux et particulièrement chez les Allemands, on préfère être brefs et précis ce qui est la preuve d'un respect envers l'autre - respect envers son temps et sa personne. La brièveté est incompréhensible et même inadmissible chez les Japonais qui préfère des énoncés plus longs car plus ceux-ci sont longs et plus vous estimez votre interlocuteur. Dans les pays occidentaux, on aime aussi à protéger sa vie privée tandis que les pays asiatiques sont plus enclins à la bonne figure.

De nos jours, les relations et communications inter-nationales, et inter-culturelles appartiennent à notre quotidien. La télévision, internet, l'éducation (apprentissage des langues et cultures étrangères) nous met en contact avec d'autres pays, nations et cultures. Acquérir une compétence interculturelle peut faciliter ces contacts et donc la communication. Pour communiquer avec autrui, la maîtrise parfaite de sa langue ne suffit pas. Il est également indispensable de comprendre le contexte culturel de celui-ci (les attitudes, les systèmes de valeurs, les comportements). «Communiquer, c'est se mettre en scène et théâtraliser une relation, c'est donc actualiser des items sociaux et culturels à travers un comportement langagier (verbal et non verbal) en s'appuyant simultanément sur des stratégies de conformité et de transgression des normes groupales et des références supposées être partagées par les différents membres d'une communauté.» (Abdallah-Pretceille, 1996: 35). Toute culture a des façons différentes de s'exprimer ou bien des variations: « on peut observer des variations sur le plan du volume sonore, de gestion de la prise de parole, des formules de politesse; même le silence se manifeste différemment d'une culture à l'autre. Il est par conséquent approprié de parler de «styles de discours culturellement différents» (Bobinson, 1987).

Acquérir une compétence interculturelle ne veut pas dire être doté d'une multitude d'informations, de données sur la ou les cultures

étrangères. Il faut acquérir aussi un certain nombre de «savoirs», ou plus exactement de «savoir-faire» et «savoir-être» qui vous permettrons de communiquer avec l'autre, d'interagir. L'acquéreur de cette compétence interculturelle doit être avant tout détenteur de connaissances et de pratiques sur sa propre culture, et être aussi capable de ne pas entraver la compréhension de l'autre culture ou l'acquisition de ses compétences nouvelles. Il doit avoir un esprit plutôt ouvert, développer ses capacités d'observation de l'altérité, ne pas se restreindre à ses propres systèmes de valeurs et ne pas juger que selon ses propres normes car cela peut déformer la perception des réalités de l'autre, entraîner des erreurs d'interprétation, des malentendus, des comportements non adéquats.

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